

HellasQCI

Deploying advanced national QCI systems and networks in Greece

Deliverable D5.2

Final report on training activities for academic & research communities

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Abstract: This deliverable presents the training activities carried out within Work Package 5 of the HellasQCI project, focusing on knowledge transfer and skills development in the area of quantum-secured communications. The reported activities address key topics related to Quantum Key Distribution, post-quantum cryptography, hybrid security architectures, and secure communication workflows, combining conceptual instruction with practical demonstrations and hands-on laboratory exercises. Training material produced throughout the project has been consolidated and made available through a centralized online platform, ensuring accessibility and long-term availability of educational resources. The deliverable provides an overview of the scope, content, and outcomes of the training programme and highlights its role in supporting informed adoption and effective use of quantum-safe communication technologies within the HellasQCI project framework.

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List of Acronyms

QCI	Quantum Communication Infrastructure
IT	Information Technologies
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
NKUA	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas
WP	Work Package
EuroQCI	European Quantum Communication Infrastructure
PETRUS	EuroQCI coordination and support action
FSO	Free-Space Optical
OGS	Optical Ground Station
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman
DH	Diffie–Hellman
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
OTP	One Time Pad
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
SPAD	Single Photon Avalanche Detector
QRNG	Quantum Random Number Generators
DV-QKD	Discrete Variable – Quantum Key Distribution
CW	Continuous Wavelength
VOA	Variable Optical Attenuator
PBS	Polarization Beam Splitter
PC	Polarization Controller
WDM	Wavelength Division Multiplexing
SpRS	Spontaneous Raman Scattering
QBER	Quantum Bit Error Rate
ESA	European Space Agency

SKR Secret Key Rate
NRZ Non-Return-to-Zero
LDAP Lightweight directory access protocol
LMS Learning Management System
SNSPD Superconducting Nanowire Single Photon Detector

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the training activities implemented within Work Package 5 of the HellasQCI project, focusing on the development and consolidation of knowledge and practical skills related to quantum-secured communications. The training programme supports the deployment and long-term operation of the national Quantum Communication Infrastructure by addressing the need for qualified personnel capable of understanding, applying, and operating QKD and post-quantum cryptographic technologies in realistic environments.

The documented activities cover a broad range of topics, including cryptographic foundations, security principles, cryptographic attacks and failure modes, QKD systems and network architectures, hybrid QKD–PQC solutions. The training programme combines lectures, workshops, demonstrations, and hands-on laboratory exercises, allowing participants to engage with both conceptual material and concrete implementations using real tools, software components, and deployment scenarios.

All training outputs have been systematically collected and made available through the HellasQCI online training platform, which serves as a centralized repository for educational material produced throughout the project. This approach ensures accessibility, continuity, and long-term availability of training resources, supporting reuse beyond individual events and extending the impact of the training activities.

Overall, this deliverable provides a consolidated account of the WP5 training activities and their outcomes, demonstrating how structured and coordinated training contributes to informed adoption of quantum-safe communication technologies and supports the broader objectives of the HellasQCI project in preparing stakeholders for the deployment and use of a national Quantum Communication Infrastructure.

2. Introduction

This deliverable documents the training activities implemented within Work Package 5 of the HellasQCI project and provides a comprehensive account of their scope, structure, and outcomes. The training programme constitutes a foundational pillar of the project, supporting the development, deployment, and future operation of a national Quantum Communication Infrastructure by strengthening the knowledge base and practical capabilities of the actors involved. As quantum communication technologies introduce new paradigms, assumptions, and operational requirements, targeted and well-structured training is essential to ensure that these technologies are understood, applied correctly, and integrated coherently into existing and emerging communication ecosystems.

The context in which the training activities are carried out is characterized by a rapidly evolving security landscape, where long-term confidentiality and trust cannot rely solely on classical cryptographic mechanisms. Advances in quantum computing, combined with increasing data longevity requirements, create a pressing need for solutions that remain secure over extended time horizons. Within this context, the training activities reported in this deliverable aim to build awareness and competence around QKD, PQC algorithms, and hybrid approaches that combine quantum and classical security mechanisms. The programme reflects the understanding that quantum-secured communications are not isolated components, but part of a broader system that spans physical infrastructure, network services, cryptographic protocols, and application-layer processes.

The scope of the training programme is intentionally broad, addressing the full lifecycle of secure communication systems. The activities begin with foundational concepts in cryptography and security, including threat models, adversarial assumptions, and common failure modes, and progressively move towards more advanced topics such as QKD architectures, key management services, post-quantum encryption and digital signatures, and hybrid deployment scenarios. This progression enables participants to develop a coherent mental model of how individual components interact and how security properties emerge—or fail—at the system level. By covering both established practices and emerging technologies, the training programme supports informed decision-making and critical evaluation of design and deployment choices.

A defining characteristic of the training activities is the emphasis on realism and applicability. Rather than focusing exclusively on abstract descriptions, the programme incorporates demonstrations, practical exercises, and laboratory sessions that expose participants to real software tools, hardware platforms, and operational workflows. These activities include interaction with encryption and decryption services, generation and handling of cryptographic keys, use of standardized interfaces for key distribution, and configuration of secure communication channels. Through these hands-on components, participants experience first-hand how theoretical concepts translate into deployed systems, and how subtle configuration choices or implementation details can have significant security implications.

The training programme also addresses the fact that cryptographic systems often fail not because algorithms are broken, but because they are misused, misconfigured, or embedded in poorly designed processes. For this reason, several training activities explicitly examine cryptographic attacks, failures, and

real-world incidents, illustrating how weaknesses arise from insufficient randomness, improper key management, insecure modes of operation, or incorrect trust assumptions. By analysing such cases, participants are encouraged to adopt a critical and cautious approach when designing and operating secure systems, recognizing that security is an ongoing process rather than a static property.

The activities documented in this deliverable are closely aligned with the architectures, use cases, and pilot deployments developed within the project. Training content is not treated as generic or detached, but is instead grounded in the specific technologies, standards, and integration scenarios that are relevant to the national Quantum Communication Infrastructure. This alignment ensures coherence across work packages and supports a shared understanding of how design decisions and implementation practices affect overall system behaviour. It also facilitates smoother transitions between experimental setups, pilot environments, and operational deployments, reducing the risk of knowledge gaps or inconsistent practices.

An integral element of the training strategy is the systematic organization and dissemination of educational material through the HellasQCI online training platform. All training outputs, including presentations, lecture material, recorded sessions, technical documentation, and laboratory resources, are collected and made accessible through this platform. This approach supports continuity and inclusiveness by allowing participants to revisit content, follow training activities asynchronously, and access material beyond the duration of individual events. It also enables the preservation of knowledge for future use, supporting onboarding of new participants and extending the impact of the training activities beyond the immediate project timeline.

The training programme has been implemented through a sequence of coordinated actions, including workshops, thematic sessions, demonstrations, and hands-on laboratories, each addressing specific aspects of quantum-secured communications. Together, these actions form a coherent body of educational content that reflects the multidisciplinary nature of the field and the diversity of skills required to support a national QCI. By engaging participants with different backgrounds and levels of expertise, the programme contributes to the development of a common vocabulary and shared understanding, which is essential for effective collaboration across organizational and disciplinary boundaries.

This deliverable provides a consolidated record of the training activities carried out under WP5, serving both as documentation of the work performed and as a reference for future capacity-building efforts. It captures not only the topics covered, but also the rationale behind the training design and the relationships between different training actions. By doing so, it supports transparency, traceability, and reuse of the training outcomes, contributing to the broader objectives of the HellasQCI project.

3. Online Training Platform

The HellasQCI online training platform, available at <https://training.hellasqci.eu/> constitutes the central digital infrastructure for the organization, dissemination, and long-term preservation of all training material generated within the framework of the HellasQCI project. It has been designed as a unified and comprehensive learning environment. It supports the educational objectives of the project, addressing the needs of a broad and heterogeneous audience, that includes academic and research staff, early-stage

Figure 3.1: HellasQCI training platform Main Page

researchers, students, cybersecurity professionals, network engineers, IT experts, and other stakeholders involved in quantum communication infrastructures.

The platform provides a single point of access to the training content produced across all HellasQCI training events, originating from QCI Days Athens 2025, hands-on laboratory sessions, as well as-focused technical trainings, in the framework of HellasQCI Training Event Crete 2024, HellasQCI Training Event Athens 2023 and HellasQCI Winter School 2025 in Thessaloniki.

All training material is organised in a structured and easily navigable manner, enabling users to access both theoretical and practical content related to QKD, PQC, quantum networking architectures, space-based

Figure 3.2: HellasQCI Winter School 2025 course

quantum communications, and related enabling technologies. The available resources include **interactive presentation flipbooks**, and recorded video lectures, that support deeper understanding of the topics covered during the physical training events.

Figure 3.3: HellasQCI training platform Flipbook and video presentation example

The presentation material delivered during the training events is published on the platform in **flipbook format**, allowing users to browse slides interactively and follow the structure of each lecture in a user-friendly digital form. The flipbooks are complemented by **on-demand video recordings** of the corresponding lectures. The videos are provided with embedded subtitles in English, and the user can

enable the picture-in-picture mode. This functionality allows the users to “detach” it from its normal page position. It floats in a small, resizable window that stays on top of other windows or tabs. The user can move it around the screen and keep watching while scrolling or working in other apps. Participants are able through the courses to revisit complex concepts, consolidate their knowledge after the completion of an event, and follow training events that they could not attend in person or via livestream.

From an educational perspective, the HellasQCI online training platform operates as a learning management system that supports asynchronous learning and self-paced study, which is particularly important given the multidisciplinary and technically demanding nature of quantum communication technologies. The HellasQCI online training platform enables continuity between different training events by preserving their outputs in a consistent digital format, thus creating a cumulative knowledge base that evolves alongside the project. This approach facilitates progressive learning paths, where users can build on foundational material before engaging with more advanced topics, and supports knowledge transfer across different target groups with varying levels of prior expertise.

Beyond its educational role, the HellasQCI online training platform plays a crucial role in ensuring the sustainability and long-term impact of the HellasQCI training events. All uploaded material is intended to remain accessible throughout the lifetime of the project and beyond its completion, allowing the results of the training programme to continue benefiting the wider community after the end of the funded period. In this way, the platform contributes to the creation of a lasting national knowledge repository that supports the operation, maintenance, and future evolution of quantum communication infrastructures in Greece. By centralizing and preserving the educational outputs of the project, the platform strengthens community building, supports skills development, and enhances the visibility and reusability of the training material produced within HellasQCI.

3.1 Online Training Platform: Scope, Structure and Outcomes

The HellasQCI online training platform constitutes a central pillar of the project’s capacity-building strategy, serving both as a repository of training material and as a dynamic hub connecting the diverse stakeholders involved in the national and European QCI ecosystem. The platform has been designed to support knowledge dissemination, continuous learning and community engagement across the full spectrum of actors participating in HellasQCI-related activities.

A key characteristic of the platform is the diversity of its user ecosystem (Figure 3.4). Moreover, the platform brings together participants from industry, academia, research institutions, public organizations, SMEs and international partners. This heterogeneous composition reflects the interdisciplinary nature of quantum communication technologies and highlights the role of the platform as a meeting point between research, technology development, policy and practical deployment. By addressing the needs of such a broad audience, the platform contributes to the creation of a coherent and sustainable national quantum ecosystem.

Figure 3.4: Composition of the HellasQCI online training platform ecosystem across different types of

Figure 3.5: Strategic communication framework supporting the HellasQCI online training platform and target audiences.

Beyond its educational role, the online training platform is embedded within the broader strategic communication framework of the HellasQCI project. Its operation supports the project's key communication objectives, namely raising awareness on quantum communication technologies, engaging relevant stakeholders, and promoting HellasQCI results at both national and European levels. As shown in

Figure 3.5, the platform is complemented by multiple communication channels, including the official HellasQCI website, newsletters and email campaigns, social media presence and scientific publications. This multi-channel approach ensures consistent visibility of training activities and maximizes outreach to policy makers, academia, research communities, industry stakeholders, and the general public.

Figure 3.6: Distribution of online training platform users by professional role.

The platform has also been actively promoted through targeted communication campaigns and dissemination actions linked to major national and international events. These include participation in flagship conferences and thematic initiatives, as well as the deployment of digital and printed communication material.

Figure 3.7: Distribution of views per thematic activity on the HellasQCI online training platform.

Usage analytics further provide valuable insights into the interests and learning priorities of the platform's users. Strong interest is observed in content related to the EuroQCI initiative and national quantum projects, as well as in modules focusing on QKD network architectures, infrastructure, practical

implementations and demonstrations. This balanced distribution confirms the importance of offering both foundational knowledge and application-oriented material within the training programme.

The platform currently serves a growing user base with diverse professional backgrounds. The majority of users originate from education, academia and technical or engineering roles, while significant participation is also observed from research and innovation professionals, management-level users, and representatives of public institutions. This diversity underlines the platform's role as a horizontal training instrument, capable of addressing different levels of expertise and professional responsibilities within the HellasQCI ecosystem.

Finally, platform access statistics highlight a clear correlation between online engagement and the physical training events organized within the project. A substantial share of platform activity is linked to the HellasQCI Training Athens 2023, while the Training Crete 2024 also generated significant user engagement. At the same time, the observed proportion of users who have not yet accessed the platform provides useful feedback for the design of future dissemination and training actions, with the aim of further increasing participation and long-term platform utilization.

4. HellasQCI Training Athens, September 2023

The 1st HellasQCI workshop for Research and Education communities was held at the premises of the National Technical University of Athens, Greece. The training was designed to provide participants with theoretical and practical knowledge on quantum communication, with the goal of enhancing the security of sensitive data and critical infrastructures in Greece and co-creating EuroQCI.

The 4-day event was launched by the new Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, Konstantinos Karantzalos, followed by welcoming remarks from Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A. The keynote speech, “Quantum Technologies – QKD Landscape in Europe,” was given by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris.

The training was open to cybersecurity professionals, IT managers and engineers, security and IT experts, researchers, students, and practitioners in the field of quantum communication, as well as decision-makers interested in futureproofing their organization’s security infrastructure. Participants could attend in person or via livestream through the GRNET DIAVLOS service. The event had two different thematic axes, namely the “Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems” held on the 18th and 19th of September and the “Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)” held on the 21st and 22nd of September. The two workshops were well-received, with an average of 100 attendees at the first workshop and 75 at the second. In total, 175 unique people attended the workshops. Additionally, an average of 100 people per day participated online via the GRNET Diavlos livestream service. Sixteen trainers provided insights and knowledge on quantum communication.

The content of the **Theoretical Lectures** is provided in the following list:

4.1 “Basic Principles of QKD” by G. M. Nikolopoulos

The talk was aimed at a non-specialized audience and gave an introduction to QKD. After a brief introduction to the so-called key-distribution problem, the presentation focused on the main physical principles underlying the operation and the security of QKD protocols, including the no-cloning theorem, the measurement of quantum states, and the behavior of single-photon states. Subsequently, the presentation revolved around the main stages, as well as possible attacks against ideal QKD protocols. The last part of the talk discussed practical issues which occur when one tries to implement a QKD protocol.

4.2 “QRNGs” by K. Vyrsoinos

This talk was oriented to the presentation of Quantum Random Number Generators that is one of the main components of QKD equipment. The short course started with the general description of Random Number Generators, their classification in pseudo- and true random generators, with the latter ones leading to quantum random number generators. Then a list of optical quantum random generators was presented providing also the physical system of the various entropy sources and the list of performance metrics. Finally, there was a short description of an integrated InP QRNG circuit evaluated by AUTH with subsequent presentation of NIST statistical testing.

4.3 “From billion photons to single photon experimental setups” by G. Giannoulis

This section introduced the principles behind the operation of single-photon blocks included in the quantum layer implementation of QKD system architectures. The short course discussed the main principles and some theoretical topics for implementing photonic blocks in support of the development of polarisation encoded QKD systems and their evaluation through QBER measurements. The purpose of this section was to understand the differences between classical communication and QKD-related setups and the challenges of photonic circuitries and setups in real-world transmission quantum links and QKD network deployments.

4.4 “Theoretical background and equipment description for hands-on experiments” by A. Stathis & A. Ntanos

This section delved deeper into the physical appearance of a simple in-house experimental setup. The objective was to gain practical insights into the common components comprising a QKD system. The short course was divided into four parts. Section 1 focused on the technique enabling classical laser sources to generate single photons. Section 2, covered the principles governing the detection of single photons, discussing the essential characteristics and its associated terminology. Section 3 included classical and quantum signals coexistence over fiber and free space, providing a hands-on demonstration of such an experimental setup. Finally, a comprehensive description of the experimental setup utilized for hands-on lab training was given. This included a discussion on the operational principles of each component, along with details on experimental parameters, methodologies, and outcomes.

4.5 “QKD in Space, satellite-to-ground QKD links” by N. Lyras & A. Ntanos

This section served as an outline of optical satellite communication systems focusing on the QKD in Space. The short course discussed the main principles of optical satellite communication systems focusing on the propagation impairments of the satellite to ground classical optical and quantum links, highlighting the challenges, the mitigation techniques as well as the opportunities for research and development. As a final step a detailed analysis of the link budget of a satellite to ground QKD link was explained, and indicative results were showcased. The purpose of this course was to provide an introduction to the QKD and optical satellite communication systems.

4.6 Hands-on Training of basic principles of QKD at NTUA

The goal of these laboratory activities was the introduction of basic components included in the quantum layer of polarisation-encoded DV-QKD systems as well the implementation of quantum links propagating over wireless FSO links and coexisting with classical data streams in optical fibers. The experimental sessions were installed and were demonstrated at the premises of Photonics Communication Research Laboratory of School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of National Technical University of Athens (**Error! Reference source not found.**). More specifically, the generation of weak coherent states by attenuating laser sources, the manipulation of photon states using simple polarization optics, the polarization analysis and the detection through a pair of InGaAs Single Photon Avalanche Diodes (SPADs). Moreover, a short-distance FSO link was installed via a pair of collimators for showcasing the successful exchange of polarization-encoded states over the air. At the end, the demonstration of an optical telescope suitable for satellite-QKD links was also included, focusing on the coupling between the optical beams and the fiber cores.

Figure 4.1: Photo from the training in Photonics Communications Research Laboratory of NTUA.

Generation of Polarization Encoded single photons

In **Error! Reference source not found.** a single photon exchange setup based on attenuated weak coherent light pulses is illustrated. By using a Continuous Wavelength (CW) laser source emitting at 1550.12 nm, pulses were generated through 10 MHz modulation via a Mach-Zehnder Modulator and attenuated with the use of a Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) to achieve a mean photon number per pulse of $\mu=0.5$. The attenuation stage down to single-photon level was implemented by using a combination of power splitters and variable optical couplers. Optical power monitors were used to calculate the mean photon number of pulse-train. In the presented setup Alice solely prepared vertically polarized photons by using a Polarization Beam Splitter (PBS) in the emission stage. The goal of this demo-experiment was to demonstrate the encoding of single-photon states as well the intensity modulation stage required for controlling the mean photon number of signal/decoy states in QKD protocols.

Figure 4.2: Single-photon exchange setup based on Weak Coherent Light (Alice side).

Polarization Analysis and Detection setup

The polarisation analysis at the quantum receiver station depicted at **Error! Reference source not found.** was demonstrated via the use of a polarisation beam splitter (PBS) providing the analysis on the H/V basis. For the compensation of the polarization drift due to the fiber transmission Polarization Controller (PC) was used, therefore the quantum signal was exclusively directed to one of the two InGaAs SPADs. The detection counts were recorded through the graphical user interface of the pair of SPADs, providing the opportunity to showcase the key parameters of the system detection. The dark count rates of both InGaAs SPADs were recorded in both free-running and gated mode, detection efficiencies of both 10% and 20% were demonstrated, and the essential parameter of dead time was calibrated allowing for different detection

Figure 4.3: Receiver's side (Bob) of the single photon exchange setup containing the SPADs, PBS, and Polarization Controllers.

efficiencies.

Coexistence setup multiplexing classical and QKD signals

To evaluate the performance of QKD signals propagating over telecom fibres carrying classical telecommunication signals, a WDM coexistence setup illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** was installed based on the use of WDM multiplexers and tunable optical bandpass filters. By controlling the power level of classical signals, the noise count rates associated with the generation of Spontaneous Raman Scattering (SpRS) noise photons can be controlled. In this way, the degradation of QBER performance for the polarisation-encoded single-photon exchange links can be measured¹. Different filtering stages based on tuneable bandwidth optical filters were used to highlight the impact of filtering nodes to suppress the presence of SpRS noise count rates in the received detection rates.

¹ A. Ntanos, et al., "Deployment-Oriented Classical/Quantum coexistence in X-haul fiber link for B5G Networks," in *CLEO 2023*, Technical Digest Series (Optica Publishing Group, 2023), paper AM3N.5.

Figure 4.4: WDM Setup for coexisting classical/quantum signals.

FSO-QKD setup using collimators

For the realization of the FSO connection two small-sized air-spaced doublet collimators with a numerical aperture of 24 mm were employed, dedicated for operation within the C-band. The FSO link was set up in laboratory as depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.**, which ensured the protection of the transmission from the outdoor environment. The goal of this experiment was to demonstrate that polarisation-encoded qubits can be successfully transmitted over the air. Stable raw click rates were successfully detected through the pair of SPADs devoted for the quantum receiver circuit, revealing the stability of the single-photon wireless exchange setup which can be used for demonstrating QKD links in short-reach, metropolitan-scale network links.

Figure 4.5: 1.5m FSO link established in PCRL to demonstrate single photon exchange over free space.

Mini Optical telescope for QKD space-segment

The last laboratory session focused on the demonstration of an optical telescope capable of supporting mini optical ground stations for satellite-QKD networks. In support of this concept, a Schmidt-Cassegrain optical telescope of 280mm aperture used for astronomical observation from NOA was shown in the laboratory **Error! Reference source not found.** (left). The key components for making this optical system suitable for earth-to-satellite QKD links were discussed in this session, while emphasis was given on the telescope-to-

fiber coupling mechanism. The optical bench for coupling light from the telescope to single-mode fiber was based on an existing design provided by ESA **Error! Reference source not found.** (right), and it was also b

Figure 4.6: Computerized Commercial telescope with a 28 cm aperture and the prototype of the receiver assembly to couple light into fiber from the telescope.

riefly discussed as part of the mini-OGS demonstration.

4.7 Hands-on Training with commercially available QKD equipment at NKUA

The training focused on introducing commercial QKD systems and simulating real-life configurations. The system employed was a Toshiba QKD4.2-MU/MB pair that implements the Toshiba T12 protocol (efficient BB84 protocol with decoy states and phase encoding). Particularly, the demonstration included a QKD optical link over a 50 km long fiber, highlighting the impact of this link on the overall system. Additionally, a gradual introduction of two optical channels was demonstrated. These channels co-propagated along with the quantum channel over a 14-kilometer fiber link, to show the impact of coexistence on the performance of the QKD pair in terms of Secure Key Rate (SKR) and Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER).

- QKD over 50 km long fiber

The initial experiment involved a 50 km QKD link, as depicted in Figure 4.7

Error! Reference source not found. The quantum channel (1310 nm) of the quantum transmitter (Alice) is multiplexed with two service channels at 1529 nm and 1530 nm. The multiplexed signal, initially passing through a 1:2 coupler at the transmitter (Alice), is then transmitted through a 50 km fiber spool, undergoing a 10 dB attenuation. Additionally, a 5 dB attenuator is applied at Alice's transmitter. The 2:1 splitter is employed to deploy an Optical Spectrum Analyzer (OSA) for monitoring the QKD service signal and the classical laser signal that will be used for the next experiments.

Following the demonstration of the QKD communication over 50 km, we replaced the 50 km fiber link with a 10m fiber link, comparing the performance of the QKD systems in the two different configurations. The trainees had the opportunity to witness the SKR and QBER changes while the system was operating in different setups. The goal of this demonstration was to show the achievable distance of a commercial QKD system and how attenuation impacts the performance of such a system.

Figure 4.8: The QKD setup over the 50 km fiber link presented as a diagram

When the fiber link was 10 m, the Secret Key Rate (SKR) increased due to the lower attenuation (a total loss of 11 dB) it encountered. This contrasts with the implementation with the 50 km fiber link, where an additional 10 dB attenuation led to a total loss of 21dB. Similarly, the Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER) decreased when transitioning from one setup to the other, as illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** below. In the 50 km setup, the QBER is 3.32% with an SKR of 19 kbps.

Figure 4.7: SKR and QBER results for the 50 km topology.

- Quantum and classical optical channels coexistence

In the second experiment of the training, the same QKD pair was utilized, with the quantum channel propagating over a 14 km fiber link instead of the 50 km. In this demonstration we gradually introduced two classical channels in the 14 km link through the 2:1 coupler, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Initially, we applied the QKD setup without activating the two classical optical channels. With this approach, we characterized the link and calculated attenuation introduced by the optical components, which was approximately 13.8 dB. For the integration of the classical channels, we connected a 4:1 coupler on the second line of the 2:1 coupler where Alice is linked.

Figure 4.9: The QKD setup over the 14 km fiber link with two classical channels introduced, presented as a diagram.

The first laser (Laser 1), that was introduced, operated at 1550 nm with a power level of -2 dBm. More specifically, it was modulated with Non-Return-to-Zero (NRZ) modulation by using a Mach–Zehnder interferometer. This modulation was designed to emulate a real-life modulated optical channel at a frequency of 10 GHz. After some minutes, when the QKD system had stabilized, we inserted the second laser (Laser2). This laser operated at 1549 nm with a power level of -2.5 dBm and functioned as a continuous wave laser (CW).

We investigated the impact of coexistence by gradually activating lasers. Upon activating the first laser, we observed a degradation in QKD performance, affecting both Secret Key Rate (SKR) and Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER). This observation is supported by an increase in noise levels measured in the range of 1276 nm to 1326 nm, as detected by the OSA. The broad spectrum of the lasers, generating photons also in the 1310 nm channel, contributed to this outcome, impacting negatively on the QKD performance. The same behavior occurred upon activating the second laser, which resulted in further degradation in terms of SKR and QBER. The goal for this experiment was to witness how the coexistence of classical optical channels introduced interference and disturbances, leading to an overall increase in total noise leading to decreased SKR. This is a common scenario, which is commonly encountered in experiments investigating the integration of QKD in optical networks.

All the aforementioned experimental scenarios were demonstrated during the hands-on sessions of the 1st HellasQCI workshop. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a photo of the Photonics Lab from NKUA during this training session.

Figure 4.10: Photo from the training in the Photonics lab of NKUA.

4.8 “The context of Cryptography” by H. Manifavas

The presentation provided a foundational overview of the role and limitations of cryptography within the broader field of cybersecurity, emphasizing that cryptography was a critical but partial component of secure system design. It highlighted that security systems operated in adversarial environments, where intelligent and adaptive attackers sought the weakest link, making holistic risk analysis, protection in depth, and well-defined threat models essential. The material stressed the need for a “security mindset” or professional paranoia, encouraging designers to think like attackers while remaining constructive and realistic. It underlined that cryptography alone could not solve security problems if it was poorly applied, embedded in weak systems, or used to create a false sense of security, and that even well-designed cryptographic systems could become obsolete as technology and attack capabilities evolved. Finally, the presentation introduced the concept of security levels, distinguishing between computational and information-theoretic security, and concluded that building robust, long-lived secure systems required careful design trade-offs, simplicity, continuous evaluation, and a deep understanding of both cryptographic mechanisms and the wider system context.

4.9 “Cryptographic Primitives” by H. Manifavas

The presentation offered a comprehensive introduction to the core cryptographic primitives that underpin modern secure communication systems, covering symmetric cryptography, public-key cryptography, and cryptographic hash functions. It explained how symmetric encryption provided efficient confidentiality for data at rest and in transit, while highlighting its main limitations, particularly the challenges of secure key distribution, key management, and the lack of nonrepudiation. The material discussed block ciphers and

modes of operation, illustrating how inappropriate choices, such as the use of ECB mode, could lead to information leakage and integrity failures, whereas more robust modes like CBC mitigated some of these risks. Public-key cryptography was presented as a complementary technology that enabled secure key exchange, authentication, and digital signatures, despite its higher computational cost, and the role of public key infrastructures and certificates in establishing trust was clearly outlined. The concept of hybrid encryption was introduced to demonstrate how asymmetric and symmetric schemes were combined in real-world protocols to balance security and performance. Finally, the presentation covered cryptographic hash functions, detailing their security properties, such as pre-image and collision resistance, and their widespread applications in integrity protection, authentication, password storage, and blockchain technologies. Through practical demonstrations and hands-on labs, the material emphasized that secure systems depended not only on strong algorithms but also on correct implementation choices, sound key management, and an understanding of cryptographic trade-offs.

4.10 “Cryptographic Attacks & Failures” by H. Manifavas

The presentation examined the main categories of cryptographic attacks and real-world cryptographic failures, highlighting how theoretical security guarantees could be undermined by weak assumptions, poor implementation, or operational mistakes. It introduced classical attack models such as ciphertext-only and known-plaintext attacks, explaining how attackers exploited patterns, redundancy, or predictable content to recover information or cryptographic keys. Brute-force attacks were discussed in detail, illustrating how key length directly impacted security, while also emphasizing that longer keys alone did not guarantee protection if randomness, implementation quality, or system design were flawed. The material further analyzed the security of public-key algorithms, focusing on the mathematical hardness assumptions behind RSA and the factoring problem, and explained how advances in algorithms, hardware, and the emergence of quantum computing challenged long-term security assumptions. Man-in-the-middle and replay attacks were presented as protocol-level threats that exploited missing authentication, poor session management, or lack of freshness in communications. A series of case studies highlighted incidents such as ransomware failures caused by low entropy, major data breaches resulting from hardcoded credentials or weak random number generation, and the use of short cryptographic keys. These examples showed that many serious security breaches were not due to flawed algorithms, but rather to the improper implementation of cryptography in complex systems, emphasizing the importance of sound design, effective key management, and realistic threat modeling.

4.11 “Cryptographic Failures: Case Studies” by E. Papadogiannakis

The hands-on training session provided an extensive, practice-oriented exploration of cryptographic failures and real-world applications of cryptography, emphasizing how theoretical security mechanisms could be compromised by implementation errors, misconfiguration, and operational misuse. Through a structured sequence of demonstrations and laboratories, the material guided participants through common attack scenarios, including eavesdropping on unencrypted network traffic, brute-forcing and dictionary attacks on poorly protected passwords, and bypassing authentication mechanisms using weaknesses in JSON Web Tokens and RSA-based digital signatures. Key management challenges were examined in depth, highlighting the risks of hardcoded or poorly protected cryptographic keys and introducing more robust approaches

such as key derivation functions, encrypted storage, and secret sharing schemes, illustrated through practical case studies involving modern browsers and secure vault systems. The session further analyzed cipher misconfiguration issues, showing how insecure encryption modes, key reuse, and improper padding could lead to information leakage, as demonstrated by high-profile incidents such as the Adobe password database breach. Additional laboratories addressed man-in-the-middle attacks, certificate misuse, and the critical role of high-quality randomness in cryptographic systems, using historical and contemporary examples to illustrate how weak random number generators could undermine otherwise secure protocols. Finally, benchmarking exercises compared the performance and security trade-offs of symmetric and asymmetric algorithms, reinforcing the idea that effective cryptographic protection required not only strong algorithms, but also correct usage, sound system design, and an awareness of evolving threats, including those posed by advances in computing technologies such as quantum computing.

4.12 “Practice session: labs and exercises” by A. Korakis, G. Balaskas, H. Papadopoulos

The practical lab session focused on hands-on experimentation with PQC and QKD-enabled secure communication, guiding participants through the full workflow of generating, managing, and using post-quantum digital signatures in a realistic operational environment. Participants were instructed to install the required software tools and configure their systems before generating post-quantum digital signature key pairs based on the Dilithium algorithm, illustrating core concepts of post-quantum authentication and trust establishment. The lab then demonstrated how public keys were distributed and registered with a QKD-enabled encryptor service, highlighting the interaction between end-user applications and secure network components. Through the EndUserApp, participants performed encryption and decryption operations using PQC mechanisms combined with QKD-derived key identifiers, showing how plaintext data could be securely encrypted, transferred, and decrypted by authorized users. The exercise emphasized practical aspects such as key handling, application configuration, and interoperability between PQC algorithms and QKD infrastructure, reinforcing the role of post-quantum digital signatures in securing communication endpoints. Overall, the session bridged theoretical PQC concepts with concrete implementation steps, providing participants with direct experience of how PQC and QKD technologies could be combined to deliver end-to-end secure communication in future-proof cryptographic systems.

4.13 “QKD_PQC Demonstrations” by A. Korakis, G. Balaskas, H. Papadopoulos

The presentation described a comprehensive set of demonstrations showcasing the integration of QKD and PQC within a realistic pilot deployment focused on secure healthcare data exchange. It outlined the architecture and objectives of the NCSR pilot, which connected NCSR Demokritos with Alexandra Hospital via dedicated optical fibre, aiming to enhance the security of cloud-based Electronic Health Records through hybrid QKD–PQC mechanisms. The material explained how QKD was used as a trusted key source within a key management service, delivering 256-bit symmetric keys to encryptors via standardized ETSI REST interfaces, while PQC algorithms—specifically Kyber for encryption and Dilithium for digital signatures—secured user-to-encryptor communications and provided authentication and authorization. Two main operational scenarios were presented: one combining QKD-secured key exchange with homomorphic encryption to enable privacy-preserving medical data analysis by external AI servers, and another demonstrating hybrid QKD–PQC secure communication between users and servers. Detailed workflows

illustrated encryption and decryption processes, key retrieval using QKD Key IDs, and secure data transmission over public networks, supported by practical software and hardware implementations on Raspberry Pi-based encryptors. Overall, the demonstrations validated the feasibility, interoperability, and added value of combining QKD, PQC, and advanced cryptographic techniques to deliver future-proof, high-assurance security for sensitive data sharing and processing in healthcare and other critical sectors.

4.14 “Trainings in QCI and QKD systems and networks” by A. Korakis

The presentation focused on a detailed demonstration of a QKD-enabled encryptor within the context of WP5 training activities, illustrating how QKD and PQC could be combined to deliver secure, application-level data protection. It presented a generic yet realistic architecture for organizations that needed to exchange sensitive data, such as hospitals, governmental bodies, financial institutions, and research centers, using QKD over optical links and PQC-secured communications over public networks. The workflow described how users digitally signed and encrypted data using post-quantum algorithms (Dilithium for signatures and Kyber for encryption) before interacting with a QKD encryptor, which retrieved unique 256-bit symmetric keys from a QKD Key Management System via standardized ETSI REST interfaces. These keys were then used for AES-256 encryption, with key identifiers enabling secure decryption by authorized recipients. The presentation further detailed the encryptor’s software and hardware specifications, its REST-based encryption and decryption services, and its integration with QKD devices, highlighting interoperability, access control, and standardized interfaces. Overall, the demo provided a clear, end-to-end view of how QKD-derived keys and PQC mechanisms could be practically deployed together to support secure data exchange across heterogeneous networks, reinforcing the applicability of quantum-safe technologies in real-world operational environments.

4.15 HellasQCI Training Athens 2023: Scope, Structure and Outcomes

The HellasQCI Training Athens 2023 constituted the first large-scale training activity implemented within the framework of Work Package 5, targeting the academic, research and cybersecurity communities. The training event was organized in September 2023 and hosted at the premises of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), leveraging advanced laboratory infrastructure to combine theoretical instruction with hands-on experimental training.

The training programme was officially launched with a welcoming and plenary session hosted at NTUA, bringing together representatives from national authorities, the European Commission and the HellasQCI consortium. High-level keynote and introductory presentations provided an overview of the European QKD landscape and positioned HellasQCI within the broader EuroQCI initiative. This opening session established a common reference framework for participants with diverse backgrounds and levels of expertise.

The training was structured as a four-day programme and organized along two complementary thematic axes. The first axis focused on QKD systems and fundamental quantum communication principles, addressing primarily researchers, students and academic staff. The second axis targeted cybersecurity experts and IT professionals, with emphasis on the integration of QKD systems into cybersecurity architectures and the coexistence of QKD with PQC solutions. This dual-track structure ensured that the

content was tailored to the specific needs of each target audience, while maintaining coherence across the overall training objectives.

The theoretical component of the training consisted of a series of lectures covering core topics such as the basic principles of QKD, quantum random number generators, QKD network architectures, single-photon experimental setups and space-based QKD links. These lectures provided participants with a solid conceptual foundation, combining physical principles, protocol-level considerations and practical implementation challenges. Particular emphasis was placed on bridging theoretical knowledge with real-world deployment scenarios.

Figure 4.11 Summary of the HellasQCI Training Event in Athens.

A central element of the HellasQCI Training Athens 2023 was the extensive hands-on laboratory training conducted at the Photonics Communications Research Laboratory of NTUA. During these sessions, participants were introduced to the fundamental building blocks of polarization-encoded DV-QKD systems, including single-photon generation using attenuated laser sources, polarization manipulation, single-photon detection and quantum link characterization. The laboratory activities enabled trainees to observe and evaluate key system parameters such as detection rates, polarization stability and Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER).

Further experimental demonstrations focused on free-space optical quantum communication links and the coexistence of quantum and classical signals over optical fibres. Participants were able to observe the transmission of polarization-encoded single photons over short free-space links and to investigate the impact of classical channel interference on QKD performance. These demonstrations highlighted practical challenges related to noise, attenuation and filtering in realistic network scenarios. Complementary hands-on training sessions were conducted at the photonics laboratories of NKUA, focusing on commercial QKD equipment operating over metropolitan-scale fibre links. Participants observed the operation of a commercial QKD system under different configurations, including varying fibre lengths and scenarios with co-propagating classical optical channels. These experiments demonstrated the impact of attenuation and channel coexistence on Secure Key Rate and Quantum Bit Error Rate, offering valuable insights into the integration of QKD systems into existing optical network infrastructures.

The HellasQCI Training Athens 2023 attracted strong participation from the national and international quantum communication community. Approximately 175 unique participants attended the training activities in person over the four days, while additional participants followed the sessions remotely through live streaming services. This hybrid format significantly extended the outreach of the training event and reinforced the role of HellasQCI as a national hub for quantum communication training and awareness. Overall, the HellasQCI Training Athens 2023 represented a key milestone for the project. It validated the training methodology adopted within WP5, demonstrated the effectiveness of combining theoretical instruction with hands-on experimentation and provided critical feedback for the refinement of future training activities. The experience gained through this first training event directly informed the design of subsequent HellasQCI trainings and contributed to the enrichment of the online training platform

5. HellasQCI Training Crete, September 2024

The 3rd HellasQCI Training Event entitled “Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security” was organized on the 4th and 5th of September 2024 in the city of Heraklion, Crete, on the grounds of the HellasQCI training series. The event provided useful information and training on advanced QKD technologies, cyber security integration, and EuroQCI-related developments, targeting research communities, cybersecurity experts, IT professionals, and stakeholders involved in the deployment and operation of quantum communication infrastructures.

The training combined high-level strategic discussions with in-depth technical sessions and hands-on laboratory demonstrations. The agenda was structured to cover PQC and QKD, practical implementation challenges, and real-world deployment scenarios, ensuring a comprehensive overview of the current status and future directions of quantum-secured communications.

Figure 5.1 Opening and high-level sessions of the HellasQCI Training Crete Sep 2024 hosted at FORTH in Heraklion.

The first day focused primarily on strategic perspectives, European initiatives, and system-level considerations. The event opened with a registration and welcoming session, followed by official opening remarks from representatives of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, GRNET, and the HellasQCI consortium. An overview of the two-day HellasQCI training program was presented, setting the context for the technical sessions that followed.

Key presentations addressed the status of EuroQCI and national QCI initiatives, highlighting synergies between HellasQCI and European projects such as PETRUS, Nostradamus, and other EuroQCI-related actions. A dedicated session examined the challenges ahead on the road to a pan-European QCI, covering topics such as standardization, interoperability, scalability, and long-term sustainability of quantum communication infrastructures. A panel discussion brought together representatives from academia,

research institutions, and industry to discuss technological, operational, and policy-related aspects of QCI deployment.

The afternoon sessions of the first day focused on architectural aspects of QKD systems and networks. Presentations covered QKD architectures, including trusted-node and end-to-end models, as well as key management layers and application-layer integration. Emphasis was placed on how QKD can be effectively combined with classical cryptographic mechanisms and existing network infrastructures to enhance security for critical applications.

The second day of the training event was dedicated to advanced technical topics and hands-on activities. The morning sessions discussed the complementary roles of PQC and QKD in future-proof security architectures. Technical lectures addressed photonic blocks for QKD, including sources, modulators, detectors, and stabilization mechanisms, as well as techniques for free-space and fiber-based quantum communication links.

The second day also featured practical demonstrations and laboratory-based training. Participants were introduced to experimental polarization-encoded QKD setups, both in physical laboratory environments and through virtual lab demonstrations. These sessions covered polarization analysis, system calibration, and performance evaluation, allowing participants to gain hands-on experience with key operational aspects of QKD systems.

Additional sessions focused on the coexistence of QKD with classical communication channels and on cybersecurity use cases enabled by quantum-secured key distribution. Real-world deployment scenarios were discussed, including the integration of QKD into existing network infrastructures and its application in critical sectors. The day concluded with a visit to a research observatory, providing participants with further exposure to optical and photonic technologies relevant to quantum communication. Below, a more detailed description of each individual talk and session is provided.

5.1 “EuroQCI Projects: PETRUS, NOSTRADAMUS” by R. Sebastian & H. Hübel

Petrus

The presentation introduced PETRUS as the Coordination and Support Action of the Digital Europe Programme, with the mandate to coordinate the first deployment of national EuroQCI projects and to prepare the large-scale QKD testing and certification infrastructure. It situated PETRUS within the wider EuroQCI ecosystem, which comprises 26 national deployment projects, six product development projects, one testing and validation infrastructure project, and PETRUS itself as the central coordination activity. The slides traced the origins of PETRUS back to earlier system architecture and design studies on quantum communication infrastructures, highlighting its role in moving from studies and demonstrations toward coordinated, operational deployment across Europe. This coordination role is illustrated through early full-stack demonstrations, such as the Mini-EuroQCI prototype shown at the 2024 European Quantum Technologies Conference (ECOC 2024) in Hanover, which demonstrated interoperability among different QKD technologies, vendors, and protocols through a vendor-independent key management and control layer enabling end-to-end quantum-safe services.

The second part of the presentation focused on PETRUS's ongoing activities and working structures aimed at enabling an end-to-end operational EuroQCI. It presented the EuroQCI Thematic Working Groups (ETWG) as a core mechanism for developing a coherent roadmap, architecture, interoperability framework, use cases, and governance models, following a holistic "5P" approach covering people, process, provider, product, and platform. The slides outlined PETRUS activities in 2024, including national deployment surveys, stakeholder engagement through one-to-one meetings and forums, educational sessions, dissemination actions, and continued roadmap development based on survey results and working group outputs. The presentation concluded with forward-looking announcements of upcoming EuroQCI-related events and workshops, reinforcing PETRUS's role as a central facilitator aligning national deployments, industrial efforts, and European policy objectives toward the full deployment of EuroQCI

Nostradamus

The presentation introduced the NOSTRADAMUS project as a European effort to define and implement testing, evaluation, and validation infrastructure for QKD devices within the EuroQCI context. Its core objective is to develop a blueprint for a Testing and Validation Infrastructure capable of supporting the evaluation and certification of QKD technologies, while also operating a prototypical testbed that can deliver initial evaluation services required for accreditation by European security authorities. The slides motivated this need by recalling early QKD implementations, where weaknesses in protocol and physical implementations led to side-channel vulnerabilities, illustrating that implementation security is as critical as theoretical security. The consortium composition was presented as deliberately diverse, bringing together telecom operators, research institutes, industry, metrology bodies, licensed IT security evaluation facilities, and technology transfer experts to ensure a holistic and certification-oriented approach aligned with EuroQCI and IRIS needs.

The second part of the presentation detailed the methodological approach of NOSTRADAMUS, including its phased work plan from 2024 to 2027 and the prioritisation of side-channel attacks relevant to European QKD deployments. A structured vulnerability analysis was described, based on a comprehensive matrix of known attacks and countermeasures from the literature, followed by a three-step prioritisation process that filters attacks by relevance, feasibility, and the effectiveness of available countermeasures. The project's role in evaluation and certification was explained through its contribution to security assurance activities, such as functional testing, vulnerability analysis, and robustness testing of the quantum channel, which require non-standard equipment and methods not currently available in most evaluation labs. The presentation concluded by identifying key challenges ahead, including the limited maturity of quantum hacking research, the lack of commercially available attack tools, and restricted access to test vehicles, and positions NOSTRADAMUS as a foundation for establishing a European security baseline, attack catalogue, and testing capability for future QKD product certification.

5.2 "Why QKD?" by H. Manifavas

This presentation built a unified narrative explaining why QKD is being considered a strategic security technology today, starting from the fundamental fragility of classical cryptography in the face of accelerating computational power and the anticipated impact of quantum computers. It highlighted how current public-key systems rely on mathematical assumptions that can be invalidated by quantum

algorithms, enabling scenarios such as retrospective decryption where intercepted data becomes readable years later, and contrasts this with QKD's physics-based security model, in which any eavesdropping attempt necessarily disturbs the quantum states and can be detected in real time. Within this framework, QKD was presented not as a data transmission method but as a key distribution mechanism that complements classical symmetric encryption, supports forward secrecy, and offers information-theoretic security independent of adversarial computational capabilities. The presentation traced the evolution of QKD from early theoretical proposals such as BB84 and entanglement-based protocols, through experimental and commercial deployments over fiber, free-space, and satellites, to current niche applications in finance, government, critical infrastructure, and healthcare. At the same time, it adopted a deliberately realistic tone by emphasizing practical challenges, including distance limitations, cost, scalability, integration with existing networks, slow key rates, lack of mature standards, and the gap between ideal security proofs and implementation-level vulnerabilities such as side-channel attacks. Rather than promoting QKD as a standalone solution, the presentation positioned it as one component of a broader quantum-safe strategy alongside PQC, shaped not only by technical progress but also by geopolitical priorities, digital sovereignty, and long-term policy decisions. It concluded by linking near-term deployments to longer-term visions such as satellite constellations, hybrid quantum–classical networks, and the quantum internet, framing QKD as a proactive, forward-looking response to future security threats rather than a reaction once quantum computers are already ubiquitous.

5.3 “QKD Architecture: Quantum Layer” by G. Giannoulis

This presentation offered a deep, physics-driven walk-through of the quantum layer in prepare-and-measure QKD systems, using BB84 as the reference framework and deliberately focusing on what happens on the quantum channel rather than on protocol abstractions. It explained how secure key generation emerges from the controlled preparation, transmission, and measurement of single-photon states over mutually unbiased bases, with true randomness supplied by quantum random number generators and security enforced by fundamental principles such as superposition, Heisenberg uncertainty, and the no-cloning theorem. The slides progressively moved from the abstract Hilbert-space description of qubits to concrete photonic implementations, showing how polarization, phase, time-bin, or frequency encoding can be realized in practice, with particular emphasis on time-bin encoding as used in HellasQCI systems at that time. Considerable attention was given to the physical creation of quantum states using weak coherent pulses, the statistical nature of photon emission, and the unavoidable gap between idealized protocols and real hardware. This gap was quantified through the Quantum Bit Error Rate, which is introduced not only as a theoretical security parameter but as a practical diagnostic tool shaped by non-ideal optics, polarization misalignment, basis rotation, detector imperfections, and noise introduced by coexistence with classical signals. The presentation then systematically connected laboratory measurements of QBER to concrete mitigation strategies in the spectral, temporal, and spatial domains, such as filtering spontaneous Raman scattering, tightening detection windows, improving synchronization, and optimizing fiber–free-space coupling, all under the unifying principle of “closing the QKD window” to suppress noise. Overall, the narrative made clear that QKD security at the quantum layer is not a binary property guaranteed by theory alone, but the outcome of careful photonic engineering, calibration, and continuous error management,

where physics, hardware design, and system-level trade-offs jointly determine whether the promised security of QKD can be realized in real deployments.

5.4 “QKD Architecture: Key Management Layer” by G. Kanellos

This presentation developed a system-level view of how QKD scales beyond isolated links by focusing on the key management layer as the central enabler of operational QKD networks, using HellasQCI as a concrete reference architecture. It started from the fundamental limitations of point-to-point QKD links, such as distance, attenuation, noise sensitivity, and the need for trusted nodes, and showed how these constraints drive the introduction of structured key relay mechanisms and layered network architectures. Within this context, the role of the Key Management Architecture was described as the glue between quantum hardware and real applications, handling key storage, relay, synchronization, authentication, lifecycle management, and secure delivery to cryptographic services, while remaining aligned with international standards such as ITU-T Y.3803 and the ETSI QKD specification suite. The presentation explained how software-defined networking concepts are applied to QKD through SDN controllers and orchestrators, enabling dynamic configuration, centralized control, multi-domain coordination, and end-to-end service provisioning across heterogeneous vendors and technologies. These architectural concepts were grounded in the Athens proof-of-concept deployment, where a three-node quantum-secure network integrated commercial QKD systems, Nokia optical transport equipment, and an advanced key management system to demonstrate interoperable operation, optimized key usage, and coordinated orchestration across application, key management, and quantum layers. The validated architecture illustrated how QKD-derived keys and quantum-safe classical keys can coexist to ensure service continuity, how key consumption adapts to real-time availability, and how standardized interfaces enable interoperability, positioning HellasQCI as a national-scale backbone that extends current state of the art and forms a practical stepping stone toward more advanced quantum networking concepts such as entanglement distribution and, ultimately, the quantum internet.

5.5 “QKD Architecture: Application Layer” by H. Papadopoulos

This presentation framed the application layer as the point where quantum-safe technologies translate into usable services for real organizations, emphasizing that cryptographic strength only becomes meaningful when it is correctly integrated into applications, workflows, and operational environments. It started from classical cryptographic goals—confidentiality, integrity, authentication, and non-repudiation—and explained how their traditional realization through public-key cryptography is fundamentally challenged by quantum computing, motivating the shift toward quantum-safe approaches that combine PQC and QKD. Rather than positioning QKD as a standalone solution, the presentation consistently promoted hybrid architectures in which QKD supplies high-quality symmetric keys, PQC provides quantum-resistant key encapsulation and digital signatures, and classical cryptography ensures backward compatibility and operational continuity during migration. This approach was grounded in practical considerations such as denial-of-service risks, trusted nodes, cost, certification gaps, and the immaturity of QKD implementations, all of which argue for layered, crypto-agile systems instead of abrupt replacements. The presentation then moved from principles to concrete designs, illustrating how QKD–PQC hybrids can be deployed in sensitive domains like healthcare through pilot architectures that integrate QKD links, key management interfaces

compliant with ETSI standards, PQC algorithms such as Kyber and Dilithium, and familiar application-layer technologies including TLS, REST services, WebSockets, and hardware security modules. Detailed scenarios showed how encryption and authentication can be realized either via dedicated encryptors or directly within client applications using key extractors, pseudo-one-time-pad constructions, and key derivation functions, demonstrating end-to-end protection for messaging, file transfer, and secure data storage. The overall narrative made clear that adopting quantum-safe security is not only a cryptographic upgrade but an organizational transformation requiring planning, standardization, interoperability, training, and gradual migration, with the application layer acting as the decisive bridge between advanced quantum technologies and their reliable, regulated use in real-world systems.

5.6 “Introduction to PQC–QKD Transition” by H. Manifavas

This presentation provided a comprehensive, risk-driven overview of PQC as the primary mitigation path against the long-term cybersecurity impact of quantum computing, grounding the discussion in both realistic capabilities and unavoidable uncertainty. It explained how quantum computers, while still limited and highly specialized, fundamentally change the threat model for cryptography by enabling algorithms such as Shor’s and Grover’s, which undermine public-key cryptography and weaken symmetric schemes, respectively, giving rise to scenarios like retrospective decryption where today’s intercepted data may be compromised decades later. The material carefully distinguished between hype and reality by introducing the notion of a cryptographically relevant quantum computer, acknowledging that such systems are not imminent while arguing that long migration timelines make early action unavoidable. Against this backdrop, PQC was presented as a pragmatic, software-based response that can run on existing infrastructure, integrate with current protocols, and protect both confidentiality and authentication through new key encapsulation and digital signature schemes. The presentation walked through the NIST PQC standardization effort, its evaluation criteria, security levels, algorithm diversity, and recent milestones, while also highlighting setbacks such as broken candidates and the importance of avoiding premature lock-in. Beyond algorithms, strong emphasis was placed on transition planning, regulatory guidance, and cryptographic agility, framing quantum safety as a system property rather than a one-time upgrade. The narrative concluded by stressing that organizations must inventory their cryptography, assess data longevity, adopt hybrid solutions during transition phases, and design systems that can evolve as standards, threats, and technologies mature, positioning PQC not as a speculative future option but as a necessary component of responsible, long-term cybersecurity strategy.

5.7 “Authentication in QKD” by G. M. Nikolopoulos

This presentation focused on authentication as a critical yet often understated pillar of QKD security, demonstrating that without proper authentication, even information-theoretically secure QKD protocols remain vulnerable to man-in-the-middle attacks. It showed that authentication is required throughout all classical communication stages of QKD, including sifting, error verification, coordination of privacy amplification, and final key confirmation.

The presentation explained why information-theoretic security in QKD strictly requires unconditionally secure message authentication codes (MACs), rather than computationally secure alternatives. It reviewed

the use of Wegman–Carter MACs based on almost strongly universal hash functions, emphasizing that their security fundamentally relies on the existence of a pre-shared secret key. Furthermore, it highlighted that the required authentication key material must scale with usage, creating practical challenges in multi-user environments and large-scale QKD deployments.

To address this bootstrapping and scalability problem, the presentation introduced Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) as a hardware-assisted mechanism for generating and managing pre-shared keys. A concrete scheme was described in which paired PUFs, challenge–response databases, and one-time-use entries enable the secure derivation of authentication keys without exposing those keys to users, software, or adversaries.

The discussion then extended authentication beyond classical communication to quantum messages themselves, clarifying that quantum authentication inherently requires encryption and that quantum message authentication codes do not provide advantages over classical unconditionally secure MACs when protecting classical data.

Finally, the presentation situated authentication within hybrid security architectures, outlining PQC–based authentication approaches using certificates, nonces, and post-quantum digital signatures. In this context, authentication was presented as a flexible and composable security layer where information-theoretic, hardware-based, and post-quantum methods can coexist—depending on operational constraints and threat models—to ensure that the secrecy promised by QKD is preserved in real-world systems.

5.8 “Demo of QKD Networks” by K. Tsimvrakidis

This presentation documented the Athens Proof-of-Concept quantum network as a concrete, end-to-end demonstration of how QKD can be integrated into a fully operational communication stack, moving beyond theory into real data encryption under realistic network conditions. It described a three-node ring deployment connecting GRNET and two NKUA sites, built as a vertically integrated architecture spanning the quantum, key management, and service layers, and deliberately optimized to minimize QKD hardware requirements through relayed operation. The demo illustrated how the service layer supports L1, L2, and L3 encryption, with OTNsec encapsulating all traffic while maintaining backward compatibility with classical schemes and enabling hybrid operation with post-quantum–safe keys. At the core of the experiment was the interaction between commercial QKD systems implementing BB84 with different physical encodings and a standards-compliant KMS that managed key buffers, synchronization, and delivery to secure application entities via ETSI-defined interfaces. The presentation highlighted stable operation under normal conditions, showing how quantum keys are generated, stored, and consumed in real time, and then deliberately introduces failure scenarios, such as a simulated KMS attack, to demonstrate network resilience: when QKD-derived keys can no longer reach the encryptors, the orchestration layer automatically switches to classical quantum-safe keys to preserve service continuity. By encrypting and decrypting live traffic over high-capacity optical links and validating recovery mechanisms, the Athens PoC demonstrated not only the feasibility of multi-layer QKD integration but also the operational maturity required for real-world deployment, reinforcing the role of HellasQCI as a practical steppingstone toward resilient, hybrid quantum-secured networks rather than a purely experimental showcase.

5.9 “Extracting and Managing Keys from QKD to Enhance Cryptographic Techniques for File Encryption” (Lab) by H. Papadopoulos

This lab-focused presentation bridged cryptographic theory and hands-on practice by demonstrating how QKD-derived keys can be extracted, managed, and directly consumed by real encryption applications, emphasizing that quantum security ultimately depends on how keys are handled at the application interface. It revisited the foundations of symmetric and public-key cryptography, digital signatures, hashing, and certificates to establish why key distribution and trust management are persistent weaknesses in classical systems and then showed how QKD addresses these weaknesses by supplying high-quality symmetric keys through a standardized network architecture. The core of the presentation was a step-by-step walkthrough of accessing QKD devices via ETSI-compliant REST interfaces, authenticating clients with certificates, requesting fresh keys or retrieving them by key ID, and securely delivering them to encryptors implemented on practical platforms such as software clients, hardware security modules, or lightweight devices. Through live demonstrations and simulator-based exercises, participants saw how QKD keys are integrated into common encryption schemes—including AES in multiple modes, ChaCha20-Poly1305, and one-time-pad or pseudo-OTP constructions—and how the same keys can be used consistently for encryption and decryption workflows. By exposing the full path from quantum key generation to file and message encryption, including authentication, certificate handling, and key lifecycle management, the presentation made clear that QKD’s value lies not only in the quantum channel but in the disciplined engineering of interfaces, protocols, and applications that transform raw quantum keys into usable, auditable, and secure cryptographic services suitable for real-world deployment

5.10 “QKD-PQC: Securing Key Transfers for Application Layer Utilization” by H. Papadopoulos

This presentation presented a comprehensive, application-oriented view of how QKD and PQC can be combined to securely deliver and use cryptographic keys at the application layer, addressing both near-term and long-term quantum threats. It started by acknowledging the limitations of classical public-key cryptography in the presence of quantum computers and positions PQC, particularly lattice-based schemes such as CRYSTALS-Kyber and CRYSTALS-Dilithium, as the primary software-based mitigation endorsed by NIST, while recognizing that QKD offers information-theoretic security for symmetric keys but is still operationally constrained and best suited for controlled or niche deployments. Building on this, the presentation advocated a hybrid QKD–PQC approach in which QKD supplies high-entropy symmetric keys, PQC secures key transport, authentication, and authorization, and classical symmetric encryption algorithms such as AES, ChaCha20-Poly1305, or one-time-pad variants protect the data itself. The core of the material was a detailed set of end-to-end workflows showing how application-layer clients interact with QKD extractors and KMS components via ETSI-compliant interfaces, using PQC-based encryption and digital signatures to request, authorize, transfer, and retrieve QKD keys over untrusted networks. Multiple realistic scenarios are explored, including secure file transfer, messaging, and web-based data storage, with concrete examples drawn from healthcare environments where encrypted data, key identifiers, and digital signatures are exchanged over public infrastructure while maintaining strong security guarantees. The presentation also highlighted practical considerations such as performance overhead, implementation

risks, certificate management, and standardization gaps, reinforcing the need for crypto-agile designs that allow gradual migration rather than disruptive replacement. Overall, it demonstrated how QKD and PQC can be engineered together into usable, standards-aligned application-layer services, transforming quantum-safe cryptography from an abstract concept into deployable, testable systems suitable for real operational environments

5.11 “Experimental Polarization-Encoded QKD in Lab & Demo” by A. Stathis, A. Ntanos & K. Vyrsoinos

This presentation delivered a deep, experiment-oriented exploration of polarization-encoded QKD, guiding participants from fundamental quantum-optical concepts to hands-on laboratory realization and system-level intuition. It explained why weak coherent pulses derived from highly coherent laser sources are used in practice to emulate single-photon behavior, emphasizing the role of attenuation, Poissonian photon statistics, and careful pulse carving in reaching the single-photon regime compatible with QKD. The presentation then built a solid physical foundation by introducing photon detection technologies, particularly SPADs, detailing their operating principles, performance metrics, and non-idealities such as dark counts, afterpulsing, dead time, and timing jitter, all of which directly affect quantum bit error rate. A substantial part of the material was devoted to polarization as a degree of freedom for encoding quantum information, developing the description from electromagnetic wave theory through Jones calculus, Stokes parameters, and the Poincaré sphere, and showing how linear, circular, and elliptical polarization states are generated, transformed, and analyzed using polarizers and waveplates. Different quantum encoding strategies were compared, with polarization encoding highlighted for its conceptual clarity and suitability in laboratory and free-space scenarios, alongside a discussion of fast polarization modulation using interferometric schemes rather than slow mechanical components. The presentation culminated in realistic polarization-based QKD module designs, including interferometric and Sagnac-loop architectures that mitigate environmental instabilities, and demonstrated how intrinsic QBER can be measured and minimized through careful calibration of sources, modulators, and analyzers. Overall, the narrative tightly connects quantum theory, photonic hardware, and experimental practice, making clear that secure polarization-encoded QKD emerges not from abstract principles alone but from disciplined control of light, noise, and measurement in real optical systems.

5.12 “HellasQCI Use Cases / Cybersecurity” by G. Gardikis

Towards Software-Defined QKD Networks

This presentation addressed the operational challenge of scaling QKD from isolated links into manageable, carrier-grade networks by introducing software-defined QKD as a natural evolution of QKD infrastructures. It started from the observation that while QKD provides tamper-resistant key exchange at the physical layer, the complexity of fault, configuration, accounting, performance, and security management grows rapidly as networks expand, making manual or device-centric control impractical. Drawing on established software-defined networking principles, the presentation explained how separating the control plane from the data plane and centralizing control enables flexible, programmable, and automated management of QKD resources. Within this framework, current standardization efforts were presented, focusing on ETSI specifications that define control, monitoring, and orchestration interfaces for SD-QKD networks. Particular

emphasis was placed on the role of YANG data models and NETCONF-based interfaces as the technical enablers for standardized configuration, monitoring, and interoperability across heterogeneous QKD devices and vendors. The presentation then showed how these interfaces support advanced monitoring and observability use cases, allowing QKD network data to be collected, indexed, visualized, and analyzed in centralized platforms, and how orchestration interfaces enable automated end-to-end service provisioning across multiple QKD and optical transport domains. By framing QKD as a software-defined, observable, and orchestrated infrastructure rather than a collection of standalone devices, the presentation highlighted both the opportunities and challenges ahead, including security, resilience, and industry adoption, and positions SD-QKD as a key step toward flexible, scalable, and operationally viable quantum-secured networks.

5.13 “Motor Oil Hellas - Quantum Cryptography implementation in Refinery Campus” by D. Vythoulkas

This presentation presented Motor Oil Hellas as a concrete industrial use case for quantum-safe communications, demonstrating how QKD and post-quantum techniques can be integrated into the cybersecurity architecture of a critical infrastructure environment. It positioned the refinery campus as a high-value target where long-term confidentiality, operational continuity, and regulatory compliance are essential, and outlined Motor Oil’s role within the project as an end user contributing real operational requirements to system design and validation. The material described a phased approach to adoption, starting from exploratory and pilot stages and progressing toward operational deployment, with a focus on securing intra-campus and site-to-site communications. In the terrestrial use case, the presentation highlighted quantum-safe MACsec and IPsec encryption for primary and disaster-recovery datacenter interconnections over single-mode fiber, using dynamically refreshed session keys to protect L2 and L3 traffic. In parallel, a satellite-based use case was introduced to explore site-to-site quantum-safe IPsec tunnels over SD-WAN, assessing the feasibility of integrating satellite QKD links despite challenges such as increased round-trip time. By grounding quantum-safe cryptography in the practical constraints of refinery operations, multi-site connectivity, and hybrid terrestrial–satellite networks, the presentation illustrated how QKD and PQC can move beyond laboratory demonstrations to address real industrial security needs, reinforcing their relevance for protecting national critical infrastructures.

5.14 HellasQCI Training Crete Sep 2024: Scope, Structure and Outcomes

The HellasQCI Training Crete Sep 2024 constituted the third major training activity of the HellasQCI project and a direct continuation of the training axes developed during the HellasQCI Training Athens 2023. The two-day training event entitled “Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security” was organized on 4–5 September 2024 in Heraklion, Crete, at the premises of the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH). The event was coordinated by GRNET and FORTH and aimed at strengthening expertise in quantum communication technologies and cybersecurity at both national and European levels.

The training targeted a broad audience including researchers, cybersecurity experts, IT professionals, engineers, students, academics and industry representatives involved in the deployment and operation of quantum communication infrastructures. The event was organized in hybrid format and attracted strong participation, with more than 400 attendees following the sessions either physically or online. The training benefited from the contribution of forty speakers originating from fourteen countries, reflecting the strong international dimension of the HellasQCI initiative and its close alignment with the wider EuroQCI ecosystem.

Figure 5.2 Participants during Training Event in Crete 2024

The training programme was officially opened with high-level welcoming remarks delivered by representatives of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, GRNET, FORTH and the European Commission. These opening sessions positioned HellasQCI within the broader European strategy for quantum-secured communications and highlighted the strategic importance of Quantum Communication Infrastructures for future digital sovereignty and cybersecurity.

The first day of the training focused primarily on strategic perspectives, European initiatives and system-level considerations. Dedicated sessions addressed the status and progress of EuroQCI and national QCI deployments, highlighting synergies between HellasQCI and European projects such as PETRUS and NOSTRADAMUS. Representatives from several National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCIs) shared experiences, challenges and best practices related to deployment, interoperability and long-term sustainability. These discussions provided participants with a comprehensive overview of the evolving European QCI landscape and the role of HellasQCI within it.

The afternoon sessions of the first day shifted the focus towards architectural aspects of QKD systems and networks. Presentations covered the QKD architecture across different layers, including the quantum layer, key management layer and application layer. Particular emphasis was placed on how QKD can be integrated with classical cryptographic mechanisms and existing network infrastructures, enabling hybrid security architectures that combine QKD with PQC. These sessions bridged high-level concepts with practical design considerations relevant to real-world deployments.

The second day of the training was dedicated to advanced technical topics and hands-on activities. The morning sessions focused on the transition from PQC to QKD and the complementary role of these technologies in future-proof security frameworks. Technical lectures addressed key photonic components and system aspects of QKD implementations, including sources, modulators, detectors, polarization control and stabilization techniques, as well as fiber-based and free-space quantum communication links.

A central element of the second day was the practical demonstration and laboratory-oriented training. Participants were introduced to experimental polarization-encoded QKD setups through both physical laboratory demonstrations and guided experimental walkthroughs. These sessions covered essential operational aspects such as polarization analysis, system calibration, performance monitoring and error evaluation, enabling participants to gain hands-on insight into the practical operation of QKD systems.

Additional sessions focused on cybersecurity use cases enabled by QKD and on the coexistence of quantum and classical communication channels. Realistic deployment scenarios were discussed, including the integration of QKD into existing network infrastructures and its application in critical sectors. A dedicated demonstration of a QKD network showcased the progress of the HellasQCI testbed on the Athens metropolitan network, highlighting a multi-node configuration and illustrating the operational potential of quantum-secured communications.

6. QCI Days 2025, Athens April 2025

The QCI Days Athens 2025 event was organized from 28 to 30 of April 2025 at the Eugenides Foundation in Athens, Greece, as a major European event dedicated to QKD, quantum-secured communications, and the development of national and European QCIs. The event brought together policymakers, representatives of European and national institutions, research and academic communities, industry stakeholders, and end users, aiming to address the strategic, technological, and industrial challenges associated with the deployment and operation of quantum communication infrastructures across Europe.

The three-day event combined high-level policy discussions with in-depth technical sessions, industry-oriented presentations, and demonstrations, offering a comprehensive overview of the current state of quantum communication technologies and their integration into real-world networks. The agenda was structured to cover a wide range of topics, including the role of QKD in securing future digital infrastructures, the interaction between QKD and PQC, architectural and operational aspects of QCI systems, large-scale network deployments, and practical use cases in critical sectors.

The first day focused on the strategic and policy dimensions of quantum-secured communications, emphasizing the future of secure communication in Europe. Opening sessions featured contributions from governmental representatives and European institutions, outlining national strategies and the broader EuroQCI vision. Keynote presentations and panel discussions addressed the security perspective of QKD, the readiness of large-scale QCI deployments, and the role of national QCI initiatives in shaping a coherent European quantum communication ecosystem. Dedicated sessions highlighted ongoing national and European projects, enabling the exchange of experiences and best practices among different countries.

The second day was dedicated to Europe's quantum industry and ecosystem development, placing emphasis on the industrialization of QKD technologies and the maturation of the supply chain. Presentations from technology providers, research organizations, and startups showcased advances in QKD components, systems, and services, as well as innovations targeting quantum-secured networks. Company pitches and use-case sessions illustrated how QKD solutions are being translated into deployable products and services, while discussions on secure connectivity from Earth to space highlighted the growing importance of satellite-based quantum communication links.

Figure 6.1: High level policy representation at QCI Days 2025. From L to R: A. De Touzalin (EC), A. R. Bofill Morientes (Min. Dig. Transformation ES), V. Martin (UPM, ES), M. Stierle (AIT, AT), D. Papastergiou (Minister of Digital Governance, GR), K. Karratzalos (Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, GR), A. Sotiropoulos (GRNET, GR), I. Papastamatiou (GRNET, GR), G. Kanellos (NKUA, GR).

The third day focused on deployment strategies, user opportunities, and market adoption. Sessions addressed the challenges of transitioning from research prototypes to operational QCI infrastructures, including standardization, certification, and interoperability. Contributions from end users and infrastructure operators provided insights into real-world requirements, expectations, and constraints, while discussions on hybrid security approaches examined the combined use of quantum and post-quantum technologies. The event concluded with forward-looking discussions on the future evolution of QCI deployments and the role of HellasQCI within the broader European landscape.

Below, a more detailed description of each individual talk and session is provided.

6.1 “The Security Perspective of QKD” by K. Elder

This presentation provided an overview of the role of PETRUS in coordinating the first wave of national EuroQCI deployments and shaping a coherent operational framework for quantum communication infrastructures across Europe, as presented during QCI Days 2025. It summarized the results of a structured survey assessing the state of play of national QCI projects, covering design, deployment, and operational phases, and highlights key findings such as the mixed maturity of deployed equipment, the continued presence of non-EU and prototype technologies, and the dominance of governmental and defence users among early adopters. The presentation emphasized disparities in awareness of the quantum threat and

QKD benefits, noting high awareness in classified, governmental, and research communities, contrasted with significantly lower awareness among non-classified critical infrastructure users, despite the fact that many QKD services will become available first in non-classified contexts. It further presented the work of the EuroQCI Thematic Working Groups, including the clarification of the separation between EU-QCI for EU-classified services and National QCIs for national or non-classified services, and the evolution of the EuroQCI Concept of Operations. To address the diversity of national approaches, the presentation introduced the development of a “ConOps Cookbook” and supporting decision papers, designed to guide Member States in making informed architectural, operational, and governance decisions when implementing their national QCIs. Overall, the presentation positioned PETRUS as a central coordination and alignment mechanism, bridging policy, deployment reality, and future service adoption to support the sustainable rollout of EuroQCI and national quantum communication services.

Nostradamus (M. Stierle)

This presentation outlined the NOSTRADAMUS project as a cornerstone European initiative for establishing a structured, credible, and harmonised testing, validation, and certification framework for QKD technologies within the EuroQCI ecosystem. It explained how NOSTRADAMUS developed a comprehensive blueprint for a Testing and Validation Infrastructure by systematically analysing hundreds of scientific publications to identify, classify, and prioritise QKD side-channel attacks, vulnerabilities, and countermeasures based on technical feasibility, market relevance, and security impact. The presentation detailed a phased methodology in which selected attacks are first reproduced and validated in research laboratories, then industrialised and transferred into an ITSEF-ready testbed environment, enabling functional testing at the qubit layer, evaluation of countermeasures, and realistic side-channel attack testing across DV-QKD, CV-QKD, entanglement-based, and MDI-QKD systems. A key contribution is the development of Common Criteria-aligned Protection Profiles and a Product Security Baseline, providing a formal bridge between theoretical security requirements and practical certification, including handling of EU-classified information. The presentation concluded by describing the planned transfer of the testbed and knowledge to JRC Ispra, positioning NOSTRADAMUS as a foundational enabler for future accreditation, certification, and trust in QKD products deployed across EuroQCI and national QCI infrastructures.

6.2 Large Networks Deployments

“Deploying HellasQCI within the EuroQCI Initiative” by I. Papastamatiou

This presentation provided a comprehensive overview of the deployment, validation, and evolution of the HellasQCI infrastructure within the broader EuroQCI initiative, emphasizing Greece’s transition from pilot experimentation to a permanent, national-scale quantum communication backbone. It detailed the phased deployment strategy, starting with Phase 0 proof-of-concept validation of a three-layer architecture integrating the QKD layer, ETSI-compliant key management and SDN control layers, and multi-layer service encryption, and progressing through Phase 1 operational demonstrations and Phase 2 full-scale backbone deployment spanning approximately 650 km. The presentation highlighted the establishment of three national domains (governmental, industrial, and educational), the integration of space-segment connectivity through upgraded optical ground stations, and the adoption of advanced features such as

switched QKD, hybrid quantum–classical key orchestration, PUF- and PQC-based authentication, and comprehensive monitoring and management tools. It further described the governance and security framework for trusted nodes, aligned with national and international security standards, and showcases concrete use cases, including healthcare and quantum-secure video conferencing, validated during QCI Days Athens 2025. In parallel, the presentation underscored the importance of training, community building, and awareness raising as integral components of HellasQCI, and concluded by outlining future steps toward multi-domain operation, PQC integration, and cross-border connectivity through CEF-funded initiatives such as SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS, positioning HellasQCI as a mature and interoperable national contributor to the emerging EuroQCI ecosystem.

“QCI-CAT” by S. Ramacher

This presentation introduced QCI-CAT as Austria’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, illustrating a mature, operational QKD network designed to support secure governmental, medical, and critical data services while integrating seamlessly into the wider EuroQCI ecosystem. It described the deployment of a multi-vendor QKD network connecting ministries in Vienna, a long-distance link to Graz for secure medical data exchange, and an extended trusted-node–based connection to a backup data center in St. Johann, reaching distances of up to 400 km. The presentation outlined the functional AustroQCI architecture, which supports interconnection with neighboring national QCIs and future integration with the satellite domain, and highlights ongoing research activities such as a test network in Innsbruck exploring hybrid QKD and advanced quantum protocols, including quantum repeaters. Emphasis was placed on the central role of key management systems in enabling end-to-end quantum-safe services and on concrete use cases ranging from secure government communications and genome data transfer to QKD-based key backups and PKCS#11 key wrapping. Finally, the presentation positioned Austria as a core EuroQCI hub through extensive participation in CEF-II cross-border projects, optical ground station deployment, and regional interconnection initiatives, reinforcing QCI-CAT’s role as both a national infrastructure and a key contributor to Europe-wide quantum-secured communications.

“EuroQCI Spain” by A. Gorni

This presentation presented Spain’s national approach to deploying Quantum Communication Infrastructure within the EuroQCI framework, highlighting a mature, research-driven ecosystem that bridges large-scale infrastructure deployment with advanced experimental use cases. It outlined Spain’s national architecture based on a software-defined networking paradigm that separates control and data planes and integrates QKD systems, key management, trusted-node key forwarding, and ETSI-standardized interfaces to enable end-to-end quantum-safe services. The presentation detailed two major metropolitan deployments—MadQCI in Madrid and the Barcelona Quantum Ring—covering more than 800 km of fiber and integrating dozens of QKD modules from multiple vendors, multi-layer encryptors, and hybrid QKD–PQC configurations. A wide range of use cases was presented, spanning healthcare, banking, law enforcement, data center interconnection, and secure video conferencing, alongside advanced research activities in free-space QKD, multicore and ultra-low-loss fibers, quantum memories, and quantum repeaters as stepping stones toward trusted-node reduction. The presentation also emphasized Spain’s strong industrial and research ecosystem, with active participation of telecom operators, security providers,

and quantum technology spin-offs, and concludes by positioning Spain as a key contributor to EuroQCI evolution, including future cross-border initiatives such as an IberianQCI and the integration of satellite and free-space quantum links.

“Pionier-Q (Poland)” by P. Rydlichowski

This presentation described the PIONIER-Q project as Poland’s national large-scale Quantum Communication Infrastructure, deployed on top of the long-established PIONIER National Research and Education Network and designed to support research, public administration, healthcare, and industrial users. It presented a consortium of 22 partners and a nationwide footprint covering universities, research institutes, public authorities, and cultural institutions, leveraging more than 30 years of NREN collaboration. The presentation detailed the implementation of approximately 1 770 km of dedicated inter-city QKD fiber links, complemented by metropolitan QKD systems in major cities, a nationwide key management infrastructure, and trusted intermediary nodes, with dedicated connections to national security authorities. A wide range of use cases was outlined, including municipal and regional interconnects, distributed data center protection, medical data hubs, industrial connectivity, and integration of QKD with blockchain technologies. The presentation further highlighted Poland’s strong emphasis on laboratory support and experimentation through the PIONIER Lab Network, as well as future integration with EuroQCI, EuroHPC, and AI Factory initiatives. Finally, it distilled key operational lessons learned, such as the need for gradual scaling, robust environmental monitoring, improved network operations tooling, and better metrics for quantum channel health, positioning PIONIER-Q as a mature, operationally informed national QCI and a strong contributor to the evolving EuroQCI ecosystem.

“QCI-DK (Denmark)” by D. Null

This presentation presented QCI.dk as Denmark’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, offering an engineer’s perspective on how QKD is deployed, operated, and integrated into real production networks rather than treated as a laboratory experiment. It described a nationwide network interconnecting universities, research institutes, and governmental entities, built as a heterogeneous environment that deliberately integrates multiple QKD technologies (both CV-QKD and DV-QKD) from different vendors and validates their interoperability with existing carrier-grade network equipment. A strong emphasis was placed on practical engineering challenges, including rack integration, power supply mismatches, lifecycle management of network hardware, link stability, and operational testing prior to deployment. The presentation illustrated how QKD-derived keys are actually consumed at the application and network layers, using standard technologies such as MACsec, ETSI GS QKD 014 interfaces, and hybrid approaches combining QKD with Shamir’s Secret Sharing to increase resilience against partial trust, interception, or denial-of-service scenarios. It further situated QCI.dk within the broader EuroQCI vision, highlighting cross-border interoperability testing, future CEF links, and the concept of a shared European “embassy network” with multiple independent technological domains. Overall, the presentation conveyed that successful national QCI deployment depends as much on pragmatic systems engineering, operational realism, and expectation alignment between telecoms and QKD vendors as on the underlying quantum technology itself.

“Q-net-Q (Germany):” by T. Hühn

This presentation introduced Q-net-Q as a large-scale German quantum networking initiative that serves as both a national testbed and a EuroQCI-aligned validation platform for deploying, integrating, and evaluating QKD in real telecommunications environments. It presented a geographically distributed infrastructure spanning Berlin, Frankfurt, Jena, Erfurt, Nordhausen, and Munich, interconnected through long-distance dark fiber links of up to 670 km and integrated with major internet exchange points such as DE-CIX. The presentation highlighted four core objectives: multi-vendor validation and certification of QKD hardware and software, evaluation of QKD services between datacenters, assessment of multi-hop backbone integration in carrier networks, and efficient QKD deployment in urban access networks. A key technical contribution was the tight integration of QKD and classical ICT infrastructures, combining BB84 prepare-and-measure and BBM92 entanglement-based QKD over shared fiber topologies with routers, P4 switches, and trusted relay nodes, as illustrated in the integrated architecture diagrams. The presentation also discussed practical planning challenges such as dark fiber topology design, the impact of aerial versus underground fiber segments on stability, and operational constraints encountered during deployment. Finally, it situated Q-net-Q within the broader EuroQCI roadmap through its involvement in the QUANT-GPICz CEF proposal with Poland and the Czech Republic, positioning the platform as a critical bridge between national QCI deployments and future cross-border quantum-secured communication networks.

6.3 QKD Use Cases

“PTQCI (Portugal)” by C. Bastos

This presentation introduced PTQCI as Portugal’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure and the country’s first concrete contribution to the EuroQCI initiative, with a strong focus on operational readiness, sovereign communications, and capacity building. It outlined PTQCI’s main objectives, which included the design, implementation, and validation of a quantum-secure network interconnecting sovereign authorities in Lisbon, the execution of representative use cases to demonstrate the practical value of quantum technologies, and the parallel deployment of a testbed to evaluate emerging solutions and inform the long-term national roadmap. The presentation presents a phased timeline covering architectural design and requirements definition, procurement and governance model establishment, and progressive testing and demonstration activities leading to a pilot quantum-secure network. In addition to infrastructure deployment, significant emphasis is placed on dissemination, training, and education actions aimed at developing national expertise in quantum communications. Finally, the presentation situates PTQCI within the broader EuroQCI context by highlighting plans for future international connections and cross-border integration, positioning Portugal as an active participant in the emerging pan-European quantum communication ecosystem.

“CZQCI (Czech Republic)” by J. Bouda

This presentation introduced CZQCI as the Czech Republic’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, designed as a high-reliability backbone network combined with flexible testing and training capabilities and tightly aligned with the EuroQCI roadmap. It described a national QKD backbone interconnecting Prague, Brno, and Ostrava, characterized by large distances and high total attenuation, and complemented by metropolitan segments used for concrete use-case testing. A central element is the use of the backbone as a testing and training polygon, enabling direct comparison of multiple QKD technologies, including discrete-variable, continuous-variable, and entanglement-based QKD, under realistic field conditions. The presentation highlighted CZQCI’s strong cross-border orientation, with four planned CEF connections to Austria, Poland, Slovakia, and Germany, as well as the deployment of an optical ground station to support the Eagle-1 satellite mission. It further emphasized openness to international terrestrial and satellite-based use cases and places significant weight on teaching, training, and popularization activities targeting decision makers, fiber and network engineers, and cybersecurity experts. Overall, CZQCI was positioned as a robust national infrastructure that balances operational deployment, experimentation, cross-border integration, and capacity building as part of the emerging EuroQCI ecosystem.

“Be-QCI (Belgium)” by E. de Vinck

This presentation provided an overview of BeQCI as Belgium’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, highlighting a phased, use-case-driven deployment strategy that combines operational rollout with advanced research and ecosystem building. It outlined three deployment phases, beginning with completed links between academic sites, Belnet data centers, and Redu–Transinne, supporting use cases such as classical–quantum coexistence studies, encrypted government data traffic, and IoT middleware integration. The ongoing second phase extended the Brussels network through trusted-node architectures and introduces a 132 km cross-border link to Luxembourg in collaboration with Lux4QCI, validating long-distance terrestrial QKD feasibility. The planned third phase further expanded toward on-chip QKD prototyping, commercial data center interconnections, healthcare data transfer between hospitals, and PQC-based links operated by the Royal Military Academy. The presentation also discussed key lessons learned, including growing awareness of quantum-safe migration but limited end-user uptake, technology maturity challenges causing deployment delays, and the pressing need for security certification and labeling frameworks to support ecosystem trust. Overall, BeQCI was positioned as a mature, cross-border-capable national infrastructure that strengthens Belgium’s role in future European collaborations, supports industrial and academic innovation, and contributes to the gradual establishment of a sustainable EuroQCI-aligned quantum communication ecosystem.

“SiQUID (Slovenia)” by A. Ramsak & K. Ulekar

This presentation introduced SiQUID as Slovenia’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure Demonstration, designed to combine governmental deployment, experimental research, and capacity building within the EuroQCI framework. It outlined a dual-network architecture consisting of a governmental QKD network serving state institutions and an experimental research network operated by academic partners, each with distinct objectives but shared technological foundations. The governmental

network focused on distributing quantum key material using entanglement-based BBM92 protocols integrated with quantum-enhanced encryptors and TEMPEST-compliant classical encryption systems, while the experimental network supports advanced research on long-distance entanglement distribution, entanglement swapping, and prepare-and-measure BB84 demonstrations, including a planned ~100 km entanglement link toward Zagreb. The presentation detailed in-house development of QKD sources, detector integration using SNSPDs and APDs, and the use of both industrial and research-grade components to balance innovation with deployability. Strong emphasis was placed on building national expertise through the training of students, postdoctoral researchers, and engineers, and on advancing QKD system industrialization. Overall, SiQUID was positioned as a strategically balanced national initiative that simultaneously delivers operational quantum-secured services, supports cutting-edge research, and strengthens Slovenia's long-term role in the European quantum communication ecosystem.

“RoNaQCI (Romania)” by G. P. Popescu

This presentation positioned Beyond RoNaQCI as a comprehensive national and academic effort that extends Romania's Quantum Communication Infrastructure beyond basic QKD deployment toward large-scale entanglement distribution, future quantum network architectures, and sustained education in quantum technologies. It presented RoNaQCI as one of the largest QKD networks within EuroQCI, comprising more than 1 500 km of QKD links across six metropolitan networks and a national backbone, supported by a broad community of academic, industrial, and public-sector partners. A significant part of the presentation was devoted to long-term research on entanglement distribution and quantum network behavior, including a series of peer-reviewed works on network decongestion, entanglement resupply, crossbar quantum networks, and satellite-assisted entanglement distribution, which collectively address scalability and efficiency limits of trusted-node QKD networks. These theoretical contributions are directly linked to practical system concepts for future QKD networks, including hybrid terrestrial-satellite architectures and cross-border interconnection models relevant to upcoming CEF calls. In parallel, the presentation highlighted concrete software implementations such as QKD key management tools, quantum-secure file transfer, and QKD-assisted VPN video conferencing, demonstrating application-layer exploitation of quantum keys. Strong emphasis was placed on education and capacity building, including national training programs, workshops, open-source tools, and the first Romanian MSc in quantum technologies, positioning Beyond RoNaQCI as a holistic initiative that integrates infrastructure deployment, advanced research, practical implementations, and long-term human capital development within the EuroQCI ecosystem.

6.4 Industrialisation of QKD

“QUIC” by D. Morcuende

This presentation introduced QuIC (the European Quantum Industry Consortium) and its role in supporting the industrialisation and large-scale adoption of QKD and quantum communication technologies within the EuroQCI context. It presented QuIC as a broad industry-driven association that brought together research organisations, academia, SMEs, startups, large enterprises, investors, and technology providers across the quantum communications value chain. The presentation highlighted QuIC's contributions to quantum

communications through structured use-case development activities that captured real-world security needs across multiple sectors, ensuring that emerging QKD technologies addressed practical market requirements rather than purely experimental goals. It also emphasized QuIC's role in strategic matchmaking, facilitating collaboration around funding instruments such as EuroQCI and CEF calls, and in mapping the quantum-secure communications value chain to identify technological gaps and critical components needed for scalable deployment. In addition, QuIC supported policy and strategy alignment, standardisation, and project-level initiatives such as NOSTRADAMUS, reinforcing Europe's industrial leadership in quantum communications. Overall, the presentation positioned QuIC as a key bridge between technology development, industrial readiness, and policy coordination, enabling the transition of QKD from research prototypes to sustainable, market-ready infrastructures.

“EQUO” by F. Stocco

This presentation introduced EQUO (European Quantum ecOSystems) as a Digital Europe Programme project aimed at advancing the industrial readiness and operational deployment of high-TRL QKD systems within the EuroQCI framework. It outlined EQUO's main objectives, which included the development, integration, and validation of QKD systems at TRL 8–9, their demonstration within operational telecommunications networks, and the promotion of industrial exploitation, dissemination, and standardisation. The presentation described a full-stack approach covering all layers of a QKD solution, from hardware subcomponents and QKD devices to management and control systems, classical security, and application integration, supported by a consortium of twelve partners spanning telecom operators, technology providers, and research institutions. Concrete outcomes included ETSI- and ITU-compliant quantum network functional architectures, progressive integration of QKD hardware subcomponents, and full quantum–classical layer integration with security analysis. The presentation highlighted on-field demonstrations, notably an operational point-to-point QKD link in Athens deployed in November 2024 with approximately 100 Mbps encrypted throughput, a similar deployment in Turin, and a planned complex QKD network in Rome featuring key routing and traffic management. Overall, EQUO was positioned as a key enabler for transitioning QKD from experimental setups to deployable, carrier-grade solutions capable of operating alongside existing services in real telecommunication networks.

“MDI-QUEEN” by R. Berrevoets

This presentation introduced the MDI-QUEEN project and Q*Bird's industrial Measurement-Device-Independent QKD solution as a scalable, secure, and network-friendly alternative to traditional trusted-node architectures for EuroQCI deployments. It explained how the MDI-QKD approach centralized measurement at detector hubs that never learned key information, thereby eliminating detector side-channel attacks while enabling multipoint-to-multipoint connectivity across many users. The presentation detailed a hub-and-end-node architecture in which low-cost qubit-sender end nodes connected to high-performance central hubs equipped with superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors, allowing cost-effective scaling, redundancy through multiple hubs, and seamless integration with classical telecom networks. Technical emphasis was placed on the industrial readiness of the MDI-QUEEN platform, including rack-mountable, data-center-grade cryogenic detection systems, integrated key management, DWDM compatibility, and extended end-to-end loss budgets of up to 40 dB. The presentation also reported on real

deployment experience in the Netherlands, where MDI-QKD networks were tested in operational environments such as the Port of Rotterdam, governmental data center interconnections, and educational networks. Overall, MDI-QUEEN was positioned as a mature, EuroQCI-ready QKD solution that combined high security, operational robustness, and scalable network design, supporting the transition from point-to-point QKD links to large-scale quantum communication networks without trusted nodes.

“QKISS” by P. Grangier

This presentation introduced QKISS as a European project focused on the industrialisation of continuous-variable QKD systems, aiming to deliver high-performance, field-ready CV-QKD technology aligned with EuroQCI requirements. Coordinated by Exail and involving industrial and academic partners including Thales, LIP6, and Institut d’Optique, the project targeted the full design and optimisation of a complete CV-QKD system, spanning electro-optic hardware, digital signal processing, post-processing, and encryption. The presentation detailed a coherent heterodyne detection architecture using a true local oscillator, Gaussian modulation under the GG02 protocol, and real-time operation with high-speed QRNGs, custom low-noise modulators, and in-house DSP capable of tens of gigabits per second. Significant emphasis was placed on excess-noise reduction, finite-size security analysis, and optimisation of secret key rates, supported by extensive laboratory and field trials, including deployments between Thales and IOGS and multi-node tests within the Paris regional QCI network. The project’s strong integration with FranceQCI and NOSTRADAMUS was highlighted through interoperability experiments with discrete-variable QKD systems and security evaluations addressing spectral leakage and Trojan-horse attacks. Overall, QKISS was positioned as a mature, open, and modular CV-QKD platform that bridged research and industrial deployment, contributing directly to the certification, interoperability, and large-scale adoption of CV-QKD within the EuroQCI ecosystem.

“QUARTER” by S. Etcheverry

This presentation introduced QUARTER as a Digital Europe Programme project dedicated to advancing the industrial maturity, integration, and deployment readiness of continuous-variable QKD technologies within the EuroQCI ecosystem. Coordinated by LuxQuanta and supported by a consortium of SMEs, large industrial players, telecom operators, and research organisations, QUARTER adopted a full value-chain approach covering photonic integrated components, QKD systems, key management, encryption, and network integration. The presentation highlighted key technological results, including PIC-based high-performance QRNGs, narrow-linewidth lasers optimised for CV-QKD, a significantly miniaturised and higher-loss-tolerant CV-QKD system, ETSI-compliant encryptor upgrades, and a standards-aligned key management system supporting ETSI, ITU-T Y.3803, NIST, and SDN interfaces. Strong emphasis was placed on interoperability and real-network validation, with field trials integrating LuxQuanta, Thales, fragmentiX, and Telefónica equipment in operational telecom nodes, alongside experimental studies on CV-QKD coexistence with amplified classical channels. Overall, the presentation positioned QUARTER as a concrete step toward carrier-grade, interoperable, and certifiable CV-QKD solutions, bridging the gap between component-level innovation and deployable EuroQCI-ready quantum-secure communication infrastructures.

“SEQRET” by U. Eisman

This presentation introduced SEQRET as an industrial solution provider addressing one of the central architectural challenges of EuroQCI deployments: the secure realization and certification of trusted nodes in QKD networks. It explained how naïve key forwarding approaches—such as unprotected Ethernet patching between QKD devices and key management systems—could expose quantum keys to physical attacks, motivating the need for hardened, tamper-resistant trusted-node designs. The core concept presented was QSplice, a trusted-node platform that tightly integrated QKD transmitters and receivers, a full-featured key management system, and tamperproof hardware protections into a single certified unit capable of secure key forwarding. The presentation highlighted that QSplice supported flexible network topologies, including mesh and star configurations, was interoperable with different QKD technologies and secure application entities, and incorporated in-band SDN-based management for operational control. By focusing on physical security, interoperability, and certification readiness, the presentation positioned SEQRET’s trusted-node approach as a practical and scalable building block for deploying secure, auditable, and standards-aligned QKD networks within the EuroQCI framework.

“eCAUSIS” by A. Kaminska

This presentation presented the eCAUSIS project as a Digital Europe Programme initiative aimed at designing and industrialising an affordable, certifiable, and user-oriented ground-based QKD system fully aligned with EuroQCI requirements. It focused on delivering an industry-grade implementation of the BB84 protocol tailored to optical-fibre transmission, integrating highly compact transmitter and receiver modules with advanced optoelectronics, European photonic integrated circuits, and high-performance single-photon detectors. The presentation outlined a full value-chain approach, covering component design, system integration, key post-processing, key management, network monitoring, manufacturing readiness, and Common Criteria-oriented certification. The project’s technical progress was illustrated through successive PCIe-based QKD prototypes, evolving from COTS-based modules to fully integrated PIC-enabled designs, and culminating in a commercial QKD product announced by Creotech, available from 2026, offering rack-mounted or PCIe form factors, ETSI GS QKD compliance, built-in KMS options, and well-defined operational and security parameters. In addition, the presentation highlighted advanced detector developments addressing both fibre-based and free-space scenarios, reinforcing the project’s relevance for terrestrial and future space-linked QKD deployments. Overall, eCAUSIS was positioned as a concrete step toward scalable, manufacturable, and certifiable European QKD products capable of supporting real operational networks within the EuroQCI ecosystem.

6.5 Innovations for Quantum-secured Networks

“skQCI (Slovakia)” by D. Aktas

This presentation outlined the Slovak Quantum Communication Infrastructure (skQCI) as a dual-track national effort combining commercially available QKD solutions with advanced entanglement-based research prototypes, aligned with the EuroQCI vision. It first presented the deployment of commercial QKD systems as full end-to-end solutions integrating QKD links with Layer-3 encryptors, targeting secure communications over moderate distances in controlled environments such as telecom facilities, and

extending toward 1-to-N fully meshed architectures with built-in redundancy. In parallel, the presentation highlighted Slovakia's strong focus on entanglement-based QKD as a natural enabler of multipartite, fully meshed quantum networks, while preserving bipartite security properties. Significant progress was reported on an entanglement-based prototype, including a laboratory photon-pair source with high detected brightness and fidelity, and a six-node fully meshed demonstration (4+2) with a deployed link between the Laser Center and RCQI. The presentation concluded by emphasizing demultiplexing techniques based on entanglement as a key mechanism for scalable quantum networking, positioning skQCI as a balanced national initiative that integrated near-term operational QKD deployment with longer-term research toward fully connected quantum communication networks.

“QCINed (Netherlands)” by A. Scheltinga

This presentation introduced QCINed as the Netherlands' national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, emphasizing its operation as an open, automated, and multi-vendor QKD network designed to support research, governmental, and industrial use cases within the EuroQCI framework. It presented QCINed as a fully integrated network service rather than a standalone technology, highlighting network automation, support for heterogeneous QKD technologies including CV-QKD, DV-QKD, and MDI-QKD, and the use of an open-source key management system to enable interoperability, transparency, and scalability. The presentation detailed QCINed's role as an open test and validation platform accessible to both industry and academia, supporting integration testing of QKD devices, KMSs, and encryptors, as well as validation of deployment models and preparation for certification. Concrete deployments were described, including the first governmental QKD connection between Dutch ministries, optimized key allocation and relaying strategies, and a four-node MDI-QKD network using Q*Bird's Falcon system, where a central hub securely supported multiple end nodes without learning key material. Finally, the presentation situated QCINed within a broader national and cross-border context, aligning NL-QCI, BENELUX-QCI, BONAMI, SEEWQCI, and CEF EuroQCI initiatives, all converging on Amsterdam as a major digital hub and future connection point to quantum computing resources, positioning QCINed as a central European node for quantum-secure networking and experimentation.

“ESTQC (Estonia)” by I. Linnas

This presentation presented EstQCI as Estonia's national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, focusing on the practical deployment, benchmarking, and operation of metropolitan and long-distance QKD testbeds aligned with the EuroQCI initiative. It described the establishment of both metro and long-haul testbeds, including a ring-network testbed supporting up to 400G classical links and designed to integrate with the Estonian national backbone and future EuroQCI interconnections. The presentation reported on extensive benchmarking activities of procured QKD devices, confirming compliance with vendor specifications while also identifying real operational constraints such as sensitivity to ambient temperature, key rate variability between device pairs, the need for software updates, and occasional system resets. Particular emphasis was placed on the importance of monitoring, diagnostics, and stability management, with trusted-node configurations and key management systems already operational. A key application focus was the integration of QKD into the emerging Estonian Government Cloud ring network, where performance, configuration, failure handling, and high-speed key management for 400G connections were evaluated in

collaboration with state IT authorities. Finally, the presentation highlighted strong regional cooperation through planned Nordic QCI interconnections with Sweden and Finland, and positioned EstQCI as an active contributor to cross-border EuroQCI development and knowledge building, including the organisation of the QCI Connect 2025 forum in Estonia.

“PRISM (Malta)” by J. Briffa

This presentation introduced PRISM as Malta’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure project, focused on deploying a secure, standards-aligned QKD network on existing public fibre infrastructure while simultaneously fostering a national quantum technology ecosystem. It described the establishment of a quantum-secured link between two governmental data centres using lit fibre operated in parallel with classical telecom traffic, relying on a physically secured central trusted node to overcome local infrastructure constraints. The presentation highlighted a vendor-agnostic, ETSI GS QKD 014–compliant key management system following the OQTAVO approach, designed to abstract device-specific limitations and enable interoperable key forwarding, alongside live network monitoring capabilities and dynamic SDN-controlled optical switching that supported redundancy, point-to-multipoint QKD, and automated failover. Further technical depth was provided on post-processing research, including LDPC-based error correction with GPU acceleration and the extension of the SimCommSys framework to model end-to-end QKD links over fibre and free-space channels, supporting protocols such as CV-QKD GG02. In parallel, PRISM positioned itself as an open-access research and experimentation platform, leveraging real-world QKD data, collaboration with EuroQCI partners, and upcoming testbeds to support protocol development, validation, and training. Overall, the presentation framed PRISM as a tightly integrated, research-driven yet deployment-oriented national QCI that addressed last-mile integration, operational challenges, and ecosystem development within the EuroQCI landscape.

“IrelandQCI (Ireland)” by D. Kilbane

This presentation provided an overview of IrelandQCI with a forward-looking focus on the evolution of quantum networks from secure key distribution toward a broader quantum-enabled communications and computing ecosystem. It highlighted a wide spectrum of use cases under active development, including quantum-secure data centres, high-speed encryption-as-a-service, quantum–classical coexistence design rules, quantum packaging, and advanced quantum key management systems. The presentation emphasized Ireland’s strong experimental and simulation capabilities, featuring platforms for free-space QKD simulation, satellite QKD feasibility studies, photonic quantum computation and communication modelling, and quantum optics experiments supported by mobile compact cryogenic stations and imaging systems. These activities were framed within a national quantum security testbed located in Waterford, serving both research and validation purposes. In addition to infrastructure development, the presentation underscored Ireland’s role in community building and international engagement, including hosting the 8th ESA ScyLight Conference in Dublin in June 2025. Overall, the presentation positioned IrelandQCI as an ambitious, research-intensive national initiative that integrated quantum communications, computation, simulation, and space studies to support the long-term evolution of EuroQCI and Europe’s quantum technology landscape.

6.6 QKD Use Cases

“BGQCI (Bulgaria)” by L. Georgiev

This presentation outlined the Bulgarian National QCI Plan as a deployment-driven initiative focused on securing critical governmental, municipal, and industrial communications using QKD within the EuroQCI framework. It presented concrete operational use cases, including a quantum-secured connection between Sofia Municipality’s Emergency Assistance and Prevention Operational Centre and its main data centre, secure links between the Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Transport and Communications, and an industrial deployment for power supply monitoring between A1 Bulgaria data centres using a trusted-node architecture over a public MPLS network. The presentation detailed the integration of QKD Alice/Bob devices, quantum key management entities, secure application entities, and CWDM-based coexistence of quantum and classical channels over limited fibre resources, highlighting pragmatic design choices driven by real infrastructure constraints. In addition to infrastructure deployment, strong emphasis was placed on extensive training and capacity building, with multiple multi-day training programs delivered to executive, technical, and research staff across public institutions, universities, research organisations, and private companies, reaching more than 200 participants. The consistently high satisfaction reported for these trainings underscored the project’s impact on national awareness and expertise in quantum communications. Overall, the Bulgarian National QCI Plan was positioned as a mature, use-case-oriented national deployment that combined practical QKD integration with broad stakeholder engagement to support the long-term adoption of quantum-secured communications in Bulgaria.

“CroQCI (Croatia)” by M. Loncaric

This presentation presented CroQCI as Croatia’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure with a strong emphasis on concrete, application-driven use cases enabled by an entanglement-based QKD network. It described a metropolitan-scale deployment in the City of Zagreb comprising eight trusted nodes interconnected over dark optical fibre, complemented by plans for an optical ground station to enable future satellite QKD integration. The architecture was based on polarization-encoded, entanglement-based QKD using the BBM92 protocol, where a central entangled photon source supported pairwise quantum correlations at the physical layer, which were then translated into a fully meshed secure communication network through the key management and ITS communication layers. The presentation highlighted four representative use cases: enhancing the security of distributed storage systems, atomic clock synchronization, preparation of a space QKD segment, and secure delivery of vulnerability reports for national security applications. By combining a research-oriented consortium with operational security stakeholders and focusing on entanglement as a scalable networking primitive, the presentation positioned CroQCI as a forward-looking national initiative that linked near-term QKD services with longer-term quantum networking and space-integration objectives within the EuroQCI framework.

“NQIS (Sweden)” by P. Lefebvre

This presentation introduced NQCIS as Sweden’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, designed as a large-scale, flexible testbed that combined operational deployment, advanced research, and user training in preparation for full EuroQCI integration. Coordinated by KTH and involving major academic and industrial partners, the infrastructure was organised around a central hub at Albanova with dark-fibre connections to Ericsson, RISE, regional energy providers, and long-distance trusted-node links extending toward Nyköping and Linköping, as illustrated in the network maps and hub overview. The presentation detailed a heterogeneous technology portfolio that included both discrete-variable and continuous-variable QKD systems from different vendors, complemented by high-performance SNSPD detection systems, enabling comparative evaluation under realistic field conditions over links ranging from metropolitan distances to more than 270 km. Strong emphasis was placed on research and development use cases, such as interoperability testing, robustness analysis under noise and environmental variations, modelling of future deployments, and experimentation with non-commercial techniques including twin-field and free-space QKD. At the key and application layers, the presentation highlighted efforts to lower adoption barriers by demonstrating QKD-secured VPNs and applications for government and enterprise use, thereby stimulating interest from telecom operators and potential end users. Overall, NQCIS was positioned as a cornerstone national platform that balanced experimentation, service-oriented demonstrations, and skills development, while directly supporting Sweden’s and Europe’s long-term quantum communication ambitions.

“NaQCI.fi (Finland)” by K. Sepponen

This presentation presented NaQCI.fi as Finland’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, structured around concrete public, governmental, technical, and research use cases and designed to support both near-term deployment and long-term EuroQCI integration. It outlined the deployment of two separate QKD networks: a public demonstration network in the Helsinki metropolitan area connecting universities, hospitals, VTT, and CSC’s secure data services using a mix of commercial DV-QKD and CV-QKD systems alongside in-house VTT devices, and a governmental demonstration network in southern Finland comprising nine DV-QKD links (45–125 km) interconnecting ten trusted sites over dark, fusion-spliced fibres (pages 2–4). The presentation detailed key technical and research activities, including interoperability testing, CWDM/DWDM co-propagation, entanglement distribution, security assessment, maintainability studies, and extensive experimentation with SNSPDs and Ge-on-Si APDs (pages 5–6). It further introduced VTT’s open, expert-customisable QKD testbed implementing time-bin, phase-modulated BB84 with active phase stabilisation, supporting R&D, education, and component testing (page 7). Finally, the presentation showcased advanced integration scenarios such as QKD-secured ORAN architectures and preparations for cross-border connectivity with Estonia and Sweden, positioning NaQCI.fi as a technically rich, application-driven national platform that combined deployment, experimentation, and training in alignment with EuroQCI objectives.

“FranceQCI (France)” by P. Robert

This presentation reported on a FranceQCI laboratory trial conducted with the French Air Navigation Service Provider (DSNA) to evaluate the feasibility of QKD-based encryption for air traffic control data, a mission-critical use case with stringent performance and availability requirements. The trial, carried out by Orange in collaboration with DSNA and Thales, assessed the integration of QKD equipment into a legacy ATC environment, with explicit constraints on latency (≤ 50 ms), jitter (≤ 5 ms), and traffic rate (< 1 Gbps), as detailed in the use-case definition (pages 2–3). A key architectural feature of the testbed was the use of an optical switch as a trusted-node solution, enabling flexible path selection, cost reduction, and extension of QKD coverage in a metropolitan context (page 4). The results demonstrated that QKD-based encryption could meet DSNA’s operational requirements, and that temporary physical interruptions of quantum links did not disrupt end-to-end key delivery thanks to key buffering mechanisms. Overall, the presentation provided strong evidence that QKD could be integrated into safety-critical operational networks such as air traffic control, validating its applicability beyond experimental settings and reinforcing the relevance of FranceQCI for high-assurance, real-world services within the EuroQCI framework.

6.7 Secure Connectivity from Earth to Space

“EAGLE-1 State of Play” by T. Bäumlér

This presentation provided an update on the EAGLE-1 mission as Europe’s first satellite-based QKD in-orbit demonstrator and a cornerstone contribution to the EuroQCI space segment. It outlined EAGLE-1 as an industry-led partnership coordinated by SES, building on the QUARTZ precursor programme and co-funded by ESA and the European Commission, with the objective of developing, launching, and operating an end-to-end satellite QKD system including space, ground, and user segments (pages 1–2). The presentation detailed the current state of system maturity, with platform, payload, and ground segment developments progressing toward system CDR closure, and highlighted the definition of pairwise key distribution workflows that ensured information-theoretic security between ground terminals through satellite-assisted key sharing (pages 3–5). Significant emphasis was placed on the certification and onboarding process for optical ground stations, describing a phased network certification approach covering optical performance, pointing and tracking, polarization control, QKD protocol execution, and end-to-end service validation (pages 7–9). The presentation also explained the operational model for requesting and consuming EAGLE-1 keys, defining roles, interfaces, and procedures for ground terminal owners and users (page 10). Finally, it introduced the EAGLE-neXt concept as the transition from demonstration to an accredited, service-oriented satellite QKD infrastructure for governmental and commercial users, positioning EAGLE-1 as a critical steppingstone toward a sustainable European space-based quantum communication capability within EuroQCI.

“GEO-QKD” by P. Pinto

This presentation presented Hispasat’s vision and technical roadmap for extending QKD to continental and global scales through a geostationary satellite mission, positioning GEO-QKD as a strategic complement to terrestrial EuroQCI networks. It explained that while fibre-based QKD was inherently limited to distances of roughly 100–200 km, space-based QKD using free-space optical links enabled secure key distribution over thousands of kilometres, with GEO satellites offering continuous coverage, no handover requirements, reduced pointing complexity, and simplified key management compared to LEO constellations. The core of the presentation was the CARAMUEL mission, conceived as the first GEO satellite mission dedicated to QKD and a precursor to future EuroQCI and IRIS² space infrastructures, based on a discrete-variable BB84 prepare-and-measure protocol at 1550 nm. The service concept targeted both high-end governmental and military users and commercial customers, integrating the satellite segment seamlessly with terrestrial fibre networks operated by partners such as Telefónica and Cellnex, and involving end users including financial institutions in service definition. The presentation detailed the system architecture, including the space payload, ground stations, operations centre, and key management interfaces, as well as a phased development timeline leading toward launch around 2028, supported by ESA and national funding. It also reported on early on-field testing between Tenerife and La Palma as part of the validation path. Overall, the presentation positioned GEO-QKD via CARAMUEL as a critical step toward an operational, service-oriented European space-based QKD capability that complemented national and cross-border terrestrial QCIs within the EuroQCI framework.

Figure 6.2 Opening and high-level strategic sessions during QCI Days 2025 in Athens.

“CYQCI (Cyprus)”, by K. Kalli

This presentation presented CYQCI as Cyprus’s national Quantum Communication Infrastructure initiative, with a strong strategic focus on establishing an optical ground station as the foundation for cross-border and space-enabled quantum connectivity within the EuroQCI framework. It outlined CYQCI’s objectives to deploy an advanced experimental national quantum network, stimulate local research and innovation, support European technological autonomy through the use of EU-manufactured equipment, and actively contribute to international standardisation efforts. A central theme of the presentation was Cyprus’s geographical positioning as a potential communication hub linking Europe with the Eastern Mediterranean, illustrated through inter-country distances to Greece, Italy, and Malta that exceeded the practical limits of terrestrial fibre-based QKD and therefore motivated space-based quantum links. The presentation detailed a step-by-step deployment approach for the Cyprus optical ground station, beginning with user requirement analysis and site selection based on weather conditions, followed by classical optical communication testing, system specification aligned with EAGLE-1 requirements, procurement, deployment, and preparation for future CEF-funded cross-border connectivity. It further situated the OGS within a broader national portfolio of ESA- and Cyprus-funded projects, including feasibility studies, mobile OGS concepts, optical channel measurement campaigns, and GOVSATCOM initiatives, positioning CYQCI as a carefully phased, strategically aligned national effort contributing to the realization of a pan-European quantum communication network.

“QCI Hungary (Hungary)” by O. Kitti

This presentation outlined Hungary’s space-segment activities within the national QCI programme, focusing on preparation for satellite-based quantum communications through free-space QKD experimentation and optical ground station development. It presented the objectives of the Hungarian QCI project, which included deploying a national quantum communication backbone, validating high-security links between governmental data centres, advancing experimental QKD systems, developing abstraction-layer software, training experts, and strengthening international cooperation. The core technical content described a polarization-entanglement-based free-space QKD setup using an 810 nm entangled photon source, fibre-to-free-space coupling, GPS-disciplined clock synchronization, and time-tagging electronics, initially tested over a 40 m indoor link with a roadmap toward ~700 m metropolitan links. Complementary experiments on clock transmission over free-space optical channels at 1550/650 nm and detailed optical background measurements were presented to address synchronization accuracy and environmental noise, both critical for urban and satellite QKD scenarios. The presentation further announced plans for a quantum-capable optical ground station to be deployed at the university in the second half of 2026, featuring an 80 cm telescope with adaptive optics, explicitly aligned with future satellite QKD missions. Overall, the work positioned Hungary’s QCI activities as a technically grounded, stepwise approach that bridged terrestrial experimentation and future satellite-based quantum networking, contributing to the long-term EuroQCI vision of a space-enabled quantum internet.

“Lux4QCI (Luxembourg)” by S. Koudia

This presentation presented Lux4QCI as Luxembourg’s national experimental Quantum Communication Infrastructure, developed as a multi-technology, multi-provider testbed to support interoperability testing, network-level innovation, and preparation for EuroQCI space integration. It described a deployed infrastructure comprising six QKD links across seven points of presence, integrating four different providers and heterogeneous QKD technologies, and actively testing the interaction between the physical quantum layer and the software-defined networking and control layers. A central contribution of the project was the development of the SEQURE key relay protocol, introduced to address the lack of standardized and interoperable mechanisms for relaying quantum keys across multiple administrative domains. SEQURE was presented as an SDN-compatible, JSON-based protocol supporting authenticated key relaying, collision avoidance through a master–slave paradigm, and flexible, programmable relay logic executed at each hop, enabling dynamic key routing and real-time control. The presentation detailed how SEQURE was integrated into the Lux4QCI architecture as a dedicated network function or SDN switch key manager, using QKD-derived keys for authentication and programmable instructions for hop-by-hop key forwarding. Future activities included last-mile integration toward full-network deployment, experimentation with multiplexing techniques for quantum–classical coexistence, interconnection with an Eagle-1 emulator, and the development of an Eagle-1–ready key management system. Overall, the presentation positioned Lux4QCI as a technically advanced national platform that combined experimental deployment, protocol innovation, and space-readiness to support Luxembourg’s and Europe’s long-term quantum communication objectives.

“QUID (Italy)” by M. Gramegna

This presentation presented QUID (Quantum Italy Deployment) as Italy’s national implementation of the EuroQCI initiative, built around a geographically extensive and scientifically distinctive quantum backbone that integrated quantum communication, metrology, and space-related infrastructures. Coordinated by INRIM and involving a balanced consortium of public research institutions, universities, and major Italian industrial players, QUID deployed Quantum Metropolitan Area Networks in 10 cities that were progressively interconnected through the Italian Quantum Backbone, a long-distance fibre infrastructure originally developed for primary frequency metrology and later repurposed as a national quantum communication platform. The presentation highlighted how this backbone uniquely supported not only QKD but also time and frequency transfer, relativistic geodesy, radioastronomy, and space geodesy, creating strong synergies between quantum communications and national scientific infrastructures. A broad portfolio of governmental, regional, industrial, port, and space-related use cases was presented, including central government administrations, regional authorities, critical industrial sites, and strategic hubs such as Matera for terrestrial–space EuroQCI interconnection. The deployment explicitly combined ground-based QKD networks with ground-to-space architectures and positioned Italy for future satellite QKD integration. Overall, QUID was framed as a mature, innovation-driven national QCI that coupled wide geographical coverage with advanced research, industrial participation, and concrete use cases, providing a strong and scalable Italian contribution to the evolving EuroQCI ecosystem.

6.8 Building the HellasQCI Community

“Quantum Ecosystem: Vision and Challenges” by P. Dimitrakis

This presentation provided a high-level analysis of the quantum technology ecosystem with a particular focus on Greece’s position, challenges, and opportunities within the rapidly evolving global and European quantum landscape. It introduced the quantum ecosystem as a multi-stakeholder environment encompassing government, academia, research and technology organisations, startups, end users, investors, standardisation bodies, and hardware and software providers, and situated Greece within worldwide trends of increasing public investment in quantum technologies. The presentation highlighted key structural challenges faced by the Greek quantum ecosystem, including fragmented and insufficient national funding, talent drain toward better-resourced international environments, limited domestic quantum hardware infrastructure, and relatively low engagement from industry and end users. Building on this assessment, it proposed a set of strategic recommendations, such as the development of a coherent national quantum strategy, targeted investment in infrastructure and EU-aligned initiatives like EuroQCI, expanded education and talent retention programs, incentives for startups and applied research, and the creation of a national stakeholder forum to coordinate policy, research, and industrial activity. The presentation concluded by identifying concrete opportunities for Greece to position itself as a regional hub for quantum education, simulation, and quantum-safe cybersecurity, leveraging EU funding mechanisms and the Greek scientific diaspora to strengthen its long-term role in the European quantum ecosystem.

“Quantum Communications for fiber and wireless channels” by H. Avramopoulos

This presentation presented the long-term research, deployment, and community-building contributions of the Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) of NTUA to HellasQCI and the broader EuroQCI vision, focusing on quantum communications over both fiber and free-space channels. It traced PCRL’s evolution from lab-scale quantum photonics research toward field-deployed QKD systems, highlighting concrete contributions such as polarization-encoded quantum transmitters, advanced spectral and temporal filtering techniques for quantum–classical coexistence, and Phase-0 HellasQCI experiments over deployed fronthaul and backhaul infrastructures. A major emphasis was placed on free-space QKD as a stepping stone toward Space-QCI, including experimental campaigns using large-aperture telescopes at the Helmos Observatory, the development of QKD-ready optical ground stations with high classical/quantum isolation compatible with Eagle-1, and inter-campus free-space QKD deployments. The presentation further outlined PCRL’s role in upgrading the Holomondas Observatory for optical and quantum communications, supporting both terrestrial and satellite-linked QKD scenarios. In parallel, strong attention was given to human capital development, with extensive training activities, laboratory exercises, and hands-on education in prepare-and-measure QKD already delivered, and future plans for quantum-light-based training and quantum optics educational kits. The presentation concluded by positioning entanglement-based fiber and free-space networks as the next research frontier, reinforcing PCRL’s role as a bridge between fundamental research, national QCI deployment, space readiness, and sustained community building within HellasQCI.

“Quantum communication is not just a technology challenge. It is a community effort.” By ADAPTIT

This presentation introduced ADAPTIT as a cross-cutting support action designed to strengthen the EuroQCI ecosystem by focusing on coordination, community building, skills development, and the practical adoption of quantum communication technologies beyond pure infrastructure deployment. It framed quantum communication not only as a technological challenge but as a socio-technical transformation requiring alignment between research organisations, industry, public authorities, operators, and end users. The presentation highlighted ADAPTIT’s role in supporting national QCIs through structured stakeholder engagement, training activities, dissemination actions, and the identification of best practices for deployment, operation, and adoption of quantum-secure services. Particular emphasis was placed on lowering barriers for non-expert stakeholders by translating complex quantum concepts into actionable knowledge, supporting workforce upskilling, and fostering dialogue between technology providers and users. By addressing organisational readiness, skills gaps, and ecosystem fragmentation, the presentation positioned ADAPTIT as an enabling layer that complemented technical EuroQCI projects, ensuring that quantum communication infrastructures could be effectively operated, trusted, and sustainably adopted across Europe.

“Fortinet – Synergies” by B. Nikolopoulos

This presentation presented Fortinet’s perspective on integrating QKD into existing, large-scale cybersecurity and networking infrastructures, emphasizing practical synergies rather than experimental deployments. It positioned QKD as a complementary key source that could be integrated into Fortinet’s Security Fabric through standardized interfaces, with the quantum functionality provided by specialized partners such as ID Quantique and Quantum Xchange, while Fortinet focused on secure key consumption and enforcement at the network and application layers. The presentation detailed how ETSI GS QKD 014–compliant APIs were used to transfer quantum keys from QKD systems into encryptors supporting IPsec and related security mechanisms, enabling seamless QKD–encryptor integration without disrupting established operational workflows. Concrete quantum-safe use cases were illustrated, including secure datacenter interconnection, database replication, backup and SAN mirroring, protection of mobile network backhaul links, and security for private 5G networks, where QKD-derived keys could be applied selectively to signaling or user data depending on operational requirements. By reporting successful live integrations across multiple European countries and highlighting ongoing collaboration between vendors and academic institutions, the presentation underscored that the value of QKD lay in ecosystem-level cooperation and standards-based integration, positioning QKD as a realistic enhancement to existing security architectures rather than a standalone or disruptive technology.

“Monitoring and Observability for QKD Networks” by G. Gardikis

This presentation focused on monitoring and observability as essential operational capabilities for deploying and sustaining large-scale QKD networks, using HellasQCI as a concrete reference case. It explained that QKD infrastructures were inherently hybrid systems combining quantum devices, key management systems, encryptors, and classical network components, making visibility, troubleshooting, and compliance significantly more complex than in conventional networks. The presentation highlighted

key challenges such as heterogeneous data sources, vendor-specific interfaces, non-standard log formats, and the need to correlate information across quantum, key-management, and application layers in real time. To address these issues, it proposed a centralized observability approach in which logs, metrics, and events from QKD devices, KMSs, encryptors, and classical routers were collected, indexed, and analyzed using mature data platforms such as the Elastic stack or Splunk. The HellasQCI implementation was presented as an example, showing how unified dashboards enabled real-time monitoring, anomaly detection, root-cause analysis, auditing, and compliance reporting across the entire quantum-secured service chain. Overall, the presentation positioned monitoring and observability not as optional add-ons but as foundational enablers for reliable, auditable, and scalable QKD network operation within EuroQCI-aligned infrastructures.

6.9 From Theory to Practical Security

“Towards a European QCI Standardisation Strategy” by O. van Deventer

This presentation made a strong, action-oriented case for the urgent development of a coherent European standardisation strategy for Quantum Communication Infrastructures, arguing that standardisation was not a bureaucratic afterthought but a strategic investment that directly shaped supply chains, market access, certification, funding opportunities, and long-term competitiveness. It explained that Europe currently lacked a unified QCI standardisation strategy and positioned CEN-CENELEC JTC 22 as the central European body capable of coordinating quantum technology standards across communication, cryptography, metrology, computing, and enabling technologies. The presentation reframed standardisation as a competitive arena in which organisations could choose different levels of engagement—from passive observation to leadership—each carrying different risks and rewards, and highlighted how active participation enabled interoperability, reduced vendor lock-in concerns, improved product credibility through benchmarks and test methods, and aligned products with future regulatory and procurement frameworks. Particular focus was placed on JTC 22 Working Group 4, whose ongoing and planned technical reports addressed QKD network best practices, gaps between QKD and PQC standards, satellite-QKD standardisation needs, and security evaluation shortcomings, all of which were directly relevant to EuroQCI deployments. The presentation concluded with a clear call to action for QCI stakeholders to actively shape standards that reflected European priorities, leverage dedicated EU funding instruments for standardisation activities, and treat standardisation as a strategic tool to grow both their own organisations and the wider EuroQCI ecosystem.

“Towards National QKD Evaluation and Certification” by U. Seyfarth

This presentation argued that the large-scale deployment of QKD required a dedicated evaluation and certification ecosystem to translate theoretical security guarantees into trusted, interoperable, and deployable products. It explained that QKD systems were highly technical and difficult to assess by non-experts, making independent certification essential to provide formal security assurance, enable interoperability between vendors, prevent vendor lock-in, and support regulatory compliance and market confidence. Within this context, the QuNET+BlueCert initiative was presented as a foundational effort to build a European blueprint for QKD certification, covering the definition of test procedures, measurement

devices, evaluation metrics, and a neutral laboratory environment for assessing DV-QKD, CV-QKD, and entanglement-based systems. The presentation emphasized the importance of systematically addressing implementation attacks, drawing on the analysis of more than 300 scientific publications to identify vulnerabilities, attack paths, and countermeasures, while acknowledging significant uncertainty and the likelihood of future discoveries. Certification was framed as a structured process progressing from research and analysis through standardisation to certification and system integration, closely aligned with the Common Criteria (ISO/IEC 15408) and the Common Evaluation Methodology. Functional testing at national metrology institutes and penetration testing at licensed evaluation facilities were highlighted as complementary steps to validate security claims. Overall, the presentation positioned certification as the critical enabler that transformed QKD from a promising research technology into a trusted, scalable, and industrially viable component of EuroQCI and national quantum communication infrastructures.

“How to Keep the Most Dangerous and Sensitive Data Private” by W. Strasser

This presentation introduced fragmentiX as a European quantum-safe cybersecurity company addressing data sovereignty through an information-theoretically secure storage and key management approach rather than relying solely on encryption strength. It presented fragmentiX’s core technology based on cryptographic secret sharing, where data was mathematically shredded into multiple independent fragments and distributed across geographically and administratively separated storage locations, such that no single fragment—or subset below a defined threshold—revealed any information, even to an adversary with unlimited classical or quantum computing power. The presentation emphasized that this approach provided true information-theoretic security for data at rest and in transit, mitigating risks such as cloud provider access, insider threats, regulatory overreach (e.g. CLOUD Act), ransomware, and future quantum attacks. fragmentiX appliances were shown to integrate seamlessly as network drives or object storage interfaces, while supporting quantum-safe key establishment through QKD, distributed symmetric key establishment, PQC, and QRNGs, and operating on certified European hardware platforms. Multiple real-world use cases were highlighted, including protection of sensitive medical data, SME cybersecurity, Fortune 500 and governmental infrastructures, long-distance QKD with trusted repeater nodes, and integration with secure backup, disaster recovery, and classified communication systems. Overall, the presentation positioned fragmentiX as a complementary pillar to EuroQCI and quantum communication infrastructures, extending quantum safety beyond key distribution to end-to-end data sovereignty through a deployable, industrially supported, and certification-oriented solution.

“The Hybrid State-of-Play: How to Securely Combine Quantum and Post-Quantum Technologies” by C. Striecks

This presentation provided a rigorous, security-focused overview of hybrid key establishment as the preferred practical approach for quantum-safe communications, combining conventional cryptography, PQC, and QKD in a modular and provably secure manner. It explained that confidentiality alone was insufficient for real-world deployments and that hybrid schemes had to satisfy a comprehensive set of security properties, including authentication, integrity, forward security, post-compromise security, and crypto agility, all under a unified security proof. The presentation reviewed recent theoretical advances building on the “Muckle” framework, culminating in Muckle+ and related constructions that enabled end-

to-end authenticated hybrid key exchanges with formal security guarantees. It reported on proof-of-concept implementations integrating QKD with PQC key encapsulation and signature schemes using liboqs, showing that overall performance was dominated by QKD key delivery latency rather than PQC overhead, and that algorithm choice had limited impact on system-level performance. The work was explicitly aligned with European Commission recommendations and ongoing ETSI standardisation activities, including the ETSI STF 684 initiative, which aimed to define quantum-resistant standards integrating QKD and PQC by 2027. Overall, the presentation positioned hybrid key establishment as the technically sound and policy-aligned path toward resilient, crypto-agile, and future-proof secure communications within EuroQCI and beyond.

“QKDise Your Applications” by D. Duschl & C. Doberl

This presentation introduced X-NET / zynd as an application-centric approach to integrating QKD and PQC into real software systems, shifting the focus from infrastructure to practical end-user adoption. Rather than requiring applications to be redesigned around QKD, the proposed concept “QKDise your application” enabled existing open-source software to be securely connected to QKD and PQC through modular extensions and standard interfaces. The solution was built around an open-source application layer that could be extended with QKD and PQC modules, supported by professional services for development, maintenance, and training, allowing organisations to adopt quantum-safe security incrementally. The presentation demonstrated applicability across a wide range of use cases, including secure email, chat, audio and video communication, AI workflows, and other open-source applications, highlighting a concrete secure video-conferencing example where QKD and PQC were combined to provide end-to-end encryption. By emphasizing openness, interoperability, and application-level integration, the presentation positioned X-NET’s approach as a pragmatic bridge between EuroQCI infrastructures and real operational services, lowering the barrier for organisations to consume quantum-safe security without deep expertise in quantum networking.

6.10 QCI Days 2025: Scope, Structure and Outcomes

The QCI Days 2025 constituted a flagship dissemination and training event of the HellasQCI project, bringing together a broad spectrum of stakeholders from academia, research organizations, industry, public authorities and the wider European quantum communication community. The event was organized in Athens during April 2025 and served as a high-visibility forum for discussing the state of the art, deployment challenges and future directions of Quantum Communication Infrastructures at both national and European levels.

The QCI Days 2025 were designed as a multi-day event combining strategic discussions, technical presentations and applied use-case sessions. The programme addressed the full value chain of QCI development, from fundamental security principles and network architectures to industrialization, deployment strategies and real-world applications. This holistic approach ensured that the event catered to participants with diverse backgrounds and expertise, while maintaining a coherent narrative around the evolution of quantum-secured communications.

The event was officially opened with high-level sessions focusing on the strategic importance of QCI for Europe's digital sovereignty and cybersecurity. Speakers from European and national initiatives provided insights into policy frameworks, large-scale deployment strategies and cross-border cooperation within the EuroQCI initiative. These opening sessions set the context for the technical and industrial discussions that followed and highlighted the role of HellasQCI as an active contributor to the European QCI ecosystem.

A significant part of the QCI Days 2025 programme was devoted to the security perspective of QKD and its role within modern cryptographic frameworks. Dedicated sessions examined the security properties of QKD, its advantages and limitations, and its interplay with classical and post-quantum cryptographic techniques. These discussions provided participants with a clear understanding of how QKD can be integrated into broader security architectures to address emerging threats in long-term secure communications.

Further sessions focused on large-scale QCI network deployments and operational challenges. Topics included trusted-node versus end-to-end architectures, scalability considerations, interoperability between different vendors and technologies, and the integration of QKD into existing telecommunication infrastructures. These sessions benefited from contributions by experts involved in national and international QCI deployments, offering valuable lessons learned and practical insights

Industrialization and innovation constituted another key pillar of the QCI Days 2025. Dedicated sessions addressed the transition of QKD technologies from research prototypes to deployable industrial solutions. Presentations covered topics such as manufacturing readiness, standardization efforts, certification, and the role of industry in scaling up quantum-secured networks. These discussions highlighted the importance of close collaboration between research institutions, industry players and network operators for the successful commercialization of QKD technologies

The programme also placed strong emphasis on practical use cases and application-driven perspectives. Several sessions showcased QKD-enabled use cases in critical sectors, illustrating how quantum-secured communications can be applied to protect sensitive data and critical infrastructures. These use cases demonstrated the added value of QKD when combined with classical security mechanisms and provided concrete examples of deployment scenarios relevant to both public and private stakeholders.

An important thematic axis of the QCI Days 2025 focused on secure connectivity from Earth to space. Sessions addressed space-based QKD, satellite communication links and the integration of terrestrial and space segments within a unified QCI architecture. These discussions underscored the strategic importance of space assets for achieving pan-European quantum-secured connectivity and highlighted ongoing efforts to align national initiatives with European space-based QCI developments. Beyond the technical content, the QCI Days 2025 played a crucial role in community building. Dedicated sessions focused on strengthening the HellasQCI community, fostering collaboration between stakeholders and promoting knowledge exchange across disciplines and sectors. The event provided ample opportunities for networking and interaction, reinforcing HellasQCI's role as a national hub within the broader EuroQCI ecosystem.

Figure 6.3 Participants during the QCI Days 2025 event

7. Focused Training on Entanglement Photon Pair Sources (EPPs)

This online training session, held on 22nd of October 2024, was organised to provide a focused and technically oriented introduction to QKD with particular emphasis on entanglement-based systems and the BBM92 protocol. The training combined theoretical background with practical system-level insight, guiding participants from fundamental QKD principles to the architecture and operation of a complete entangled-photon QKD setup. Key topics included photon source and laser characteristics, component connectivity, critical system parameters and their impact on performance, and the interpretation of core data metrics such as key rate, quantum bit error rate, visibility, and heralding efficiency. Beyond theory, the session incorporated a guided software walkthrough, configuration options, and discussion of different operational scenarios, enabling participants to understand how design choices and parameter settings affect real system behavior. Through interactive discussions and Q&A sessions, the training aimed to strengthen participants' ability to analyze, configure, and evaluate entanglement-based QKD systems in realistic deployment and experimental contexts.

7.1 HellasQCI Photonic Layer Training – “Entanglement-based quantum Key Distribution” by S. Neumann

This presentation delivered a detailed, hardware-focused introduction to entanglement-based QKD, explaining both the physical principles and the practical realization of eQKD systems within the HellasQCI photonic layer. It introduced entanglement as a source of intrinsically correlated randomness and presented the BBM92 protocol as the operational foundation, highlighting its advantages in terms of long-distance operation, reduced reliance on trusted nodes, and suitability for fully connected network topologies. The presentation walked through the generation of polarization-entangled photon pairs using spontaneous parametric down-conversion in a Sagnac-loop source, their transmission over telecom fiber, and detection with superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs). Significant emphasis was placed on source characterization and system tuning, including pair generation rates, singles and coincidence rates, heralding efficiency, visibility of entanglement, and the impact of losses and filtering, providing quantitative insight into performance optimization. By linking theoretical concepts with concrete engineering parameters and safety considerations, the presentation equipped participants with a realistic understanding of how entanglement-based QKD systems are built, configured, and evaluated in practice for deployment within quantum communication infrastructures.

7.2 HellasQCI Software Layer Training by S. Mair

This presentation focused on the software layer of HellasQCI QKD systems, providing a practical, operator-oriented view of how quantum communication platforms are configured, monitored, and administered in real deployments. It explained how interaction with the system is performed through multiple interfaces, including ETSI GS QKD 014 APIs, web-based user interfaces, Grafana dashboards for monitoring, Linux command-line tools, configuration files, and scientific or hardware-specific endpoints. The presentation distinguished between user and system administrator perspectives, outlining how operators interpret system state, performance indicators, and environmental signals, and how administrators manage software

components, updates, and system health. Emphasis was placed on the fact that the deployed components are specialized, well-tested builds derived from standard software products, operating reliably in controlled environments but still requiring expert understanding for troubleshooting and optimization. The training highlighted the importance of foundational skills in Linux administration, Docker, and general QKD system architecture, and set realistic expectations regarding operational support, updates, and the need for vendor interaction when complex issues arise, thereby framing the software layer as a critical enabler of stable, secure, and maintainable QKD network operation within HellasQCI.

8. Winter School, Thessaloniki November 2025

The HellasQCI Winter School Training Workshop was organized from 26 to 28 November 2025 in Thessaloniki, Greece, as an advanced training event dedicated to quantum-secured communications, with a particular focus on QKD, space-based quantum links, and hands-on system implementations. Hosted at KEDEK and NOESIS, the Winter School brought together researchers, students, industry experts, and representatives of national and European QCI initiatives, aiming to strengthen technical expertise and foster deeper understanding of both theoretical and practical aspects of quantum communication technologies.

The three-day program was structured to progressively guide participants from strategic and policy-level perspectives to advanced theoretical foundations and, finally, to practical hands-on experience. The agenda combined policy-oriented discussions on the EuroQCI vision and national QCI developments with in-depth technical lectures covering quantum information theory, space QKD, photonic technologies, and emerging hardware components. This structure ensured that participants acquired a holistic view of the quantum communication landscape, spanning governance, technology development, and system deployment.

The first day focused on the strategic framework of QKD and its role within the EuroQCI initiative, highlighting the importance of hybrid security approaches that combine quantum and classical cryptographic techniques. Sessions included keynote presentations and panel discussions involving representatives from multiple national QCI initiatives, providing comparative insights into deployment strategies, operational challenges, and best practices across Europe. Industrial sessions complemented these discussions by showcasing commercial QKD solutions and emerging technologies, offering participants exposure to the current state of the market and its evolution.

The second day was dedicated to the theoretical foundations and enabling technologies for space-based QKD. Lectures addressed core concepts of quantum information theory, satellite QKD architectures, and optical communication technologies for space applications. Particular emphasis was placed on practical challenges such as photon detection using SNSPDs, photonic integrated circuits, and high-speed optical transceivers for inter-satellite links. The program also included presentations on national and academic space missions, as well as preparatory sessions for hands-on experiments, bridging theory with practical implementation.

The third day centered on hands-on training activities, allowing participants to directly engage with the building blocks of QKD systems. Through guided laboratory sessions, attendees explored key components and operational principles of QKD setups, gaining practical experience in system assembly, calibration, and performance evaluation. The training concluded with a satellite tracking demonstration at NOESIS, providing a tangible link between terrestrial QKD concepts and space-based quantum communication scenarios.

8.1 National QCIs:

The Winter School and associated training activities brought together national QCI initiatives to present the current state of their deployment, experimentation, and coordination within the EuroQCI framework. Through a series of focused presentations, participating countries outlined their national architectures,

deployment strategies, use cases, and integration paths toward a pan-European quantum-secured communication infrastructure combining terrestrial and satellite segments. Collectively, the material illustrated the transition from pilot-scale demonstrations to operational infrastructures, emphasizing interoperability, standardisation, software-defined control, trusted-node governance, and the gradual integration of space-based QKD. In parallel, strong emphasis is placed on training, competence building, and stakeholder engagement, underlining that the success of EuroQCI depends not only on technological maturity but also on organisational readiness, skills development, and cross-border cooperation.

“Deploying HellasQCI within the EuroQCI Initiative” by I. Papastamatiou

This presentation provided a comprehensive overview of the HellasQCI initiative as the national Quantum Communication Infrastructure of Greece, deployed within the EuroQCI framework. It detailed the design and phased implementation of three metropolitan QKD backbone networks in Athens, Thessaloniki, and Heraklion, interconnected with optical ground stations to support future satellite QKD services. The presentation outlined the layered HellasQCI architecture spanning the QKD layer, ETSI-compliant key management and SDN control layers, and multi-layer service encryption, and documents the evolution from preparatory proof-of-concept deployments to large-scale national and international demonstrations. Particular emphasis was placed on the implementation of 17 multidisciplinary use cases across national security, public health, critical infrastructures, industry, and research, as well as on extensive training activities, community building, and alignment with European standardisation and CEF-funded cross-border initiatives.

“Quantum Communications Activities in Luxembourg: EuroQCI and Beyond” by S. Koudia

This presentation described Luxembourg’s coordinated approach to quantum communications through the LUQCIA laboratory infrastructure and the Lux4QCI national deployment, positioning them within the broader EuroQCI ecosystem. It presented LUQCIA as a state-of-the-art experimental facility supporting QKD research, training, and industry collaboration, and Lux4QCI as an operational multi-technology QKD network integrating different vendors, protocols, and a software-defined key management system. The presentation highlighted cross-border terrestrial QKD demonstrations, ongoing KMS integration and SDN-based orchestration, and Luxembourg’s role in the TransEuroOGS CEF project to enable satellite-terrestrial interoperability via Eagle-1. In addition, it introduced QNETSIM as a validated simulation platform for hybrid terrestrial–non-terrestrial quantum networks, supporting future quantum internet concepts and large-scale system design.

“Cyprus Quantum Communication Infrastructure (CYQCI)” by K. Kalli

The CYQCI presentation outlined Cyprus’s national roadmap for deploying a quantum communication infrastructure that integrates terrestrial QKD networks, QKD research activities, and satellite quantum communications through an optical ground station. It described a fibre-based national QKD network connecting governmental, defence, healthcare, research, and critical infrastructure stakeholders, supported by preliminary deployment results and performance analysis. The presentation further detailed experiments with switched QKD links, highlighting operational challenges such as system stability and re-alignment overheads, and presented plans for satellite QKD connectivity with deployment of an optical

ground station. Strong emphasis was placed on risk management, the establishment of a national Quantum Communication Competence Centre, and extensive training, outreach, and stakeholder engagement activities aimed at ensuring sustainable national adoption of quantum-secured communications.

BG National QCI Presentation – HellasQCI Winter School

This presentation presented the Bulgarian National QCI initiative, focusing on its national deployment strategy, institutional coordination, and alignment with EuroQCI objectives. It outlined the planned QKD network architecture, targeted governmental and critical infrastructure use cases, and the role of national research and telecom stakeholders in supporting deployment and validation. The presentation emphasized the importance of interoperability testing, gradual integration with European cross-border infrastructures, and capacity building through training and collaboration. It positioned Bulgaria’s efforts as a complementary component of the wider EuroQCI ecosystem, contributing to regional coherence and cross-border quantum-secured connectivity in Southeast Europe.

IrelandQCI – Building a Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Ireland

The IrelandQCI presentation documented Ireland’s progress in establishing a national quantum communication infrastructure that combines metropolitan QKD deployment, experimentation facilities, and extensive education and outreach activities. It described an evolving metro QKD network connecting public institutions, industry, and academia, alongside dedicated quantum technology engineering and testing facilities. The presentation highlighted Ireland’s strong focus on training, early-career development, public engagement, and demonstrator use cases, as well as its active participation in EuroQCI coordination actions such as PETRUS and future CEF-funded cross-border projects. IrelandQCI was presented as an example of a balanced approach that integrates infrastructure deployment with skills development and ecosystem building.

“QCI Hungary” by M. Galambos

The QCI Hungary presentation outlined the national strategy and progress toward building a Hungarian quantum communication infrastructure aligned with the EuroQCI vision. It presented the planned terrestrial backbone, integration with existing fiber infrastructure, and the role of trusted nodes and key management systems. The presentation also addressed governance aspects, stakeholder involvement, and the anticipated use cases, focusing on secure government communications and critical infrastructure protection, while highlighting challenges related to scalability, cost, and long-term sustainability.

“Beyond RoNaQCI – Romania National QCI” by B. Ciobanu

This presentation described Romania’s approach to developing its national QCI, including architectural design choices, pilot deployments, and alignment with EuroQCI standards and interoperability requirements. Emphasis was placed on integrating QKD systems with classical cryptographic mechanisms, preparing national stakeholders for quantum-safe transitions, and leveraging cross-border connectivity. The presentation also highlighted Romania’s focus on capacity building, testing environments, and gradual expansion toward operational services.

“National Quantum Communication Infrastructure Sweden (NQCIS)” by M. Bourennane

The Swedish NQCIS presentation provided an overview of Sweden’s national quantum communication infrastructure initiative, detailing its phased deployment strategy and focus on secure, resilient communications. It covered the use of QKD in metropolitan and intercity networks, interaction with research institutions and industry partners, and the emphasis on standardization and interoperability. The presentation also discussed Sweden’s approach to evaluating QKD technologies and integrating them with existing security frameworks to support public-sector and critical-infrastructure applications.

“Estonian Quantum Communication Infrastructure EstQCI” by I. Linnas

The EstQCI presentation outlined Estonia’s national QCI roadmap, highlighting the country’s emphasis on digital trust, cybersecurity, and secure government services. It described planned network topologies, the role of QKD pilots, and integration with Estonia’s advanced digital governance ecosystem. The presentation stressed interoperability with EuroQCI, cross-border collaboration, and the importance of combining QKD with PQC to ensure long-term security.

“QCI CAT 2025 – Lessons Learned by I. Linnas

This presentation summarized lessons learned from QCI-related activities and assessments conducted in Estonia, focusing on technical, operational, and organizational insights. It highlighted practical challenges encountered during deployment and testing, such as infrastructure readiness, integration with legacy systems, and operational complexity. The presentation emphasized the value of early pilots, realistic use cases, and continuous feedback loops to refine architectures and inform future national and European QCI deployments.

8.2 “HellasQCI in Practice: Quantum Network Demonstrations” by G. Kanelos

This presentation provided a detailed, practice-driven account of how HellasQCI translates the EuroQCI vision into large-scale, real-world quantum network deployments and demonstrations, focusing on operational complexity rather than protocol theory. It described the Greek national QCI landscape with three metropolitan backbone networks and satellite-ready optical ground stations, and situated HellasQCI within the broader CEF and EuroQCI framework, including cross-border initiatives such as SEEWQCI. The core of the presentation was the QCI Days 2025 and ECOC 2025 QKD network demonstrations, which showcased a field-deployed, multi-node, multi-vendor, and multi-domain quantum network integrating DV-QKD and CV-QKD systems from different manufacturers through interoperable, multi-layer key management architectures aligned with ETSI standards. These demonstrations supported simultaneous L1, L2, L3, and application-layer encryption services, including the first-ever four-node quantum-secure international video conference across Greece, Austria, and Spain, alongside healthcare, cloud, and research use cases. The presentation further analyzed the architectural and economic challenges of scaling QKD, comparing relayed and dynamically switched QKD networks through both experimental results and theoretical models, and showing that switched QKD offers improved resource utilization, resilience, and scalability in dense urban environments when combined with advanced control, scheduling, and PUF-based authentication mechanisms. Overall, the presentation demonstrated that while significant milestones have been achieved in interoperability, orchestration, and service delivery, further progress in policy definition,

operational management, and shared-infrastructure concepts is essential for transitioning EuroQCI from national pilots to a sustainable, pan-European quantum communication infrastructure.

8.3 Industrial QKD Session

The set of presentations delivered during the HellasQCI Winter School 2025 provided a coherent overview of the technological, industrial, and security dimensions shaping the deployment of quantum-safe communication infrastructures. Together, they address the urgency of transitioning to quantum-resilient networks, the maturation of enabling hardware and photonic components, the emergence of industrial solutions for terrestrial and space-based QKD, and the reinforcement of trust mechanisms through hardware-based security primitives. The contributions combine strategic perspectives, concrete system architectures, product-level developments, and hands-on research outcomes, illustrating how European and national initiatives are moving from experimental validation toward scalable, interoperable, and operational quantum communication ecosystems aligned with the EuroQCI vision.

“Terrestrial eQKD” by M. Selimovic

This presentation introduced entanglement-based QKD as a fundamentally secure approach to future-proof cryptographic key exchange, emphasizing its immunity to both classical and quantum computational attacks. It explained the physical principles of entanglement and monogamy of entanglement, highlighting advantages such as high key rates, long transmission distances exceeding 350 km, and simplified network architectures through centralized wavelength-division multiplexing. The presentation showcased zerothird’s industrial-grade entangled photon sources installed in Athens within HellasQCI, detailed system performance metrics, and positioned entanglement-based QKD as a cornerstone technology for scalable quantum networks beyond algorithm-dependent PQC.

“Quantum Safe Networks – Time to Act Is Now (Nokia)” by T. Fragkioudakis

Nokia’s presentation focused on the immediate need for a defense-in-depth approach to quantum-safe networking, combining PQC with physics-based key generation and distribution mechanisms such as QKD. It outlined a layered security architecture spanning physical, data link, IP, MPLS, and application layers, stressing crypto agility and resilience as essential properties during the long migration period toward quantum-safe infrastructures. The presentation illustrated concrete optical and IP networking components, as well as a real deployment example of the Athens Quantum Secure Network, demonstrating hybrid key management, orchestration across layers, and optimized use of QKD resources in operational environments.

“Single Quantum B.V. Company Pitch – Winter School HellasQCI” by A. Athanasiadou

This presentation presented Single Quantum’s development of SNSPDs as a critical enabling technology for quantum communication systems. It traced the evolution of SNSPD technology from early prototypes to high-efficiency, low-jitter, and high-count-rate commercial systems currently deployed worldwide. The talk detailed product families, customization options, and performance characteristics, highlighting their relevance for fiber-based, free-space, and satellite QKD applications, and underscoring the role of advanced photonic detection hardware in achieving long-distance, high-rate quantum communications.

“QRBIT – Industry Presentation” by G. Giannoulis

The QRBIT presentation described the company’s role in bridging low-TRL research innovations and high-TRL industrial solutions for free-space and satellite-based quantum and optical communications. It outlined QRBIT’s activities in photonic integration, optical terminal development, system prototyping, and end-to-end integration services, as well as its involvement in European and national projects related to EuroQCI and space-QKD. The presentation emphasized technology transfer, TRL elevation, and participation in the emerging quantum technology supply chain, positioning QRBIT as a key industrial actor supporting both terrestrial and space segments of quantum communication infrastructures.

“PUF-based QKD Authentication – QUBITECH Workshop” by N. Sassalou

This workshop presentation addressed the critical challenge of authenticating QKD nodes by introducing Physical Unclonable Functions as a hardware-based root of trust for quantum-ready communications. It explained why secure authentication is essential for QKD protocols and how PUFs enable information-theoretic authentication without storing long-term secrets, overcoming limitations of purely computational approaches. The presentation detailed a proposed enrollment and authentication protocol, demonstrated standalone and rack-mounted prototypes, and reported ongoing R&D activities and demonstrations, highlighting PUF-based authentication as a practical and vendor-agnostic enhancement to the security of QKD networks.

8.4 “Introduction to Quantum Information Theory” by I. Antoniou

This presentation provided a rigorous and conceptually grounded introduction to quantum information, tracing the notion of information from its classical probabilistic foundations to its fundamentally quantum-mechanical reformulation. It began by defining information as a measure of predictability, following Wiener and Shannon, and showed how classical information theory and entropy emerge from probability theory and statistical physics, before demonstrating why these concepts are insufficient to describe physical reality at microscopic scales. The presentation then motivated the need for quantum information by reviewing key experimental and theoretical milestones—wave–particle duality, quantization of energy, atomic spectra, and the photoelectric effect—that led to quantum theory and introduced quantum probability as a departure from classical probability through the use of state vectors, Hilbert spaces, and projection operators. Core quantum phenomena such as superposition, uncertainty, Schrödinger’s cat, and entanglement are presented not as paradoxes but as natural consequences of quantum probability, with entanglement identified as the central resource enabling quantum computation, communication, and sensing. Building on this foundation, the presentation introduced the qubit as the fundamental unit of quantum information, discussed physical realizations of quantum registers, and presented quantum entropy in the von Neumann formalism as the quantum analogue of classical entropy. It concluded by positioning quantum information as the conceptual basis of quantum computing and quantum technologies, highlighting both its deep physical roots and its forward-looking role in computation, communication, education, and interdisciplinary research, including emerging academic programmes in quantum science and technology.

8.5 “Introduction to Space QKD” by A. Stathis

This presentation provided a comprehensive introduction to space-based QKD as a necessary extension of terrestrial QKD to overcome fundamental distance and scalability limitations imposed by optical fiber losses and trusted-node constraints. It motivated quantum-secure communications by highlighting the long-term threat posed by quantum computers and “store now, decrypt later” attacks, and positions QKD as the most mature quantum cryptographic primitive available today. The presentation explained why free-space satellite links are uniquely suited for long-distance QKD, noting that photons traverse only a short atmospheric path while propagating mostly through near-lossless vacuum, enabling continent-scale and global key distribution via LEO, MEO, and GEO satellites. It systematically reviewed satellite-relevant QKD protocol families—prepare-and-measure, entanglement-based, and measurement-device-independent—and compares uplink, downlink, double-downlink, and inter-satellite configurations, identifying satellite-to-ground downlinks as the most feasible near-term option. A substantial part of the presentation was devoted to engineering challenges, including atmospheric absorption and turbulence, cloud coverage, pointing, acquisition and tracking, background noise, wavelength selection, and the harsh space environment, alongside mitigation techniques such as adaptive optics, spatial and spectral filtering, and advanced single-photon detectors. The role of optical ground stations and operational constraints such as satellite visibility, pass duration, and finite-key effects were also addressed. The presentation concluded by framing satellite QKD as a key enabler for future quantum networks and the quantum internet, emphasizing that even before global quantum networking becomes a reality, the technologies developed for space-based QKD are already delivering significant advances in satellite communications, space optics, and secure infrastructure.

8.6 “Comprehensive Tutorial Towards Satellite QKD using QuantLink” by A. Ntanos

This presentation introduced QuantLink as a comprehensive simulation framework designed to model, analyze, and optimize satellite-based QKD links, with a particular focus on realistic satellite-to-ground scenarios relevant to European QCI deployments. It presented QuantLink as an end-to-end toolchain that integrates satellite orbit forecasting, atmospheric channel modelling, protocol-level QKD simulation, and operational constraints to estimate key performance indicators such as secret key rate, quantum bit error rate, and link availability over time. The presentation detailed how more than forty configurable input parameters are used to describe satellite payloads, QKD sources and protocols, detector technologies, optical ground station characteristics, finite-key effects, and channel assumptions, enabling flexible what-if analyses. It demonstrated realistic simulations based on LEO and MEO satellites, including the use of publicly available orbital data, elevation-angle-dependent link budgets, turbulence and pointing losses, background noise, and cloud-free line-of-sight probabilities. Both prepare-and-measure and entanglement-based protocols are supported, allowing comparative evaluation of protocol performance under identical physical conditions. Through European use-case studies connecting multiple optical ground stations via a satellite acting as a trusted node, the presentation showed how QuantLink can assess temporal availability, expected key volumes, and network-level feasibility over multi-week periods. Overall, the presentation positioned QuantLink as a practical decision-support and design tool for planning, validating, and scaling

space-based QKD infrastructures within the EuroQCI context, bridging theoretical models and operational deployment considerations.

8.7 Enabling Quantum Links in Space Through SNSPDs Technology by A. Athanasiadou

This presentation focuses on the critical role of SNSPDs in enabling high-performance quantum communications, particularly for space-based and long-distance QKD applications. It introduced SNSPD technology as the most sensitive and fastest single-photon detection solution currently available, emphasizing its decisive advantages over avalanche photodiodes in terms of detection efficiency, dark count rates, timing jitter, and broadband operation across telecom and extended infrared wavelengths. The presentation described the design, testing, and deployment of large-scale SNSPD receiver systems, including multi-pixel arrays integrated into cryogenic platforms and optical ground stations, with a highlighted use case involving the Aristarchos telescope in Greece and testing campaigns at JPL. Quantitative performance results were presented, showing system efficiencies exceeding 60%–90% at 1550 nm, ultra-low dark counts, sub-15 ps timing resolution, and dramatic jitter reduction through constant fraction discriminator electronics, even at high count rates. The material further demonstrated how SNSPDs significantly enhance entanglement-based QKD by enabling much higher coincidence rates, lower QBER, and extended transmission distances, and discusses ongoing developments such as multimode and polarization-maintaining fiber coupling to ease free-space integration. Overall, the presentation positioned SNSPD technology as a foundational enabler for satellite QKD, deep-space optical communications, and future quantum networks, where detector performance directly translates into increased reach, robustness, and practical feasibility of quantum-secured links.

8.8 “PICs for Space” by M. Zervas

This presentation introduced photonic integrated circuits as a key enabling technology for space-based and terrestrial quantum communications, highlighting how large-scale photonic integration can replicate for optics the transformative impact that electronic integration had on microelectronics. Using LIGENITEC as a concrete example, the presentation explained how silicon nitride PIC platforms support a wide range of quantum, communication, sensing, and space applications by offering low optical loss, high stability, and scalable manufacturing from prototyping to high-volume production. It describes the dual-fab strategy combining a 200 mm line for standardized, high-volume processes and a 100 mm line for flexible R&D and non-standard integration, enabling rapid innovation while maintaining industrial-grade quality and automation. Particular emphasis was placed on performance challenges such as propagation loss, wavelength versatility from visible to mid-infrared, and high-speed modulation, with examples including wafer-scale ultra-low-loss waveguides and hybrid lithium-niobate-on-silicon-nitride modulators achieving bandwidths beyond 100 GHz. The presentation positioned these technologies as critical building blocks for quantum computing, QKD, satellite communications, and space instrumentation, demonstrating how photonic integration is maturing from research prototypes to deployable platforms capable of supporting future quantum communication infrastructures.

8.9 “Optical Communications Technologies Through Space” by I. Kamenidis

This presentation provided a comprehensive overview of optical communication technologies through space, positioning them as a strategic evolution from radio-frequency satellite communications toward ultra-high-capacity, secure, and resilient connectivity. It explained the fundamental advantages of optical wavelengths, including much higher carrier frequencies, narrow beam divergence, improved link budgets, and inherent resistance to interference and jamming, enabling data rates from hundreds of Gbps to the Tbps range with relatively simple modulation schemes. The presentation reviewed key historical milestones in space optical communications, from early interplanetary laser experiments to operational optical relay systems such as ESA’s SpaceDataHighway and recent deep-space demonstrations, establishing the technological maturity of lasercom. It then addressed the main technical challenges, including diffraction limits, pointing, acquisition and tracking accuracy, atmospheric effects, and system-level design considerations. Within this context, the talk introduced current European initiatives such as ESA’s HyDRON mission and the ESTOL standard, which define interoperable, multi-orbit optical networking architectures spanning LEO, GEO, and ground segments. Finally, it presented Hellas Sat’s roadmap toward next-generation optical satellites, notably Hellas Sat 5, envisioned as a multi-mission GEO platform integrating high-capacity optical terminals, optical inter-satellite links, quantum-safe technologies, and hybrid optical–RF capabilities to support future commercial, governmental, and defence communication needs.

8.10 “GreekObs2OGS” by S. Delis

This presentation described the GreekObs2OGS project as a strategic national effort to upgrade the Helmos, Skinakas, and Holomontas observatories into dual-use optical and quantum ground stations forming the space segment of HellasQCI. Managed by ESA under the Greek National Satellite Space Project and funded through the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility, the project aims to deliver fully operational optical and quantum communication capabilities while preserving astronomical functionality through rapid reconfiguration. The presentation detailed the demanding mission-level, optical, and quantum technical requirements, including high-precision tracking, SDA-compliant optical terminals, quantum signal isolation, and full laser safety automation, positioning the observatories for compatibility with future EuroQCI missions such as EAGLE-1. It highlighted Raymetrics’ role as prime contractor and technical coordinator, responsible for system integration, ESA compliance, and consortium management, and emphasizes the strategic value of a geographically distributed three-site architecture that maximizes coverage, resilience, and weather diversity. Overall, the presentation positioned GreekObs2OGS as the foundational space–terrestrial bridge of HellasQCI, enabling space-to-fibre QKD gateways, strengthening national sovereignty in secure communications, and establishing Greece as a regional hub for space-based quantum communications within the evolving EuroQCI ecosystem.

8.11 “Miniaturized VCSEL and PIC Transceivers for High Data Rate Intra and Inter-satellite Optical Links” by I. Stampoulidis

This presentation focused on the development of high-data-rate optical transceivers based on VCSEL and photonic integrated circuit technologies as key enablers for optical intra- and inter-satellite links within future space communication infrastructures. It explained how the transition from RF to optical links allows

dramatic increases in throughput, reduced size, weight, and power, and improved resilience for LEO, MEO, and GEO satellite networks, positioning optical inter-satellite links as a cornerstone for next-generation space systems. The presentation detailed the architecture of compact optical transceivers, combining VCSELs, photodiodes, SiGe BiCMOS electronics, and advanced packaging techniques into highly integrated modules capable of tens to hundreds of gigabits per second, while meeting the stringent environmental and reliability requirements of space. Particular emphasis was placed on the role of photonic integration in enabling coherent detection, migration toward 1550 nm operation, and scalability toward terabit-class links, building on European heritage from missions such as EDRS and recent LEO demonstrations. The presentation concluded by outlining the technology maturation path from early design to flight-qualified hardware, highlighting the importance of a European supply chain and sustained R&D investment to support future space optical networks and their integration with quantum-secure communication infrastructures.

8.12 “PeakSat – AUTH’s Optical Communications CubeSat Mission” by I. Gkolias

This presentation presented PeakSat as an ambitious 3U CubeSat mission designed to demonstrate optical satellite-to-ground communications and to strengthen Greece’s role in the emerging EuroQCI and HellasQCI space ecosystem. Developed through a strategic collaboration between Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and industry partners, PeakSat integrates both commercial and in-house subsystems, with its primary payload being an optical terminal operating at 1550 nm-class wavelengths and supporting data rates up to 100 Mbps. The mission is tightly coupled with the Holomontas Optical Ground Station, which is being upgraded into a fully operational optical and quantum ground station with high-precision tracking and pointing capabilities, forming a key node for space–terrestrial integration. The presentation detailed the system design, environmental qualification, and extensive testing campaigns that have brought PeakSat to flight readiness, as well as a carefully phased in-orbit experimentation plan covering acquisition, calibration, bidirectional optical links, and multi-OGS scenarios. Scheduled for launch in February 2026, PeakSat is positioned as a concrete in-orbit demonstrator that bridges academic research and industrial development, validates European optical communication technologies in space, and contributes directly to the preparation of future quantum-secure satellite communication services within the HellasQCI and EuroQCI frameworks.

8.13 “Holomontas Presentation” by K. Tsiganis

This presentation described the development of the Holomontas Optical Ground Station as a key Greek asset for space-based optical and quantum communications within the HellasQCI and EuroQCI frameworks. It outlined the role of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki’s LTMA group in satellite tracking and laser communications and presents Holomontas as an evolving multi-purpose station supporting LEO tracking, optical communications, and future quantum links. The presentation detailed the installation and commissioning of receiver and transmitter equipment, including a 40 cm OGS prototype, dual-channel reception with more than 120 dB isolation between classical and quantum channels, and secure connectivity to the Thessaloniki HellasQCI node via dedicated dark fiber. It further highlighted infrastructure upgrades under the Greek Obs2OGS initiative to achieve Eagle-1 compatibility, including new domes, telescopes, turbulence mitigation systems, and fiber-coupling capabilities. Finally, the presentation situated

Holomontas within active demonstration activities such as PeakSat and HellasQCI use cases for QKD-encrypted satellite data delivery, positioning the station as a critical space–terrestrial gateway for future quantum-secured satellite communications in Greece.

8.14 “QRNGs for Space QKD” by T. Chrysostomidis

This presentation provided a comprehensive overview of quantum random number generators with a focus on optical, laser phase-noise–based QRNGs as critical enabling components for space-based QKD systems. It explained the role of high-quality randomness in cryptographic security and positions QRNGs as true random number sources derived from fundamental quantum phenomena, contrasting optical approaches with non-optical electronic implementations. The presentation detailed the operating principles of continuous-wave and pulsed laser phase-noise QRNGs, showing how quantum phase diffusion is converted into measurable amplitude fluctuations using unbalanced interferometers, and how this approach enables high-speed randomness generation suitable for GHz-rate QKD protocols. Particular emphasis was placed on integrated photonic implementations, including silicon and InP PIC-based QRNGs, which offer compactness, stability, and multi-gigabit-per-second output while meeting stringent space constraints on size, weight, and power. The presentation further addressed practical challenges for satellite deployment, such as power-efficient electronics, entropy evaluation, randomness extraction using Toeplitz hashing, and compliance with NIST statistical tests, and demonstrates experimentally that PIC-based QRNGs can support decoy-state BB84 QKD over free-space channels with low QBER. Overall, the presentation positioned integrated optical QRNGs as a mature, scalable, and space-compatible technology that underpins secure quantum communications and is essential for future satellite QKD missions within the EuroQCI framework.

8.15 “Theory of Hands-On Experiments” by P. Kourelis

This presentation provided the theoretical foundation underpinning the hands-on laboratory experiments of the HellasQCI Winter School, guiding participants from basic photonic concepts to practical QKD-relevant implementations. It explained how “single photons” are generated and manipulated in real laboratories using weak coherent pulses derived from laser sources, motivated by technological maturity, efficiency, and cost considerations, and introduced the statistical nature of photon number states through Poissonian distributions. The presentation covered the generation, modulation, attenuation, and detection of optical signals, detailing the operation of key components such as laser sources, electro-optic modulators, photodiodes, and single-photon avalanche detectors, together with their non-idealities and performance metrics. Multiple quantum information encoding schemes were discussed, including time-bin, phase, frequency, and polarization encoding, with particular emphasis on polarization-based encoding and interferometric polarization modulation used in practical QKD systems. The material further addressed real-world challenges such as coexistence of classical and quantum signals, spontaneous Raman scattering, crosstalk, and their mitigation using optical filtering, and introduced simplified quantum bit error rate estimation as a diagnostic tool. Overall, the presentation bridged theory and practice by preparing participants to understand, operate, and analyze laboratory QKD setups, laying the groundwork for the subsequent hands-on experimental sessions.

8.16 “BB84 Demonstration and 2-bit Quantum Computer” by I. Theodonis

This presentation provided an educational, concept-driven introduction to quantum cryptography through an intuitive explanation and live-style demonstration of the BB84 QKD protocol, complemented by a hands-on introduction to quantum computing concepts using an NMR-based quantum processor. It began by motivating the need for QKD through the limitations of classical symmetric and asymmetric cryptography in the face of advancing quantum computers, highlighting threats such as “store now–decrypt later” and contrasting them with information-theoretically secure one-time-pad encryption enabled by quantum key exchange. Using photon polarization as the physical carrier of qubits, the presentation explained core quantum principles—including superposition, measurement, no-cloning, and quantum randomness—and showed how BB84 allows two parties to establish a shared secret key while detecting any eavesdropping through measurable error rates. The protocol was presented step by step, from random basis choice and public discussion to key shifting and error checking, alongside a discussion of its practical limitations such as key rate overhead, distance constraints, and detector imperfections. The second part broadened the perspective by introducing quantum computing fundamentals, qubits, superposition, entanglement, and quantum gates, and demonstrated how these abstract concepts map onto real hardware using an educational NMR quantum computer, linking quantum cryptography to the wider quantum technology landscape. Overall, the presentation served as a pedagogical bridge from physical intuition to protocol operation and quantum computing awareness, tailored for training audiences within the HellasQCI Winter School

8.17 Winter School Thessaloniki 2025: Scope, Structure and Outcomes

The HellasQCI Winter School Thessaloniki 2025 constituted an advanced, academically oriented training activity within the HellasQCI project, focusing on space-based quantum communications, optical ground stations and hands-on quantum network demonstrations. The Winter School was organized in November 2025 in Thessaloniki and brought together students, early-stage researchers, academics, engineers and industry experts, offering an in-depth and structured learning experience on cutting-edge quantum communication technologies.

The Winter School was designed as a multi-day programme combining theoretical lectures, system-level discussions and extensive hands-on experimental training. Its scope extended beyond terrestrial QKD systems, placing strong emphasis on the space segment of Quantum Communication Infrastructures and the integration of terrestrial and space-based quantum links within the EuroQCI framework. This approach allowed participants to gain a holistic understanding of end-to-end quantum-secured communication systems.

The first day of the Winter School focused on national and European Quantum Communication Infrastructures and on theoretical foundations relevant to quantum-secured networks. Introductory sessions provided an overview of national QCI initiatives and positioned HellasQCI within the broader EuroQCI landscape. Subsequent lectures addressed quantum information theory and fundamental concepts required to understand the operation and security of QKD systems. These sessions established a solid theoretical baseline for participants before moving to more advanced and application-oriented topics.

The second day was dedicated to space-based QKD and optical ground station technologies. The programme covered space QKD architectures, satellite-based quantum links and end-to-end space quantum communication systems. Dedicated sessions examined enabling technologies such as superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors, photonic integrated circuits and optical communication technologies for space applications. Presentations on Greek optical ground stations, including Holomontas, Helmos and Skinakas, highlighted their role within HellasQCI and the broader EuroQCI space segment.

In addition to the theoretical sessions, the Winter School placed strong emphasis on applied demonstrations and practical understanding. Tutorials and demonstrations covered satellite QKD workflows, system architectures and experimental considerations, enabling participants to bridge theoretical concepts with operational space quantum communication scenarios. These sessions provided valuable insights into the challenges associated with atmospheric effects, link budgets and system synchronization in space-based QKD.

The third day of the Winter School focused primarily on hands-on training and experimental demonstrations. Participants engaged in structured laboratory sessions dedicated to the building blocks of QKD systems, including photon-based protocols, experimental setups and system calibration. These hands-on modules were designed to reinforce the theoretical knowledge acquired during the previous days and to develop practical skills related to the operation and evaluation of quantum communication systems (Figure 7.3).

A highlight of the Winter School was the live satellite tracking demonstration conducted at NOESIS. This activity linked the hands-on QKD exercises with real-world space communication scenarios and illustrated the interaction between terrestrial quantum systems and space assets. The demonstration emphasized the importance of integrating terrestrial and space-based infrastructures in order to achieve secure, pan-European quantum communication networks.

TRAINING EVENT IN THESSALONIKI 2025

3 DAYS
OF TRAINING

3 LABS

40 SPEAKERS

1 ST DAY
HIGH LEVEL
QKD policy &
EuroQCI vision
@ KEDEA

2 ND DAY
THEORY
Space QKD
@KEDEA

3 RD DAY
HANDS ON
QRNG and
QKD BB84 protocol
@WinPhoS

250
ATTENDEES

150 ONLINE

100 PHYSICAL

11 NatQCI

PETRUS EuroQCI
NOSTRADAMUS

15 COUNTRIES
PARTICIPATED

AUSTRIA: QCI-CAT	ROMANIA: RoNaQCI
BULGARIA: BGQCI	SPAIN: EuroQCI-Spain
CYPRUS: CYQCI	SWEDEN: NQCIS
ESTONIA: ESTQCI	SWITZERLAND: Ligentec
GREECE: HellasQCI	UK: University of Strathclyde
IRELAND: IrelandQCI	
HUNGARY: QCIHungary	
ITALY: ThinkQuantum	
LUXEMBURG: Lux4QCI	
NETHERLANDS: Single Quantum B.V.	

Figure 8.1: Participants during the training event in Thessaloniki

9. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented a comprehensive overview of the training activities implemented within Work Package 5 of the HellasQCI project, documenting their scope, content, and overall contribution to the project objectives. The training programme has been designed and executed as a core supporting action for the deployment and future operation of a national Quantum Communication Infrastructure, addressing the need for structured knowledge transfer and practical familiarisation with quantum-secured communication technologies.

Through a combination of lectures, workshops, demonstrations, and hands-on laboratory sessions, the training activities covered a wide spectrum of topics ranging from cryptographic foundations and security principles to QKD systems, post-quantum cryptographic algorithms, hybrid QKD–PQC approaches, and application-level secure communication workflows. This holistic approach enabled participants to develop a coherent understanding of how individual components interact within complex secure communication systems and how design, configuration, and operational choices impact overall security and reliability.

A key outcome of the training programme is the emphasis on real-world applicability and realistic deployment scenarios. By engaging participants with actual tools, software components, standardized interfaces, and representative use cases, the activities moved beyond theoretical exposition and supported practical insight into the challenges and constraints associated with deploying and operating quantum-safe communication infrastructures. The inclusion of cryptographic attack scenarios and failure cases further reinforced awareness of common pitfalls and highlighted the importance of careful system design and informed usage.

The systematic collection and dissemination of training material through the HellasQCI online training platform represents an important element of sustainability and long-term impact. By ensuring that all educational resources remain accessible beyond individual training events, the project establishes a lasting knowledge base that can support future capacity-building efforts, onboarding of new participants, and wider dissemination to relevant stakeholders.

Overall, the training activities documented in this deliverable contribute to the creation of a shared understanding of quantum-secured communications and support the broader objective of preparing the ecosystem required for the adoption of quantum-safe technologies. The outcomes of WP5 strengthen the foundations for the effective deployment, operation, and future evolution of the national Quantum Communication Infrastructure envisioned by HellasQCI, ensuring that technological developments are matched by appropriate skills, awareness, and practical competence.

10. Annex 1 – HellasQCI Training Event reports

10.1 HellasQCI Training Athens 2023 report

HellasQCI

HellasQCI 1st Training Workshop report 18-19 21-22 September 2023, Athens, Greece

Lead beneficiary(s): GRNET

Author(s): Ilias Papastamatiou, Artemis Psarianou, Homer
Papadopoulos

Date: September 26, 2023

Dissemination Level: Public

Report Analysis

The HellasQCI project held its first training event on September 18-19 and 21-22, 2023, at the National Technical University of Athens, Greece.

The training was open to cybersecurity professionals, IT managers and engineers, security and IT experts, researchers, students, and practitioners in the field of quantum communication, as well as decision-makers interested in future-proofing their organisation's security infrastructure. Participants could

attend in person or via livestream through the [GRNET DIAVLOS](#) service. The event had two different thematic axes, namely the “**Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems**” held on 18 and 19 of September and the the “Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)” held on 21 and 22 of September. The two workshops were well-received, with an average of 100 attendees at the first workshop and 75 at the second. In total, **175 unique people** attended the workshops. Additionally an average of **100 people per day participated online** via the GRNET Diavlos livestream service. **Sixteen trainers** provided insights and knowledge on quantum communication. Mr Nicholas Frendo and Mr Noel Farrugia represented Malta’s National QCI and attended the four days full training event.

The new Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, Konstantinos Karantzalos, addressed a welcome note to commence the 4-Day Training Event. The Secretary General mentioned: “I would like to recognize the previous leadership of the Ministry and GRNET for their work on this important project. I wish everyone a successful start to the 4-day training event”.

The Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A., Prof. Stefanos Kollias, in his welcome speech stated: “Quantum technology is one of the technologies that already concern us and will be of great interest to us in the coming period. It will have an impact on all sectors. I am personally involved in machine learning and artificial intelligence and we’re trying to develop technologies compatible with quantum technology. So we found ourselves today at an advanced meeting and training that concerns both engineers, researchers, and students. GRNET, as coordinator of the HellasQCI project, will strive in cooperation with the partner universities to achieve the best education of engineers, students, and researchers in these technologies. I wish you a good start and good luck in this seminar”.

The CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris Dr. Eleni Diamanti was invited as a keynote speaker and presented the “Quantum Technologies - QKD Landscape in Europe”. In her presentation she gave a generic overview of quantum technology and demonstrated the evolution of quantum technologies since the beginning of the 20th century. She showed the European Efforts in Quantum Communication in the period of 2016-2021 and she explained the EuroQCI goals toward the creation of an operational, integrated satellite and terrestrial system that covers the entire EU for the exchange of cryptographic keys in the highest level of security.

The HellasQCI Project Coordinator GRNET S.A., Dr Ilias Papastamatiou, in his presentation made an HellasQCI project overview and explained in detail the goals of HellasQCI and the aim of EuroQCI for the protection of sensitive data and the safety of the communication infrastructures.

The Aristotle University of Thessaloniki–AUTH Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, gave an Overview of Four Day HellasQCI Training.

The CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris Dr. Eleni Diamanti presented the way communication is secured in a quantum world by showing the overall context of quantum communication networks and its combination with PQC and the barriers that are overcome with the use of quantum technology. She also presented the Paris Testbed deployment at the FranceQCI.

Principal Researcher of FORTH Dr Georgios M. Nikolopoulos analyzed the Basic Principles of QKD and gave a brief introduction to QKD. He gave the related definitions of photons, and public key cryptography, he also showed the application of BB84 protocol in the communication process.

The Aristotle University of Thessaloniki–AUTH Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsoinos gave in his presentation an overview of the Quantum Random Number Generators. He also explained that the QRNGs are based on quantum optics.

Assistant Professor at The National Kapodistrian University of Athens HellasQCI Technical coordinator George T. Kanellos divided his presentation in 3 sections, The first was an overview of status of QKD networks, the limitations of QKD technology, explained why a key management process is necessary and gave specific examples of QKD networks. In the second part investigated the emerging technologies that are essential for the deployment of the QKD networks such as Advanced QKD networks controls that are necessary to create large scale networks. In the final section provided specific definitions such as quantum entanglement, distribution, quantum teleportation, and how all that reflect to HellasQCI.

R&D Data Engineering from Space Hellas Mr Ilias Balabanis, gave an overview of encryption and decryption with QKDs and presented a proof of concept that was deployed within the EU OPENQKD project.

Post-doc Senior Researcher Giannis Giannoulis at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Photonics Communications Research Laboratory of National Technical University of Athens in his presentation discussed about the building blocks that are used at the laboratory, what it is expected, what are the challenges and what can be handled at the laboratory when conducting single photon experiments. He also provided the QKD System Architecture, he was focused on the Quantum Layer Implementation and Quantum Layer Evaluation.

Research Director from NCSR Demokritos – WP6 leader, Dr Homer Papadopoulos explained the evolution of safe to quantum safe telecommunications. For the use case of Healthcare he analysed that QKD is not sufficient. He gave the definition of PQC and homomorphic encryption. Finally, he introduced the Healthcare use case being used in HellasQCI. He also gave a short overview of the forthcoming which was to set up an encryptor for a QKD Device.

Director of research in Walton Institute, Partner of the project, Dr Deidre Kilbane, presented the Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Ireland. She gave an overview of QKD National Network in Ireland and showed the use cases at the sectors of Banking & Finance, Cloud and Data Centre, Healthcare, Government and Defense.

Associate Professor at the Department of Electrical Engineering and Informatics of Cyprus University of Technology Dr Konstantinos Katzis presented the Cyprus Quantum Communication Infrastructure. In his presentation he briefly explained the architecture of QKD, the EuroQCI initiative and the objectives of CYQCI. He also explained the application of the QKD network in Cyprus and the use cases that are being developed. He also showed the establishment of the Optical Ground Station.

Coordinator of Polish Quantum Communication coming also from Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center PSNC, Dr Piotr Rydlichowski presented what it is envisioned with the Polish QCI proposal how it relates to EuroQCI, as well as other projects connected with quantum communications and quantum technologies and how to develop secure communication scenarios and use cases.

The second day of the training event was hybrid as the first session was containing lectures at the central auditorium. The day lectures in terms of theory were about the space optics. The second session was containing experiments done in laboratory. The two laboratory sessions were conducted in the Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) of NTUA and in the Optical Communications and Photonics Technology Laboratory at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens.

Post doc researchers at the Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) of NTUA Dr Nikolaos Lyras and Dr Argiris Ntanos presented QKD in Space, satellite ground QKD links. They showed the optical satellite communication systems, they continued to show the advances and the drawbacks of this technology, as well as the Challenges and opportunities. Lastly, they presented the technological steps that can be used in classical and space QKD communications systems and the benefits of space based QKDs.

Post doc researchers at the Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) of NTUA Dr Aris Stathis, in his presentation he gave the theoretical background and described the equipment for the hands-on training. In his presentation he included the generation of photon pulses, the detection of photons, and explained the block of photons that were built in the laboratory.

The following session included the hands-on training that took place in NKUA and NTUA

In brief the NKUA at the optical Communications and Photonics Technology Laboratory National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Department of Informatics and Telecommunications hands-on training included the basic set up of a QKD system and performed some tests over different meters of fiber.

The Laboratory session in the NTUA included the following

- Operating Principle of Single Photon Avalanche Detectors (SPAD)
- Coherent Light: Poissonian Photon statistics and single photon interference
- Generation, transmission and detection of encoded single-photons over a dark fiber
- Transmission and detection of single- photons over free space
- Coexistence of classical and quantum signals over converged fiber/FSO link

On the third day of the training event Senior Research Collaborator at ICS-FORTH, Dr Harry Manifavas presented the role of cryptography in cybersecurity, its weaknesses, adversarial settings, cryptography's weaknesses, security design criteria, and security strength levels.

In the next lesson **Dr Harry Manifavas** covered topics such as the fundamental cryptographic primitives, symmetric cryptography, public key cryptography, cryptographic hash functions, and their practical applications in real-life scenarios.

In the following **Dr Harry Manifavas**, discussed about various cryptographic attacks, including ciphertext- only and known-plaintext attacks, brute force attacks, cryptographic key length recommendations, public key algorithms security, factoring problems, man-in-the-middle and replay attacks, and cryptographic failures.

In the first session of the laboratory **Emmanouil Papadogiannakis from ICS FORTH** made demonstrations which involved attempting to attack a social network by bypassing authentication.

In the second session of the laboratory, he continued to show exploiting cryptographic failures, cipher misuse, and crypto misconfiguration.

On the fourth day of the training event **Dr Harry Manifavas** presented PQC challenges in symmetric and public-key quantum computing, including retrospective decryption, Shor's and Grover's algorithms, threat mitigation, NIST PQC standardization effort, PQC transition recommendations, and cryptographic agility.

Afterwards, **Dr Harry Manifavas** introduced Quantum Cryptography and Quantum Encryption, discussing their use cases, requirements, security, and protocols, as well as their threats, limitations, and criticisms.

Research Director from NCSR Demokritos – WP6 leader, Dr Homer Papadopoulos explored the integration of Quantum Key Derivatives (QKD) into the cryptographic landscape, addressing challenges in practical deployment and exploring current trends in QKD standardization efforts.

In the following session **Collaborating Researcher at the eHealth & Knowledge Management Unit Mr Korakis Antonis and PhD Student for the University of Piraeus and an Early-Stage Researcher at NCSR Demokritos Mr Balaskas** George demonstrated how to extract QKD device keys, using PQC algorithms for digital signatures, encrypting files, and enabling computations on encrypted data without decryption.

Next in the practical session **Mr Antonis Korakis and George Balaskas** provided step-by-step instructions for setting up an encryptor and key retrieval from a QKD device, encrypting files with AES 256, using digital signatures, and understanding Homomorphic techniques for secure cloud computations.

Useful information about the HellasQCI project kick-off meeting and the project's objectives:

- DIAVLOS, GRNET's web streaming service recording or the high level welcome remarks: https://diavlos.grnet.gr/room/611?eventid=14792&vod=12369_event
- Meeting agenda and partners available here : <https://hellasqci.eu/first-training-event/>

Other useful links and info:

- HellasQCI info page on GRNET website: <https://grnet.gr/business-directory/hellasqci/>
- [EuroQCI](#) info website page
- [HellasQCI portal \(Home - HellasQCI\)](#)

- Official project Hashtag: #HellasQCI
- Official kick-off meeting Hashtag:
- GRNET Social Media Channels: [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Instagram](#), [YouTube](#)

Training Event Photo material

Figure 10.1: Plenary Session at the Multimedia Amphitheater, NTUA, Athens

Figure 10.2: Prof. Konstantinos Karantzalos, Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance

Figure 10.3: Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.

Figure 10.4: Keynote speech by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University, Paris

Figure 10.5: From L to R: Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsoinos (AUTH), Prof. Stefanos Kollias (Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.), Prof. Konstantinos Karantzalos (Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance), Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A., Ass. Prof. Kanellos (NKUA - HellasQCI Technical Coordinator), Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist, Boussias Media

Figure 10.6: From L to R: Dr. Homer Papadopoulos, (National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos), Dr. Johanna Sepúlveda Chief Engineer Quantum- Secure Communications, Airbus Defence and Space, Artemis Psarianou BA, DipM, ACIM, MA, AC, (Head of Marketing and Communications Department - GRNET S.A.), Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsokinos (AUTH), Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, (HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A.), Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist, (Boussias Media), Dr Deirdre Kilbane Director of Research in Walton Institute for Information and Communication Systems SETU, IrelandQCI Coordinator, Ass. Prof. Kanellos (NKUA - HellasQCI Technical Coordinator)

Figure 10.7: Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) – Hands-On Experience @ NTUA Operating Principle of Single Photon Avalanche Detectors (SPAD)

Figure 10.8: Research Laboratory – Hands-On Experience @ NKUA National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Training Event Media publications

<https://tomanifesto.gr/hellasqi-theoritikes-kai-praktikes-gnoseis-sto-seminario-gia-tis-kvantikes-technologies-153848>

10.2 HellasQCI Training Crete Sep 2024

A two-day Training Event on Quantum Technologies and Cybersecurity, coordinated by GRNET and FORTH

Aiming at training the new generation of engineers in quantum telecommunication technologies and strengthening cybersecurity at national and European level, the training event on: “Quantum Key Distribution QKD (QKD) and Cyber Security” and two thematic axes EuroQCI Deployment & Cooperation and QKD Systems and PQC for Cyber Security, on September 4 & 5, 2024 at the premises of the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH), in Crete.

This event is a direct continuation of the two previous axes QKD Systems and Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and PQC that were developed during the four-day training event that took place a year ago at the premises of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

The training event was organised by the consortium of the European co-funded project HellasQCI, with the participation of forty (40) speakers from fourteen (14) countries who shared with the audience their specialised knowledge on cutting-edge and rapidly developing quantum technologies. Over four hundred (400) cybersecurity professionals, computer scientists and engineers, as well as students, researchers and academics specialising in the fields of optical and quantum technologies, and representatives of the respective industry, attended the hybrid training event and asked questions to the speakers.

The training event commenced with the addresses of: Athanasios Paliatsos, representative of the General Secretary of Telecommunications and Posts, Konstantinos Karantzas, Greek Ministry of Digital Governance, Dimitrios Katsianis, Assistant Professor, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens and

Deputy Chairman at GRNET S.A., Nektarios Tavernarakis, Chairman, Board of Directors at FORTH, Dimitris Plexousakis, Vice-Chairman, Board of Directors at FORTH, and Fabiana Da-PIEVE, European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT). The high-level session was moderated by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, Senior Project Manager at GRNET, HellasQCI Coordinator.

Amongst the international speakers, the event featured representatives from ten (10) National Infrastructures for Quantum Communications (NatQCIs) including QCI-CAT (Austria), LUX4QCI (Luxembourg), Pionier-Q (Poland), QCI Hungary (Hungary), PRISM (Malta), PTQCI (Portugal), CYQCI (Cyprus), RONAQCI (Romania), EuroQCI SPAIN (Spain) and EstQCI (Estonia), who talked about the challenges faced and solutions applied to enhance cybersecurity, showcasing the excellent cooperation amongst these NatQCIs and the Greek National Communication infrastructure – HellasQCI. Moreover, two important European Quantum-centred projects were presented, Nostradamus and Petrus, which, in turn, contribute to the implementation of the European Quantum Communications Infrastructure (EuroQCI).

During the demo of the QKD network, participants had the opportunity to see a glimpse of the future of secure communications by observing the progress of the HellasQCI testbed on the Athens metropolitan network. The demonstration took place on a complex three-node network, connecting GRNET to the University of Athens at a distance of up to 45 km. Each node was equipped with three layers: the Quantum Layer, the Key Management Layer and the Application Layer, offering integrated encryption solutions. One of the innovations of the demonstration was the hybrid operation of the key management system, which had the ability to manage both quantum keys and classical keys, ensuring uninterrupted security in case of QKD failure. At the same time, the system allowed optimization of QKD resources, requiring fewer pairs of devices to support more nodes. Finally, the demo included QKD devices from different vendors, proving the interoperability and practical application of these technologies.

On the last day of the training event, the participants had the opportunity to visit and enjoy a guided tour of the Skinakas Observatory, a strategic partner of the HellasQCI project. The Skinakas Observatory together with the observatories of Chelmos (Peloponnese) and Cholomontas (Thessaloniki) are being converted into optical ground stations (OGS) for the space part of EuroQCI and HellasQCI provides terrestrial connectivity to the metropolitan network sites – MAN (Heraklion-Crete, Athens and Thessaloniki respectively) via fibre optics and QKD devices.

The event culminated in the realisation that the development of the pan-European EuroQCI initiative, along with the Greek Quantum Communications Infrastructure HellasQCI, will contribute to building secure telecommunications, protecting sensitive data, and safeguarding critical infrastructure. This will ensure a successful and secure transition to tomorrow's digital technology for the citizens, as well as the public and private enterprises, of Greece and Europe.

QCI Days Athens 2025 Report

Greece in the epicenter of a quantum-safe digital future aligned with the EuroQCI initiative

28 - 30 April 2025, Eugenides Foundation, Athens

Lead beneficiary (s): GRNET

Author (s): Ilias Papastamatiou, Artemis Psarianou, Anna Tourtoura

Date: July 1, 2025

Dissemination Level: Public

Abstract: QCI Days 2025, held in Athens from 28–30 April 2025, was a major European event on quantum-secure communication. It was organized by **GRNET**, supported by the **Ministry of Digital Governance**, under the guidance of the **General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post**, as part of the **International Year of Quantum Science and Technology (IYQ)** and **World Quantum Day 2025**, with **AIT** and **Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)** as co-organizers. The event saw strong participation from over 600 attendees (physical & online) across 30+ countries, featuring dynamic discussions, 90+ speakers, and 6 panel sessions.

A highlight was the **cross-border QKD demonstration**, emphasizing progress toward a quantum secure infrastructure. The event significantly contributed to advancing EuroQCI goals and the vision of a quantum secure and digitally sovereign Europe.

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Executive Summary

[QCI Days Athens 2025](#), held from 28–30 April 2025 at the [Eugenides Foundation](#) in Athens, Greece, was a **landmark European event** in quantum-secure communication. Organized by GRNET ([HellasQCI](#) Project Coordinator), AIT ([QCI-CAT](#) Project Coordinator), and UPM ([EuroQCI Spain](#) Consortium partner) under the auspices of the [Greek Ministry of Digital Governance](#) and with the support of the [General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post](#), this third edition of the QCI Days followed the [QKD Days Madrid 2022](#) and [QCI Days Vienna 2024](#) events, positioning itself within the International Year of Quantum Science and Technology ([IYQ 2025](#)) and the **EuroQCI** initiative.

With **over 600 participants** from **30+ countries**, and more than 90 speakers and 6 interactive panel discussions, it provided a high-level platform for leading voices from government, EU institutions, academia, and the private sector to advance the EuroQCI vision and explore the future of secure communications. Moreover, the event highlighted Greece’s strategic role in quantum innovation, particularly through HellasQCI, the national Quantum Communication Infrastructure project coordinated by GRNET.

Overall, the **strong participation**, dynamic **discussions** both during and beyond the panels, the successful **cross-border QKD demonstration**, and the event’s impactful media outreach collectively underscored a clear message: quantum-secure infrastructure is no longer a theoretical ambition—it is a tangible reality now being implemented and scaled across Europe.

Broadcasted daily via **GRNET’s DIAVLOS live webstream service**, the event reached a broad European and international audience. In total, the livestream received ~300 unique viewers per day, originating primarily from Greece, followed by Germany, Austria and Belgium and smaller shares from France, United Kingdom and the Netherlands. The average viewing time was an impressive 00:46:30 reflecting strong engagement from the audience.

The three-day event featured:

High-level opening speeches by Greek, Austria and Spain’s government officials as well as European Commission officials including: Dimitris Papastergiou, **Minister of Digital Governance**, Greece, Konstantinos Karatzalos, **General Secretary of Telecommunications & Post**, Aristeidis Sotiropoulos, **CEO, GRNET**, Vicente Martin, **Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)**, Martin Stierle, **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology**, Ana Rosa Bofill Morientes, **Spanish Ministry of Digital Transformation**, Michael Wiesmüller, **Austrian Federal Ministry of Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure** and Aymard De Touzalin, **European Commission**.

An ongoing multi-vendor live demonstration of cross-border QKD among Greece, Austria, and Spain, showcasing technological maturity and interoperability.

Keynote speeches by global quantum pioneers such as [Professor Artur Ekert](#) from University of Oxford and CQT Singapore, and [Dr. Eleni Diamanti](#), from the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS).

Presentations from **25 National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCIs)**: HellasQCI (Greece), QCI-CAT (Austria), EuroQCI Spain, Pionier-Q (Poland), QCI.DK (Denmark), Q-net-Q (Germany), PTQCI (Portugal), CZQCI (Czech Republic), Be-QCI (Belgium), SiQUID (Slovenia), RoNaQCI (Romania), skQCI

(Slovakia), QCINed (The Netherlands), EstQCI (Estonia), PRISM (Malta), IrelandQCI, BGQCI (Bulgaria), CroQCI (Croatia), NQCIs (Sweden), NaQCI.fi (Finland), FranceQCI, CYQCI (Cyprus), QCIHungary, Lux4QCI (Luxembourg), QUID (Italy).

90+ speakers from **30+** countries (EU member states & beyond)

6 Interactive panels, Petrus workshop, a dedicated exhibition area with **20** exhibitors

4 Premium Sponsors: NOKIA, AdaptIT, ID Quantique, and Fortinet.

Overflow room: **17** Posters

Dome projection at the Eugenides Foundation New Digital Planetarium with the theme: [We are Stardust](#)

A final **keynote** by **Assistant Professor Dimitris Katsianis**, Deputy Chairman of GRNET, emphasizing trust, collaboration, and digital sovereignty in the Quantum era.

Report Analysis

Day-by-Day Highlights

Day 1: April 28, 2025

Theme: Securing the Digital Future: Quantum Key Distribution & Beyond

Opening Session: **The Future of Secure Communications in Europe** with:

Dimitris Papastergiou, Minister of Digital Governance, Greece

Konstantinos Karatzalos, General Secretary of Telecommunications & Post

Aristeidis Sotiropoulos, CEO, GRNET

Vicente Martin, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)

Martin Stierle, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

Ana Rosa Bofill Morientes, Spanish Ministry of Digital Transformation

Michael Wiesmüller, Austrian Federal Ministry of Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure

Aymard De Touzalin, European Commission

Demo Overview and Presentation: Assistant Professor **George T. Kanellos**,

Technical Coordinator of the HellasQCI project from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, introduced the live **QKD** demonstration. He then guided participants to the exhibition area, where HellasQCI showcased the first-ever live, 4-node quantum-secure video conference between four major Greek institutions: NCSR-D, NTUA, NKUA, and GRNET.

Moreover, the demo presentation featured a 15-node multi-vendor cross-border QKD network among Greece, Austria, and Spain, showcasing technological maturity and interoperability.

Focus: George T. Kanellos discussed the technical aspects of the HellasQCI demo, including its deployment readiness and the urgency of addressing the quantum threat.

Session Conclusion: The demonstration underlined that quantum threats are imminent and that R&D must evolve rapidly into deployment-ready innovations.

Keynote by **Professor Artur Ekert** on the unpredictability of quantum mechanics.

High-level panel discussion on the future of secure communication in Europe moderated by D. Mallas, CNN Greece with panelists: A. Ekert, K. Karatzalos, Aymard De Touzalin, M. Stierle, V. Martin

Focus: The panelists explored regulatory frameworks, interoperability, and challenges in implementing QKD infrastructures across Europe.

Session Conclusion: The discussion concluded that collaboration among EU member states and stakeholders is crucial to building robust, harmonized infrastructures.

Session on “**The Security Perspective of QKD**” with distinguished speakers including: Keith Elder, Senior Consultant at Deutsche Telekom, representing the Petrus Coordination & Support Action initiative, Hannes Hübel, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, representing the Nostradamus Project, Evangelos Zacharakis, Director of the Centre for Technological Support, Developments and Innovation (KETYAK), Panagiotis Akouilanos, Hellenic National Defence General Staff (HNDGS)

Focus: The speakers emphasised the urgent need to raise awareness of quantum threats among non-classified sectors and to promote early adoption of QKD technologies. They highlighted the current focus on secure data transmission and discussed the growing range of quantum applications being tested—especially in research, defense, and military domains.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that while awareness and application of QKD are high in classified and defense sectors, broader engagement from non-classified users is essential to drive widespread adoption. As quantum threats grow more imminent, deploying quantum technologies efficiently—especially in data security—is crucial to restoring trust and resilience in digital communications.

Panel discussion with the speakers of the session “The Security Perspective of QKD”, moderated by Assistant Professor Dimitris Mitropoulos at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), Head of Reliability Engineering Directorate at GRNET

Focus: The panel focused on the security framework necessary for the reliable deployment of QKD systems across Europe. Speakers addressed the need for EU-wide standardisation and certification protocols, stressing the importance of regulatory clarity to enable interoperability between national infrastructures. The discussion also emphasized the role of top-down awareness efforts to expand QKD adoption beyond classified environments and into broader public and private sectors

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that achieving secure and interoperable QKD deployment across Europe depends on the establishment of unified EU certification and standardisation schemes.

Session on **Large Networks Deployments** and a subsequent Q&A session: Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, GRNET, HellasQCI project coordinator, Sebastian Ramacher, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, representing QCI-CAT - Austria, Andrea Gorni, The Institute of Photonic Sciences (ICFO), representing EuroQCI Spain, Piotr Rydlichowski, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), Pionier-Q project coordinator - Poland, Dev Null, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), QCI.DK, Thomas Hühn, HS Nordhausen, Q-net-Q project - Germany.

Focus: Speakers focused on the implementation challenges of long-distance quantum links, integration of PQC, and collaborative efforts under the CEF funding framework. There was significant emphasis on infrastructure readiness, cross-border interoperability, and real-world constraints, secure node definitions, and aerial fiber behavior.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that national QCI projects are progressing from pilot deployments to robust infrastructures, with growing alignment under the EuroQCI initiative. Key takeaways included the urgent need for harmonized EU-wide security baselines for cross-border links, the critical role of scalable and secure KMS implementations, and the technical complexity of integrating quantum systems

into existing ICT networks. Collaboration, standardisation, and incremental scaling—starting with local links—were identified as essential to achieving an operational, interconnected, and secure European quantum communication network.

QKD use cases and a subsequent Q&A session: Catarina Bastos, PTQCI, Indra Deimos, Jan Bouda, CZQCI, Masaryk University, Emmanuel De Vinck, Be-QCI, Belnet, Anton Ramsak and Lara Ulcakar, SiQUID, University of Ljubljana, George Pantelimon Popescu, RoNaQCI, University Politecnica Bucharest and a subsequent dynamic Q&A session.

Focus: Speakers from the above-mentioned national QCI projects shared their network architectures, deployment strategies, and lessons learned. They focused on practical use cases, KMS implementation, educational initiatives, and the importance of certification and interoperability.

Session Conclusion: The panel discussion that followed featured interesting views by the speakers and the session concluded that while many countries are making strides in QKD deployment and training, certification remains a key bottleneck to broader adoption, especially in classified and long-distance use cases. There was consensus that education, standardisation, and software readiness are critical next steps. A recurring theme was the **need to promote awareness and trust in QKD technologies** among institutions and the public, with certification frameworks playing a pivotal role in building credibility and enabling integration with existing infrastructures.

Short **presentation** of the **4 premium sponsors of the QCI Days Athens 2025:** Polychronis Papachristou, ADAPTIT SA, Fortinet (presented a video message), Catherine Simondi, ID Quantique, Themistoklis Sofos, NOKIA.

Day 2: April 29, 2025

Theme: Europe's Quantum Industry & Ecosystem Development

Enrique Sanchez, from Forschungszentrum Jülich, speaking on the **International Year of Quantum Science and Technology (IYQ 2025)**

Focus: The significance of 2025 as the International Year of Quantum, spotlighting Europe's ambitions in quantum science, technology, and sovereignty.

Session Conclusion: The speech emphasized the need for innovation, industrial capacity (including chip manufacturing in the EU territory), and public awareness to shape the EU Quantum Act.

Session on **Industrialisation of QKD** with: David Morcuende representing QuIC, Francesco Stocco from Telsey, representing Equo, Remon Berrevoets from Q*Bird representing Equo, Philippe Grangier from CNRS, representing QKISS, Sebastian Etcheverry from LuxQuanta, representing Quarter, Imran Khan from KEEQuant, representing SEQRET, Anna Kaminska from Creotech, representing eCausis and Panel Discussions with all the above speakers as panelists and Laura Ortiz from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid as moderator.

Focus: The session focused on the **industrialisation of QKD technologies** across Europe, featuring insights from DEP1 projects and the European Quantum Industry Consortium (QuiC). Speakers highlighted the progress in developing high-TRL QKD systems, their integration with classical infrastructure, and key management systems (KMS) tailored to diverse topologies. Emphasis was placed on interoperability, real-world deployments, and industry-grade demonstrations across major cities.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that industrialisation of QKD is no longer aspirational—it is in motion across Europe with live testbeds, market-ready prototypes, and aligned policy roadmaps. Panelists agreed that QKD and PQC should be pursued in parallel as complementary solutions, especially in high-security contexts. Certification and security standards emerged as urgent gaps, requiring joint effort across research, industry, and policy bodies. The path forward includes stronger stakeholder collaboration, clarity around security assumptions, and continuous education to ensure that QKD technologies are not only secure and interoperable but also trusted and adopted at scale.

Company pitches with representatives from **eleven (11) companies**, including the 4 premium sponsors of the QCI Days Athens 2025: Polychronis Papachristou from ADAPTIT, Bill Nikolopoulos from Fortinet, Themistoklis Sofos from NOKIA, Jean-Robert from ID Quantique, Simone Capeleto from ThinkQuantum, Hagai Eisenberg from HEQA Security, Ulrich Eismann from KEEQuant, Leif Eric Hintzsche from Quantum Industries, Victor Gomis from LuxQuanta, Lee Johnson from Toshiba, and Tommaso Occhipinti from QTI.

Focus: The company pitch session featured key industry players showcasing cutting-edge quantum technologies and solutions, including the 4 premium QCI Days Athens 2025 sponsors: ADAPTIT, Nokia, Fortinet, and ID Quantique - who had the opportunity to pitch their company in 4 minutes - to emerging innovators in QKD, secure connectivity, and quantum hardware including: ThinkQuantum, KEEQuant, LuxQuanta, Quantum Industries, Toshiba, HEQA Security, and QTI who pitched for 2 minutes.

Session Conclusion: This session underscored the vibrancy of the European quantum industry, revealing a dynamic mix of mature vendors and agile startups driving forward quantum-secure solutions.

Session on **Innovations for Quantum-secured Networks** with representatives from five (5) National QCIs projects: Djeylan Aktas from Slovak Academy of Science representing skQCI - Slovakia, Alexander Scheltinga from Quantum Delta NL representing QCINed - the Netherlands, Ingrid Linnas from Estonian State Infocommunication Foundation, representing EstQCI - Estonia, Johann Briffa from University of Malta, representing PRISM - Malta, Deirdre Kilbane from Walton Institute, representing IrelandQCI.

Focus: This session featured cutting-edge developments from the above-mentioned national QCI projects, each presenting novel architectures and technology pilots. Speakers emphasized real-world implementations of **meshed quantum networks**, entangled photon distribution, **open Key Management Systems (KMS)**, and hybrid approaches integrating QKD with PQC to secure governmental infrastructure and public services.

Session Conclusion: The session highlighted a growing trend of innovation and cross-border collaboration within the EuroQCI framework. The NatQCI Projects demonstrated that scalable, **interoperable quantum-secured networks** are rapidly

transitioning from research to deployment. The **convergence of QKD and PQC** emerged as a practical path forward for building resilient quantum communication infrastructures across Europe.

Session on **QKD Use Cases** with BGQCI, CroQCI, NQCI, NaQCI.fi, FranceQCI

Focus: This session showcased national QCI initiatives from the above-mentioned NatQCIs, each presenting practical use cases, testbed deployments, and network topologies tailored

to local needs. Speakers highlighted applications in public infrastructure, government services, and cross-border connectivity, while emphasizing technical flexibility, training, and hybrid deployment models.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that while each national QCI project is shaped by its own infrastructure and policy context, common themes—such as **modularity, adaptability, and client-specific use cases** are critical for broader adoption. The Q&A underscored the **need for interoperability**, vendor transparency, and real-world **validation to strengthen trust** and utility.

Second round of **Company pitches** with representatives from twelve (12) companies: Werner Strasser from fragmentiX Storage Solutions, Juan Pedro Brito Mendez from Qoolnet, Marc-Antoine Potagnik from AUREA TECHNOLOGY, Merquy, Nikolaus Dürk, Christoph Döberl from X-NET, Patrick Dieterich from QTLabs, Anna Hedegaard from QuantumPrime, Thanos Bezaitis from Vector Technologies, Jean Menguy from Cailabs, Aida Garcia from Q-DYNAMICS, Thomas Nieddu from Weling, and Remon Berrevoets from Q*Bird.

Focus: The second round of company pitches brought forward a diverse set of quantum and cybersecurity companies presenting innovations ranging from space-based quantum communications to integrated satellite modules, secure storage, and cost-effective QKD systems. Companies highlighted practical solutions for classical and quantum networks, emphasizing scalability, affordability, and sector-specific adaptability across telecommunications, defense, research, and education.

Session Conclusion: This session reaffirmed the breadth and depth of Europe's quantum industry landscape, featuring **both established players and agile startups** addressing different layers of the quantum value chain. The pitches showcased a strong emphasis on real-world deployment, modularity, and **future-ready infrastructure** pointing to a **rapidly maturing market** ready to support the **EuroQCI vision**.

Session on **Secure Connectivity from Earth to Space** with representatives from six important projects: Thomas Bäumer from SES, representing the EAGLE-1 project, Pedro Pinto from Hispasate, representing GEO-QKD, Kyriacos Kalli from Cyprus University of Technology, representing the CYQCI project, Oláh Kitti from Budapest University of Technology and Economics, representing QCIHungary project, Seid Koudia from University of Luxembourg, representing the Lux4QCI project, and Marco Gramegna, from Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM), representing the QUID project.

Focus: This session explored the expanding frontier of space-based quantum communications, with updates on key initiatives including EAGLE-1, GEO-QKD, and national efforts from Cyprus, Hungary, Luxembourg, and Italy. Speakers discussed the development of **optical ground stations (OGS), satellite-based QKD protocols**, and the role of interoperability, security protocols, and **quantum memory** in linking terrestrial and space segments for a future quantum internet.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that secure satellite-enabled quantum communication is progressing with active ground station development, protocol standardisation, and satellite mission planning. Projects like EAGLE-1 and SEQUIRE mark major milestones in Europe's move toward integrated terrestrial-space QKD infrastructure. Despite environmental and technical challenges, the vision of a quantum-secure, transcontinental network is fast becoming a concrete component of the EuroQCI roadmap.

Ongoing Demo Presentation of a **15-node cross-border QKD network** (Greece, Austria, Spain)

Ongoing exhibition with **20 industry exhibitors** and **17 poster presentations**

Evening event with VIP **Dome projection** in the New Digital Planetarium of the Eugenides Foundation with theme: We are stardust.

Dinner Reception with live music

Day 3: April 30, 2025

Theme: Deployment Strategies & User Opportunities

Session on **Building the HellasQCI Community** and subsequent panel discussion moderated by S. Papathanasopoulou, Gen. Secretariat of Telecommunications & Post. This session featured leading experts including: Zenon Mousmoulas, GRNET,

P. Dimitrakis, from NCSR Demokritos, D. Syvridis, from NKUA, H. Avramopoulos, from NTUA, P. Papachristou, from ADAPTIT, B. Nikolopoulos, from FORTINET, G. Gardikis, from SPACE HELLAS.

Focus: This session centered on **Greece's national efforts** to build a sustainable quantum ecosystem through the HellasQCI project. Speakers from **academia, government, and industry** highlighted the **infrastructure under development**, including a multi-domain QKD network, use-case demonstrations, training platforms, and cross-sector collaboration. The session also emphasised the **strategic importance of national planning**, community building, and integrating quantum technologies into research, education, and critical services.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that Greece is laying strong foundations to become a **key player** in Europe's quantum landscape. The **HellasQCI** project, with its national testbeds and open stakeholder engagement, exemplifies how coordinated community-building can **drive technological progress**. Education, national strategy alignment, and vendor-academic cooperation emerged as essential pillars for **accelerating adoption**. By transitioning from experimental setups to real-world deployments, **Greece is positioning itself to lead** within the broader EuroQCI framework.

Keynote Speech by Dr. Eleni Diamanti (CNRS, France) on "**What makes a successful EuroQCI?**"

Focus: In her keynote, Professor Eleni Diamanti explored the **key factors** that will determine the success of the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI). She outlined the **evolution of quantum networks** from proof-of-concept to scalable, secure communication systems and emphasized the

importance of performance metrics, certification, global collaboration, and hybrid cryptographic strategies that integrate QKD with PQC and classical systems.

Session Conclusion: The keynote concluded that achieving a successful EuroQCI hinges on advancing technical performance, ensuring interoperability through standardisation, and demonstrating real-world quantum advantage beyond QKD. Diamanti called for a defense-in-depth security strategy, closer alignment between research and certification bodies, and investment in high-TRL systems. She highlighted that the quantum future depends not only on robust technology but also on a cohesive European vision and international cooperation in building quantum-safe, interconnected infrastructures.

Session and subsequent panel discussion: **From Theory to Practical Security**

(QKD standardisation, deployment)

Focus: This session bridged the gap between theoretical quantum cryptography and its practical implementation, focusing on standardisation, certification, and hybrid security models. Speakers addressed the urgent need for European-wide QKD standards, national certification frameworks, and practical tools like secure storage solutions. Presentations also explored combining QKD with PQC cryptography for enhanced resilience and outlined the steps for integrating QKD into real-world applications.

Session Conclusion: The session concluded that **transitioning** from theoretical frameworks to secure, real-world quantum communication **requires coordinated standardisation**, credible **certification schemes**, and **adaptable hybrid solutions**. As quantum threats loom closer, developing crypto-agile infrastructures and enabling the seamless integration of QKD into everyday applications are critical.

Session and subsequent Panel Discussion: **Listening to the Market – End-User Perspectives**, moderated by Dr. Diamanti featuring experts from the industry including: Marta Buffa from NOKIA, Jean-Sebastien Pegon from ID Quantique, Juan Morales Saez from Telefonica, Konstantinos Chatzifotis presentation - Vithoukas Dionisios round table discussion from Motor Oil, Alejandra Beghelli Zapata from British Telecom, and Andreas Neuhold from CANCOM.

Focus: This session explored the critical role of industry engagement and market-driven insights in shaping the future of quantum-secure communication technologies. With participation from major stakeholders from EU and beyond, the discussion centred on aligning technological innovation with real-world end-user needs. Key themes included secure-by-design network architectures, regulatory compliance, cost-effectiveness, and risk mitigation strategies in anticipation of quantum-era threats. The panel also highlighted the importance of bridging academia and industry to ensure that advanced research translates into deployable, scalable, and value-driven solutions that resonate with evolving market expectations.

Session Conclusion: The discussion reaffirmed that **listening to market** signals is essential to the successful deployment of quantum communication solutions. **Security, cost, and regulatory compliance** were identified as immediate concerns, but the panel emphasised the need to also uncover and address **hidden end-user expectations**. A proactive, security-by-design approach, capable of integrating into existing networks and preparing for quantum-related risks, was presented as an imperative, as well as meaningful industry-academic collaboration and early engagement with end-users.

Closing Speech Dimitris Katsianis, GRNET Deputy Chairman: Emphasized quantum tech as a matter of strategic digital sovereignty and trust.

Focus: In his closing keynote, Assistant Professor Dimitris Katsianis GRNET Deputy Chairman, reflected on the **collective achievements of QCI Days Athens 2025** and emphasized the strategic **shift of quantum technologies** from academic research to national infrastructure. He celebrated the meeting of diverse stakeholders governments, institutions, researchers, and industry coming together for a unified purpose and underscored the critical role of **trust, collaboration, and coordination** in building a secure, quantum-ready Europe.

Session Conclusion: The keynote concluded with a clear **call to action:** to transform momentum into long-term commitment. **EuroQCI is already being deployed**, but success will depend on inclusive collaboration, capacity building, and policy alignment. **Greece** reaffirmed its role as a leader in this ecosystem, and **GRNET is committed** to continuing its work through the HellasQCI project.

Closing Ceremony of QCI Days Athens 2025 - The Quantum Key returns to its custodian, AIT - Austrian Institute of Technologies, for safekeeping.

Petrus Workshop moderated by Keith Elder, Petrus

Aggregate Statistics

Physical Attendees: **~300**

Online Attendees: **~300** daily unique viewers on GRNET's live web streaming service DIAVLOS

Speakers & Moderators: **90+**

Participating Countries: **30+**

National QCI Projects Represented: **25**

Posters: **17** NatQCIs posters

Exhibitors: **20** tech exhibitors & **4** premium sponsors

Panels & Q&A Sessions: **6**

Live Demonstration: **1** large-scale QKD demo demonstrating cross domain connectivity between Greece, Austria and Spain

Conclusion

QCI Days Athens 2025 provided more than just updates, it **solidified a European community** around the **shared goal** of quantum-secure communication. With the support of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance, the leadership of GRNET, the coordinated efforts of three national Quantum Communication Infrastructure Projects from Greece (HellasQCI), Austria (QCI-CAT) and Spain (EuroQCI Spain), and the

broader EuroQCI framework, Europe is well-positioned to advance quantum technologies and safeguard its digital sovereignty.

Over the course of three days, the event showcased the real-world maturity of national QCI projects, cutting-edge innovations in terrestrial and satellite-based QKD, and the increasing convergence of research, industry, and policy. From multi-node QKD demonstrations and training platforms to panel discussions on certification, interoperability, and post-quantum hybridisation, it became clear that Europe’s quantum ecosystem is entering a phase of actionable deployment.

Keynote speeches underscored the importance of performance metrics, trust-based collaboration, and global coordination. The strong presence of academia, cybersecurity experts, and industry—from startups to space-tech leaders—demonstrated the full breadth of the quantum value chain. Greece emerged as a confident leader, not only in infrastructure and technical expertise but also in community-building, strategic alignment, and vision.

The organising and programme committees of QCI Days Athens 2025 wish to extend a warm thank you to all speakers, organisers, and participants for building the future—secure, interconnected, and quantum-ready. Let this gathering not only mark the end of a successful event, but the beginning of deeper cooperation and continued progress across Europe’s quantum frontier.

Useful Links:

Event Website and agenda [here](#). Press Release in English [here](#). EuroQCI [here](#).

HellasQCI [here](#). Austria QCI [here](#). Spanish QCI [here](#).

DIAVLOS Recorded Livestream [1st Day](#)

[2nd Day](#) [3rd Day](#)

Photo Gallery

10.4 HellasQCI Winter School Assessment Report

Assessment Report

Event: HellasQCI Winter School – Training Workshop

Dates: 26–28 November 2025

Venues: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, WinPhos Lab, KEDEA

Framework: HellasQCI Project – National Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Greece

Overview

The **HellasQCI Winter School – Training Workshop**, held on 26–28 November 2025, marked a significant milestone in the training activities delivered by the HellasQCI consortium as part of Greece’s national quantum communication initiative. Organised under the International Year of Quantum Science and Technology (IYQ), and held under the auspices of the Ministry of Digital Governance and Artificial Intelligence, the workshop aimed at training the next generation of engineers in quantum telecommunications and advancing cybersecurity capabilities at the national and European level. HellasQCI, Greece’s national quantum communication infrastructure deployed within the wider EuroQCI initiative, is co-funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101091504).

The Winter School represents a key step in strengthening Europe’s quantum-secure ecosystem through a high-impact programme tailored to three main stakeholder groups: academic and research staff, digital security experts, and end-users from national security authorities and critical infrastructure operators. More than 250 students, researchers, and professionals were trained in QKD, quantum network architectures, and quantum-secured applications, while 40 international speakers from 15 countries contributed to fostering knowledge exchange and cross-border alignment.

Beyond skills development, the programme supports Greece’s readiness for the upcoming EuroQCI CEF Phase 2 deployments—most notably the SEEWQCI and TransEuroOGS projects starting in January 2026—and reinforces the country’s role as a regional hub for Southeast European quantum infrastructure. By engaging industry stakeholders and endorsing commercially viable, quantum-ready cybersecurity solutions, the Winter School strengthens the long-term sustainability and interoperability of HellasQCI within the broader European quantum communications landscape.

Watch the **video** with the Highlights [here](#)

Event Overview & Execution

The HellasQCI Training Event in Thessaloniki (2025) was successfully implemented as a three-day, intensive capacity- building programme combining policy-level discussions, advanced technical theory, and hands-on practical training in QKD.

The event was organised under the framework of the HellasQCI project, under the auspices of the Ministry of Digital Governance and AI, and aligned with the objectives of the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI).

The training programme spanned three days, covering three complementary thematic pillars: (i) high-level QKD policy and the EuroQCI vision, (ii) theoretical foundations and technologies for space-based QKD, and (iii) hands-on training on QRNGs and QKD protocols, including BB84.

A total of three dedicated laboratory sessions were delivered, ensuring strong practical engagement alongside theoretical learning.

The event brought together 40 expert speakers from academia, research organisations, industry, and national authorities, representing 11 National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCIs) and key European initiatives, including PETRUS and NOSTRADAMUS. Participation was broad and inclusive, with approximately 250 attendees, combining 150 online participants and 100 physical attendees, enabling both wide outreach and in-depth on-site interaction.

In total, 15 countries were represented, reflecting the strong pan-European dimension of the event and its alignment with EuroQCI objectives. The training was executed through a hybrid format, leveraging modern conferencing infrastructure for remote access while maintaining high-quality in-person sessions, laboratories, and demonstrations. This approach ensured effective knowledge transfer, active participation, and meaningful networking across national and disciplinary boundaries.

Overall, the event was executed in a structured, efficient, and impactful manner, reinforcing HellasQCI’s role as a national and European hub for quantum communications training and contributing directly to workforce development, interoperability, and ecosystem building within the EuroQCI framework.

Thematic Content

Day 1 – High-Level QKD Policy and EuroQCI Vision (26 November 2025, KEDEA)

The first day of the HellasQCI Winter School focused on the strategic, policy, and ecosystem dimensions of QKD and the EuroQCI initiative. The training opened with welcome remarks from representatives of the Ministry of Digital Governance and AI (MinDigital), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), GRNET, KETYAK, and the Hellenic Space Center (HSC), highlighting the national importance of quantum-secure communications for public administration, national security, research, and space applications. An overview of the three-day programme was provided by AUTH, followed by a keynote lecture from the University of Strathclyde, setting the scientific and technological context for quantum communications in Europe, and a presentation by NKUA on HellasQCI's participation in flagship EuroQCI demonstrations (QCI Days 2025 and ECOC 2025).

The programme continued with an overview of the PETRUS and NOSTRADAMUS projects, presented by Deutsche Telekom, illustrating how large-scale European initiatives contribute to interoperability, validation, and industrialisation of QKD technologies. A dedicated panel on National Quantum Communication Infrastructures (NatQCIs) brought together representatives from [HellasQCI](#) (GRNET), [Lux4QCI](#) (University of Luxembourg – SnT), [CYQCI](#) (Cyprus University of Technology), [BGQCI](#) (Teleconsult EOOD, Bulgaria), and [IrelandQCI](#) (Walton Institute, SETU), providing a comparative overview of national deployment strategies and cross-border collaboration. In the afternoon, a second NatQCI panel included contributions from [QCI-CAT](#) from Austria (AIT), [EuroQCI Spain](#) (ICFO), [EstQCI](#) from Estonia (RIKS), [NQCS](#) from Sweden (Stockholm University), [QCIHungary](#) (KIFÜ) and [RoNaQCI](#) from Romania (University Politehnica of Bucharest), underlining the pan-European dimension of EuroQCI.

The day concluded with an industrial QKD session featuring European technology providers and integrators, including ThinkQuantum, Zero Third, Nokia, Single Quantum, QRBIT, and QUBITECH, offering insights into commercially available QKD systems, components, and deployment challenges, followed by a networking reception.

Day 2 – Theory for Space QKD and Optical Ground Stations (27 November 2025, KEDEA)

The second day was dedicated to the theoretical and technological foundations of space-based QKD and optical communications. The programme began with an introduction to quantum information theory by AUTH, followed by sessions on space-based QKD architectures and satellite QKD systems delivered by QRBIT and the Photon and Communication Research Laboratory (PCRL). A comprehensive tutorial on satellite QKD using the QuantLink platform provided participants with an in-depth understanding of end-to-end space quantum links.

Subsequent sessions focused on enabling technologies for space quantum communications, including superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs) by Single Quantum, photonic integrated circuits (PICs) by Ligentec, optical communication technologies through HellasSat, and the GreekObs2OGS initiative presented by Raymetrics. Industrial and space-sector contributions continued with presentations on miniaturised VCSEL and PIC transceivers for inter-satellite optical links by LEO Space, as well as the PeakSat optical CubeSat mission by the AUTH CubeSat Team.

The afternoon sessions highlighted Greece’s Optical Ground Stations (OGSs), with detailed presentations of Holomontas (AUTH), Helmos (National Observatory of Athens), and Skinakas (FORTH / University of Crete), demonstrating their role within HellasQCI and the broader EuroQCI space segment. The day concluded with sessions on quantum random number generators (QRNGs) for space QKD, hands-on experiment theory, and a practical demonstration of the DV-QKD BB84 protocol and a two-bit quantum computer by NTUA and QGreece.

Day 3 – Hands-On QKD Training and Demonstrations (28 November 2025, KEDEK & NOESIS)

The third day focused on applied, hands-on training, allowing participants to directly engage with QKD technologies and operational concepts. Structured laboratory sessions on the building blocks of QKD were conducted in three consecutive modules, guiding participants through practical aspects of QKD system operation, photon-based QKD protocols, and experimental setups. These sessions were designed to reinforce theoretical knowledge acquired during the previous days and to develop operational competence in quantum-secured communications.

The training concluded with a live satellite tracking demonstration at NOESIS, linking the hands-on QKD exercises with real-world space communication scenarios and underlining the importance of integrating terrestrial and space-based quantum infrastructures within HellasQCI and EuroQCI.

Cumulative Training Impact (2023–2025)

Total Attendees: 1,040+ professionals trained

Total Lessons: 75 training modules delivered

Total Laboratory Sessions: 9 hands-on labs conducted

International Engagement: Training spanning 3 Greek cities and 15+ countries

Recurring Partners: PETRUS CSA, Nostradamus, and 20+ NatQCI projects demonstrating sustained

EuroQCI ecosystem engagement

Training Platform Users: 124

HellasQCI Community Registry: 37 Members

Infographics of Training Events - [Athens 2023](#) - [Crete 2024](#) - [Thessaloniki 2025](#)

TRAINING EVENT IN ATHENS 2023

4 DAYS OF TRAINING | **4 LABS** | **20 LESSONS**

16 TRAINERS | **5 SPEAKERS** | **375 ATTENDEES**

TYPE OF PRESENCE:
175 PHYSICAL | **200 ONLINE**

PARTICIPATION PER COUNTRY:

1. GREECE: 81%
2. IRELAND: 6%
3. BELGIUM: 6%
4. UNITED KINGDOM: 2%
5. FRANCE: 1%
6. LUXEMBOURG: 1%
7. NETHERLANDS: 1%
8. CYPRUS: 0.6%
9. MALTA: 0.6%
10. GERMANY: 0.5%
11. POLAND: 0.5%

TRAINING EVENT IN CRETE 2024

2 DAYS OF TRAINING | **1 DAY: EUROQCI DEPLOYMENTS & COOPERATION** | **2 DAY: QKD+PQC FOR CYBERSECURITY**

2 LABS | **2 DEMOS** | **40 SPEAKERS** | **4 PANELS**

415 ATTENDEES | **50+ PEOPLE VISITED THE SKINAKAS OBSERVATORY**

TYPE OF PRESENCE:
126 PHYSICAL | **289 ONLINE**

14 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATED

- GREECE: HELLASQI
- CYPRUS: CYQD
- LUXEMBOURG: LUQKQI
- ESTONIA: ESTQD
- SPAIN: EUROQI SPAIN
- HUNGARY: QD HUNGARY
- POLAND: POLQK Q
- AUSTRIA: QD-CAI
- MALTA: FISH
- PORTUGAL: PTQD
- ROMANIA: ROMQD
- ITALY: THIN QUANTUM
- SWITZERLAND: QUANTIQUE
- NETHERLANDS: SINGLE QUANTUM

TRAINING EVENT IN THESSALONIKI 2025

3 DAYS OF TRAINING | **3 LABS** | **40 SPEAKERS**

1 ST DAY: HIGH LEVEL QKD policy & EuroQCI vision @ HELLAS | **2 ND DAY: THEORY Space QKD @ UNIDEA** | **3 RD DAY: HANDS ON QKD and QKD BB4 protocol @ QKDplus**

250 ATTENDEES | **150 ONLINE** | **100 PHYSICAL**

11 NatQCI's | **PETRUS^Q / NOSTRADAMUS**

15 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATED

- AUSTRIA: QD-CAI
- BULGARIA: BQDQ
- CYPRUS: CYQD
- ESTONIA: ESTQD
- GREECE: HELLASQI
- IRELAND: IRLQDQI
- HUNGARY: QD Hungary
- ITALY: THIN Quantum
- LUXEMBOURG: LUQKQI
- NETHERLANDS: Single Quantum B.V.
- ROMANIA: ROMQD
- SPAIN: EuroQI Spain
- SWEDEN: SWEQD
- SWITZERLAND: Ligette
- UK: University of Strathclyde

11. Annex 2 – Agendas of Training Events

11.1 HellasQCI Training Athens 2023

HellasQCI Four-Day Training Event

18-19 & 21-22 September 2023

National Technical University of Athens

Zografou campus

Program of the Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems

1st Day Training - September 18th, 2023

Welcoming Session

(In this session spoken Language will be Greek)

Moderator: Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist, Bousias Media

Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library

Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/NkcFx7woMTUMNc2q9>

08:30- 09:00	Registration
09:00 – 09:10	Welcoming Remarks by Prof. Konstantinos Karantzas, Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance
09:10 – 09:20	Welcoming Remarks by Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.
09:20 – 09:25	Welcoming Remarks by the European Commission (video message)
09:25 – 09:40	Keynote speech “Quantum Technologies - QKD Landscape in Europe” by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris
09:40 – 09:50	“HellasQCI project overview and synergies with EuroQCI” by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A.

This project is co-funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 10101506

HellasQCI - Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Greece

09:50 – 09:55	“Overview of Four Day HellasQCI Training” by Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH
09:55 – 10:10	Q&A
10:10 – 10:25	Coffee Break

Second Session:

(Spoken Language will be English)

Moderator: Yiannis Yianoulis, NTUA

Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library

Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/NkcFx7woMTUMNc2q9>

10:25 – 11:00	Eleni Diamanti, CNRS CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris Plenary Session
11:00 – 11:30	George Nikolopoulos, FORTH Basic Principles of QKD
11:30 – 12:15	Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, AUTH QRNGs
12:15 – 13:00	George Kanellos, NKUA QKD Networks
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 14:45	Giannis Giannoulis, NTUA/GRNET From billion photons to single photon experimental setups

This project is co-funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 101019734

14:45 – 15:05	Ilias Balampanis, Space Hellas SA QKD with Raspberry PI's as encryptors/decryptors
15:05 – 15:30	Homer Papadopoulos, NCSRDI QKD with PQC for a Healthcare use case
15:30 – 15:45	Deirdre Kilbane, WIT IrelandQCI
15:45 – 16:00	Konstantinos Katzis, EUC CyQCI
16:00 – 16:15	Piotr Rydlichowski, PSNC PIONIER- Q
16:15-16:45	Conclusions and Discussion (Q&A)

2nd Day Training - September 19th, 2023

(Spoken Language will be English)

Moderator: Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, AUTH

Location: NTUA Zografou Campus, Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library

Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/NkcFx7woMTUMNc2q9>

09:00 – 10:00	Aris Stathis, Argiris Ntanos, NTUA/GRNET Theoretical background and equipment description for hands-on experiments
10:00 – 10:45	Nikos Lyras, Argiris Ntanos, NTUA/GRNET QKD in Space, satellite-to-ground QKD links
10:45 -11:00	Coffee Break
Change Room: Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL)	
Directions: https://goo.gl/maps/4CyFnLFENcgkX3GN9	

Co-funded by
the European Union

This project is co-funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 10101501.

HellasQCI - Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Greece

<p>11:00 -13:00</p>	<p>Hands On Experience @ NTUA</p> <p>Operating Principle of Single Photon Avalanche Detectors (SPAD)</p> <p>Coherent Light: Poissonian Photon statistics and single photon interference</p> <p>Generation, transmission and detection of encoded single-photons over a dark fiber</p> <p>Transmission and detection of single- photons over free space</p> <p>Coexistence of classical and quantum signals over converged fiber/FSO link</p>
<p>13:00 – 14:00</p>	<p>Lunch Break</p>
<p>14:00 – 17:00</p>	<p>Hands-On Experience @ NKUA</p> <p>Optical Communications and Photonics Technology Laboratory (Room Y2)</p> <p>National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Department of Informatics and Telecommunications Panepistimiopolis, Ilisia Athens, 16122</p> <p>https://www.di.uoa.gr/department/contact-location</p>

This project is co-funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 101017581

Program of the Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)

3rd Day Training - September 21st, 2023: Introduction to cryptography
Lectures and hands on experience

(Spoken Language will be English)

Moderator: Harry Manifavas, FORTH

Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library

Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/NkcFx7woMTUMNc2q9>

09:00 - 09:15	Welcome Session
09:15 – 10:15	Harry Manifavas, FORTH Cybersecurity and the role of Cryptography The Weakest Link Property The Adversarial Setting Cryptography Pitfalls Security and Other Design Criteria Security Strength levels
10:15 - 11:00	Harry Manifavas, FORTH Basic cryptographic primitives Symmetric Cryptography Public Key Cryptography Cryptographic Hash Functions Applications of cryptography in real life
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee Break
11:15 – 12:00	Harry Manifavas, FORTH

This project is funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 10101586

HellasQCI - Quantum Communication Infrastructure for Greece

	<p>Cryptographic Attacks and Failures Ciphertext-Only and Known-Plaintext Attacks Brute Force Attack Cryptographic key length Recommendations Public Key Algorithms Security The Factoring Problem Man-in-The-Middle and Replay Attacks Cryptographic Failures: Case Studies</p>
12:00 - 13:00	<p>Emmanouil Papadogiannakis, FORTH</p> <p>Demonstrations</p> <p>Attacking a social network</p> <p>Bypassing authentication</p>
13:00- 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 17:00	<p>Emmanouil Papadogiannakis, FORTH</p> <p>Practice session: labs and exercises</p> <p>Exploiting cryptographic failures</p> <p>Cipher misuse</p> <p>Crypto misconfiguration</p>

4th Day Training - September 22nd, 2023: Introduction to Post Quantum Cryptography and Quantum Key Distribution

Lectures and hands on experience

(Spoken Language will be English)

Moderator: Homer Papadopoulos, NCSRDI

Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library

Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/NkcFx7woMTUMNc2q9>

09:00 – 10:00	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Introduction to Post-Quantum Cryptography Quantum Computing Threat Landscape for Symmetric and Public-Key Cryptography Challenges: Retrospective Decryption, Shor's and Grover's Algorithms Quantum Computing Threat Mitigation Post-quantum Cryptography NIST PQC Standardization Effort PQC Transition Recommendations and Cryptographic Agility</p>
10:00 – 11:00	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Introduction to QKD Quantum Cryptography and Quantum Encryption QKD Use Cases QKD Requirements, Security and Protocols Attacks and Limitations Challenges and Criticism Quantum Random Number Generators</p>
11:00 – 11:15	<p><i>Coffee Break</i></p>

This project is cofunded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme grant agreement No. 101019341

11:15 – 12:00	<p>Homer Papadopoulos, NCSRD</p> <p>Integrating QKD into the existing Cryptographic Landscape: Addressing Challenges in Practical Deployments of QKD and Quantum-Safe Cryptography, and Exploring Current Trends</p> <p>QKD standardization efforts and challenges</p> <p>EuroQCI</p>
12:00 - 13:00	<p>Antonis Korakis, George Balaskas, Homer Papadopoulos NCSRD</p> <p>Demonstrations</p> <p>Extract keys from a QKD device.</p> <p>Digital signatures with PQC algorithms</p> <p>Encrypt files with PQC algorithms</p> <p>Enable computations on encrypted data without decryption.</p>
13:00- 14:00	<p><i>Lunch Break</i></p>
14:00 – 17:00	<p>Antonis Korakis, George Balaskas, Homer Papadopoulos NCSRD</p> <p>Practice session: labs and exercises</p> <p>Walk through step-by-step instructions for setting up the encryptor and key retrieval from the QKD device. Encrypt your files with AES 256.</p> <p>Set up your own digital signatures using PQC Dilithium library to authenticate yourself to the encryptor.</p> <p>Encrypt your files with PQC Kyber's encryption methods to access the encryptor.</p>

11.2 HellasQCI Training Crete Sep 2024

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security

AGENDA 4 SEPTEMBER, 2024

Programme of the 3rd Training Event on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) for Cyber Security

1st Day Training - September 4th, 2024 (Moderator: Ilias Papastamatou, GRNET)

09:00-09:15	Registration
09:15-09:45	Welcome Remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Athanasios Paktasos, Ministry of Digital Governance • Dimitrios Katsianis, Deputy Chairman, Board of Directors, GRNET • Nektarios Taverarakis, Chairman, Board of Directors, FORTH • Dimitris Pichoussakis, Vice-Chairman, Board of Directors, FORTH • Fabiana Da FINEY, European Commission
09:45-09:50	Overview of the Two-Day HellasQCI Training Evangelos Markatos, FORTH
09:50-10:35	Keynote speech Hannes Hübel, AIT
10:35-10:45	HellasQCI project overview and synergies with EuroQCI Ilias Papastamatou, GRNET
10:45-11:00	Coffee Break
11:00-11:20	EuroQCI Projects PETERUS Romischer Sebastian, AIT NOSTRADAMUS Hannes Hübel, AIT
11:20-12:20	National QCIs (panel) Panel Theme: Challenges ahead on the road to EuroQCI Moderator: George Kanellos, NKUA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CYQCI, Cyprus Kyriacos Kalli / Konstantinos Katsis • ESTQCI, Estonia Ingrid Linna • PRISM, Malta, Johann Birfija • PTQCI, Portugal, Catarina Bastos • RONAQCI, Romania, Alin Bogdan
12:20-12:40	Why QKD? Harry Mantavias, FORTH

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security

AGENDA 4 SEPTEMBER, 2024

12:40-13:20	Lunch break
13:20-14:10	National QCIs (panel) Panel Theme: Challenges ahead on the road to EuroQCI Moderator: Evangelia Athanasaki, GRNET <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QCI CAT, Austria, Sebastian Ramacher • EuroQCI Spain, Andrea Gorní • LUX4QCI, Luxembourg, Justas Ur Rehman • PIONIER-O, Poland, Piotr Rydlichowski • QCI-Hungary, Hungary, János Mohácsi
14:10-14:30	QKD Architecture: Quantum Layer Giannis Giannoulis, NTUA
14:30-14:50	QKD Architecture: Key Management Layer George Kanellos, NKUA
14:50-15:10	QKD Architecture: Application Layer Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR-D

Organizers of the 3rd Training Event

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Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security

AGENDA 4 SEPTEMBER, 2024

15:10-16:10	Space session (panel) Panel Theme: Space: the final frontier for QKD? Moderator: Vassilis Charalambous, FORTH & UoC & EUC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giannis Giannoulis, NTUA • Konstantinos Katsis, CYQCI • Menios Tsiganis, AUTH • Vasilis Vartas, Raymetrics • Wolf von Kitzing, FORTH • Manolis Xilouris, NOA
16:10-16:20	Coffee Break
16:20-17:20	Business session / Commercial solutions Moderator: Konstantinos Tsimvrakidis, Petros Papadropoulos <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ThinkQuantum, Simone Capello • ID Quantique, Peyman Parahi • Single Quantum, Alki Athanasiadou
17:20	End of day 1

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Cyber Security

AGENDA 5 SEPTEMBER, 2024

2nd Day Training - September 5th, 2024 (Moderator: Evangelos Markatos, FORTH)

09:30-10:00	Introduction to PQC, PQC Transition Harry Mantavias, FORTH
10:00-10:30	Authentication in QKD Giorgos Nikolopoulos, FORTH
10:30-11:15	"Demo of QKD Networks" Giorgos Kanellos, NKUA (video)
11:15-11:30	Coffee Break
11:30-12:15	Extracting and Managing Keys from QKD to Enhance Cryptographic Techniques for File Encryption (Lab) Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR-D (hands on)
12:15-13:00	QKD-PQC: Securing Key Transfers for Application Layer Utilization Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR-D
13:00-14:00	Lunch break
14:00-14:45	Experiment Polarisation-Encoded QKD in Lab Aristeidis Stathis, NTUA Argiris Nianos, NTUA Kostas Vyrosimos, AUTH
14:45-15:00	Demo of Polarisation-Encoded QKD in (Virtual) Lab Aristeidis Stathis, NTUA Argiris Nianos, NTUA Kostas Vyrosimos, AUTH
15:05-15:50	HellasQCI Use Cases Cybersecurity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Towards Software-Defined QKD Networks Georgios Gardikas, SPACeHellas • Quantum Cryptography implementation in Refinery campus Dionysios Vythoulkas, Motor Oil Hellas
15:50-16:00	End of Day 2
17:00	Visit to Skinakas Observatory

Organizers of the 3rd Training Event

In the framework of HellasQCI

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HellasQCI Project has received funding under the G.A.No. 101091504

11.3 QCI Days

Agenda

Date: 28 – 30 April 2025
Location: Eugenides Foundation
387, Syggrou Ave., 17564, P. Faliro, Greece

1st Day - 28 April 2025: Securing the Digital Future: Quantum Key Distribution & Beyond

<p>08:30 09:15 Registration & Coffee</p> <p>09:15 10:30 Opening Session: The Future of Secure Communication in Europe Dimitris Papastergiou - Minister of Digital Governance (Greece) Konstantinos Karatzalos - Secretary General of Telecommunications & Post (Greece) Aristeidis Sotiropoulos - GRNET - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology Vicente Martin - Universidad Politecnica de Madrid Martin Stierle - AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Ana Rosa Bofill Morientes - Ministry of Digital Transformation (Spain) Michael Wiesmüller - Federal Ministry of Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure (Austria)</p> <p>10:30 10:40 Demo Presentation George T. Kanellos - National & Kapodistrian University of Athens</p> <p>10:40 11:25 Coffee Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>11:25 11:50 Keynote Artur Ekert - University of Oxford and CQT Singapore</p> <p>11:50 12:20 Panel Discussion (Moderation: Dimitris Mallas)</p> <p>12:20 13:00 The Security Perspective of QKD Petrus State of Play: Keith Elder - Deutsche Telekom Nostradamus: Hannes Hübel - AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Evangelos Zacharakis - Centre for Technological Support, Development and Innovation Panagiotis Akoulianos - Hellenic National Defence General Staff</p> <p>13:00 13:30 Panel Discussion (Moderation: Dimitris Mitropoulos)</p>	<p>13:30 15:00 Lunch Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>15:00 16:00 Large Networks Deployments HellasQCI (Greece): Ilias Papastamatiou - GRNET QCI-CAT (Austria): Sebastian Ramacher - AIT EuroQCI Spain: Andrea Gorni - ICFO Pionier-Q (Poland): Piotr Rydlichowski - PSNC QCI.DK (Denmark): Dev Nulff - DTU Q-net-Q (Germany): Thomas Hühn - HS Nordhausen Q&A Session</p> <p>16:00 16:30 Coffee Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>16:30 17:20 QKD Use Cases PTQCI (Portugal): Catarina Bastos - Indra Deimos CZQCI (Czech Republic): Jan Bouda - Cybersecurity Hub Be-QCI (Belgium): Emmanuel De Vinck - Belnet SIQUID (Slovenia): Anton Rainsak and Lara Ulcakar - University of Ljubljana RehaQCI (Romania): George Pantelimon Popescu - Politehnica Bucharest Q&A Session</p> <p>17:20 17:30 Closing Day 1 & Invitation to Demo & Presentation Sponsorships</p> <p>17:30 18:30 Demo & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>18:30 Reception</p>
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Agenda

Date: 28 – 30 April 2025
Location: Eugenides Foundation
387, Syggrou Ave., 17564, P. Faliro, Greece

2nd Day - 29 April 2025: Europe's Quantum Industry & Ecosystem Development

<p>09:00 09:30 Registration & Coffee</p> <p>09:30 09:50 International Year of Quantum Science and Technology Enrique Sanchez - Forschungszentrum Jülich</p> <p>09:50 10:45 Industrialisation of QKD QUCI: David Marcuende - QuIC Equi: Francesco Stocco - Telsy MDI-QUEEN: Remon Berrevoets - Q*Bird QKISS: Philippe Grangier - CNRS Quantex: Sebastian Echeverry - LuxQuanta SECRET: Ulrich Esenann - KEEQuant eCausis: Anna Kaminska - Creotech</p> <p>10:45 11:10 Panel Discussion (Moderation: Laura Ortiz)</p> <p>11:10 11:40 Coffee Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>11:40 12:15 Company Pitches ADAPTIT Fortinet NOKIA IDQuantique ThinkQuantum</p> <p>12:15 13:05 Innovations for Quantum-secured Networks siQCI (Slovakia): Džeylan Aktas - Slovak Academy of Science QCI-Ned (The Netherlands): Alexander Schetanga - QDNL EstQCI (Estonia): Ingrid Linna - RISK PRISM (Malta): Johann Briffa - University of Malta IrelandQCI (Ireland): Deirdre Kilbane - Walton Institute Q&A Session</p>	<p>13:05 14:35 Lunch Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>14:35 15:25 QKD Use Cases BGQCI (Bulgaria): Lachezar Georgiev - Technical University of Sofia CroQCI (Croatia): Martin Lonsane - Ruđer Bosković Institute NQCI.S (Sweden): Pascal Lefebvre - KTH Royal Institute of Technology NaQCI.fi (Finland): Kari Seppänen - VTT FranceQCI (France): Patrice Robert - Orange Q&A Session</p> <p>15:25 15:55 Company Pitches fragmentix Storage Solutions X-NET Qoolnet Mercury Cybersecurity Limited AUREA TECHNOLOGY Vector Technologies Ltd</p> <p>15:55 16:30 Coffee Break & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>16:30 17:35 Secure Connectivity from Earth to Space EAGLE-1 State of Play: Thomas Baumer - SES GEO-QKD: Pedro Pinto - Hispasat CYQCI (Cyprus): Cyprus University of Technology QCI-Hungary (Hungary): Olah Kitti - University Budapest Lux4QCI (LUX): Seid Koudia - University of Luxembourg QUID (Italy): Marco Gramaglia - INRIM Q&A Session</p> <p>17:35 17:45 Closing Day 2 & Invitation to Demo</p> <p>17:45 18:30 Demo & Exhibition & Posters</p> <p>18:30 19:10 Planetarium</p> <p>19:10 Reception</p>
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QCI DAYS
ATHENS 2025

Agenda

Date: 28 – 30 April 2025
Location: Eugenides Foundation
387, Syggrou Ave., 17564, P. Faliro, Greece

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF
Quantum Science
and Technology

3rd Day - 30 April 2025: Deployment Strategies & User Opportunities

08:30 09:00 Registration & Coffee

09:00 09:45 Building the HellasQCI Community
General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post (Greece)
GRNET - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology
NCSR-D - National Center For Scientific Research Demokritos
NKUA - National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
NTUA - National Technical University of Athens
ADAPTTT
FORTINET
SPACE HELLAS

09:45 10:10 Panel Discussion (Moderation: Sophia Papathanasopoulou)

10:10 10:35 Keynote
Eleni Diamanti - French National Centre for Scientific Research

10:35 11:05 Coffee Break & Exhibition & Posters

11:05 12:00 From Theory to Practical Security
Towards a European QCI Standardisation Strategy: Oskar Van Deventer - TNO
Towards National QKD Evaluation and Certification
Ulrich Seyfarth - Bearing Point
How to Keep the Most Dangerous and Sensitive Data Private
Werner Strasser - fragmentIX
The Hybrid State-of-Play: How to Securely Combine Quantum and Post-Quantum Technologies: Christoph Striecks - AIT
QKDise Your Applications: Niki Dürk and Christoph Döbert - X-Net and Zynd

12:00 13:05 Listening to the Market: End-User Expectation
How to Underpin a Quantum-Secure Economy: Marta Buffa - Nokia
Jean-Sebastien Pignon - IDQ
Juan Morales Saenz - Telefonica
Digital Projects, including Quantum and Post-Quantum Initiatives: Vithoukas Dionisios - MotorOil
Alejandra Beghelli Zapata - British Telecom
QKD Implementation - Concept to Execution: Andreas Neuhold - CANCOM

13:05 13:30 Panel Discussion (Moderation: Eleni Diamanti)

13:30 13:45 Closing QCIDays Athens 2025 (Dimitris Katsianis - GRNET)

13:45 14:45 Lunch Break & Exhibition & Posters

14:45 16:45 PETRUS Workshop

DEP1 Projects

MDI-QUEEN	SEQRET	QKISS
eCausis	EQUO	QUARTER

DEP2 Projects

HellasQCI (Greece)	skQCI (Slovakia)	CYQCI (Republic of Cyprus)
QCI-CAT (Austria)	QCINed (The Netherlands)	QCIHungary (Hungary)
EuroQCI Spain	EstQCI (Estonia)	Lux4QCI (Luxembourg)
Pionier-Q (Poland)	FranceQCI (France)	QUID (Italy)
QCI.DK (Denmark)	PRISM (Malta)	CZQCI (Czech Republic)
Q-net-Q (Germany)	IrelandQCI (Ireland)	RoNaQCI (Romania)
PTQCI (Portugal)	BGQCI (Bulgaria)	SIQUID (Slovenia)
Be-QCI (Belgium)	CroQCI (Croatia)	NaQCI.fi (Finland)
	NQCI.s (Sweden)	

Exhibitors in the Showroom & Supplier Pitches

Adaptit	Quantum Industries	fragmentIX
Nokia	Toshiba	X-NET
Fortinet	Heqa Security	Qoolnet
IDQuantique	QTI	Mercury Cybersecurity
ThinkQuantum	Vector Technologies	AUREA TECHNOLOGY
Keequant	QTLabs	Q-DYNAMICS
Luxquanta		Callabs

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Ministry of Digital Governance

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11.4 Focused Training on Entanglement Photon Pair Sources

Online Training: Meccanica – EPPS 22 October 2024

Agenda

Time	Topic
13:00	Welcome
13.15	Introduction to QKD principles
13.30	Overview of the entangled photon source and BBM92 protocol
14.00	System architecture: laser and component connectivity
14.15	Key system parameters (source & laser): roles and impact
14.30	Theoretical overview of data metrics: heralding, key rate, QBER, visibility, ...
15.00	Q&A
15:15	Coffee break
15.30	Guided walkthrough: software structure and logic
16.00	Configuration options and parameter overview
16.30	Discussion of different configuration scenarios
16.45	Q&A
17.00	End of meeting

11.5 Winter School Thessaloniki

AGENDA
HELLASQCI WINTER SCHOOL
TRAINING WORKSHOP

26 NOVEMBER, 2025

1st Day Training:
High level QKD policy and EuroQCI vision @ KEDEA

09:00 - 09:30	Registration
09:30 - 09:50	Welcome Remarks Ministry of Digital Governance and Artificial Intelligence, AUTH University, GRNET, Hellenic Space Center
09:50 - 10:00	Overview of 3-day HellasQCI Winter School
10:00 - 11:00	Keynote Speech
11:00 - 11:30	BREAK
11:30 - 11:50	PETRUS NOSTRADAMUS
11:50 - 12:50	Session 1 National QCs HellasQCI, Lux4QCI, CYQCI, BGQCI, IrelandQCI
12:50 - 13:20	HellasQCI In Practice Quantum Network Demonstrations

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AGENDA
HELLASQCI WINTER SCHOOL
TRAINING WORKSHOP

26 NOVEMBER, 2025

13:20 - 14:30	LUNCH BREAK
14:30 - 15:30	Session 2 National QCs QCI-CAT, EuroQCI Spain, EstQCI, NQCIS
15:30 - 17:00	Industrial QKD Session: IDQ, ThinkQuantum, ZERO3, NOKIA, Single Quantum, QRBIT, QUBITECH
17:00 - 18:00	Reception

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AGENDA
HELLASQCI WINTER SCHOOL
TRAINING WORKSHOP

27 NOVEMBER, 2025

2nd Day Training:
Theory for Space QKD @KEDEA

09:00 - 10:00	Introduction to Quantum Information Theory AUTH
10:00 - 10:30	Towards Entangled Photons in Space PCRL, QRBIT
10:30 - 11:00	Introduction to Space QKD PCRL, QRBIT
11:00 - 11:30	BREAK
11:30 - 11:50	Enabling Quantum Links in Space through SNSPDs Technology Single Quantum
11:50 - 12:10	PICs for Space Liganlec
12:10 - 12:30	Optical Communications Technologies through Space HellasSat
12:30 - 12:50	GreekObs2OGS Raymetrics
12:50 - 13:10	Miniaturized VCSEL and PIC transceivers for high data rate intra- and inter-satellite optical links LEO Space

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AGENDA
HELLASQCI WINTER SCHOOL
TRAINING WORKSHOP

27 NOVEMBER, 2025

13:10 - 13:30	PeakSat. AUTH's Optical Communications CubeSat Mission AUTH CubeSat Team
13:30 - 14:30	LUNCH BREAK
14:30 - 14:50	Cholomonitis Presentation AUTH
14:50 - 15:10	Chelmos Presentation NOA
15:10 - 15:30	Skinakas Presentation FORTH, UoC
15:30 - 16:00	QRNGs for Space QKD AUTH
16:00 - 16:30	Theory of Hands On Experiments PCRL, QRBIT
16:30 - 16:45	BREAK
16:45 - 17:30	BB84 Demonstration and 2-bit Quantum Computer NTUA, QGreece

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HOCI
HELLENIC ORGANIZATION FOR QUANTUM INFORMATION COMMUNICATIONS

AGENDA
HELLASQCI WINTER SCHOOL
TRAINING WORKSHOP

28 NOVEMBER, 2025

3rd Day Training:
Hands on QKD training @ KEDEK & NOESIS

09:00 - 11:00	Hands on - Building Blocks for QKD I
11:00 - 11:30	BREAK
11:30 - 13:30	Hands on - Building Blocks for QKD II
13:30 - 15:00	LUNCH BREAK
15:00 - 17:00	Demonstration of real Alice-Bob QKD link
17:00 - 17:30	BREAK
17:30 - 18:15	Satellite Tracking Demo at NOESIS

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Under the auspices of: gmiel, HELLASQCI, KEDEK, NOESIS, HELLENIC REPUBLIC, HELLENIC NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS, HELLENIC NATIONAL METEOROLOGICAL SERVICE, HELLENIC NATIONAL RADIOASTRONOMY CENTER, HELLENIC NATIONAL SPACE CENTER, HELLENIC NATIONAL TELEVISION AND RADIO CENTER, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF POLYTECHNIC EDUCATION, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MARINE EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF AQUACULTURE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF VETERINARY MEDICINE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF FORESTRY, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TOULON, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF CRETE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF SPARTA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TRIESTE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PERUSSIA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF URBINO, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MACERATA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF ANCONA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF FERRARA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PADOVA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF VERONA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TRENTO, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TRIESTE, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PERUSSIA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF URBINO, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MACERATA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF ANCONA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF FERRARA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF PADOVA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF VERONA, HELLENIC NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF TRENTO

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